

SOME NUMERICAL METHODS AND ANALYSIS OF A CLASS OF QUANTUM STOCHASTIC DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this work was carried out by **SAMUEL OLUWASEYI OGUNDIPE** with matriculation number **231045**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) in the Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, under my supervision.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my **Grandma** and my **parents**, whose love, prayers and support have been the foundation of my academic journey.

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First and foremost, I sincerely give all glory, honour, and adoration to the Almighty God, the source of wisdom, knowledge, and understanding. His grace, mercy, and strength have been my sustaining power throughout the course of this programme and the successful completion of this project.

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ABSTRACT

The classical stochastic differential equation given as

$$dX(t, \omega) = a(t, X) dt + b(t, X) dQ(t), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T], \quad (1)$$

where the driving process $Q(t)$ is a martingale, and a and b are adapted functionals. There has been several numerical schemes developed for it, where each exhibits distinct stability and convergence properties depending on the nature of the driving process and the functional space of the solution.

A generalization of this equation is the quantum stochastic differential equation introduced by Hudson and Parthasarathy, expressed as

$$dX(t) = E(t, X(t)) d\Lambda_\pi(t) + F(t, X(t)) dA_f^\dagger(t) + G(t, X(t)) dA_g(t) + H(t, X(t)) dt, \quad (2)$$

where E, F, G , and H are stochastic operator-valued functions defined on a Hilbert space. In 1992, Ekhaquere reformulated this equation in an equivalent form involving the non-classical differential equation stated as;

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = P(t, X(t)) \langle \eta, \xi \rangle, \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T], \quad (3)$$

which represents an ordinary differential equation of non-classical type.

The stochastic process $X(t)$ acts as a densely defined linear operator on a tensor product of two Hilbert spaces, one of which is the Boson Fock space. The vectors η

and ξ belong to a dense subset of this tensor product Hilbert space, and the mapping $(\eta, \xi) \mapsto P(t, X)(\eta, \xi)$ defines a sesquilinear form for each fixed pair (t, X) .

We analyze the numerical approximation of the QSDE using its equivalent inner-product form. The numerical investigation employs three principal methods: the **Lagrangian Quadrature Method**, the **Linear Multistep Scheme**, and the **Newton-Cotes Method**. Each method is carefully designed to ensure the consistency, stability, and convergence of the approximate solution $X(t)$ toward the exact stochastic process. These schemes are implemented using **Python programming language**, which provides a flexible and efficient computational environment for testing the proposed algorithms.

Our computational results show that the developed schemes generalize Taylor-type approximations of Itô processes under weak convergence criteria. The proposed algorithms exhibit numerical stability and yield results that compare favorably with analytical benchmarks. Furthermore, the implementation avoids direct approximation of the driving quantum processes, thereby preserving the natural adaptation of the schemes to quantum dynamical models.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The study of stochastic differential equations (SDEs) has long been central to the mathematical modeling of systems influenced by randomness. Over the years, numerous researchers have developed and analyzed numerical schemes for solving classical stochastic differential equations of the form

$$dX(t, \omega) = H(t, X)dt + F(t, X)dQ(t), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T], \quad (1.1)$$

where the driving process $Q(t)$ is a martingale, and H and F are assumed to be sufficiently smooth and deterministic functions. Each of the developed schemes exhibits specific characteristics depending on the form of the driving process and the structure of the solution space associated with equation (1.1).

A generalization of the classical equation (1.1) is found in the quantum domain through the **quantum stochastic differential equation (QSDE)** introduced by Hudson and Parthasarathy. This equation takes the form

$$\begin{aligned}
dX(t) &= E(t, X(t))d\Lambda_\pi(t) + F(t, X(t))dA_f^\dagger(t) + G(t, X(t))dA_g(t) + H(t, X(t))dt, \\
X(t_0) &= X_0, \quad \text{almost all } t \in [t_0, T].
\end{aligned}
\tag{1.2}$$

where E, F, G , and H are stochastic operator-valued functions defined in a suitable class of stochastic processes. These coefficients determine how the quantum stochastic integrals are taken with respect to the creation, annihilation, and gauge processes, denoted by $A_f^\dagger(t)$, $A_g(t)$, and $\Lambda_\pi(t)$ respectively. These integrator processes are formally defined on a Hilbert space framework, and equation (1.2) consequently involves *unbounded linear operators* acting on such a space.

It is essential to emphasize that quantum stochastic calculus provides several advantages over the classical Itô calculus. The introduction of QSDEs allows the formulation of stochastic models in a **noncommutative quantum** framework, where random variables are replaced by operator-valued processes. This approach not only extends standard probability theory to quantum settings but also enables a deeper understanding of stochastic processes in quantum mechanics. Applications include the modeling of quantum control systems, open quantum systems, and stochastic evolutions in Fock space.

Quantum stochastic differential equations of the type (1.2) commonly appear as mathematical models describing diverse quantum dynamical phenomena and control processes. They serve as fundamental tools in quantum stochastic control theory and quantum filtering. However, due to their operator-valued nature, obtaining analytical solutions to such equations is often challenging. As a result, it becomes imperative to

construct reliable **numerical approximation schemes** capable of yielding accurate and stable solutions.

A notable property of equation (1.2) is that it reduces to the classical Itô stochastic differential equation (1.1) when the quantum effects are neglected within a simple **Fock space**. In such a setting, the Itô process may be interpreted as a multiplication operator-valued process acting on this Hilbert space. Despite the significant analytical progress made in studying QSDEs, there remains a relative scarcity of numerical investigations in the literature compared to the classical case.

In the work of **Ekhaguere (1992)**, equation (1.2) was reformulated into an equivalent differential form expressed as

$$\frac{d}{dt}\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle = P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T], \quad (1.3)$$

where $\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle$ denotes the matrix elements in a dense subset of the tensor product Hilbert space, and $P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ is a sesquilinear form for fixed (t, X) . This formulation transforms the QSDE into an **ordinary differential equation of non-classical type**, making it more amenable to numerical treatment.

The stochastic process $X(t)$ is thus viewed as a densely defined linear operator acting on the tensor product of two Hilbert spaces, one of which is typically the Boson Fock space wherein lies the noise processes. The equivalent formulation introduced by Ekhaguere not only facilitates a better understanding of QSDEs but also provides a pathway to develop consistent, stable, and convergent numerical methods.

The motivation for this study stems from the increasing role of QSDEs in quantum

optics, open quantum systems, and quantum information theory, where understanding quantum stochastic evolution is crucial. However, their noncommutative structure and operator-valued nature pose significant analytical and numerical challenges. These include difficulties in discretization, ensuring operator stability, and maintaining convergence within nonclassical Hilbert spaces. Therefore, there is a need for efficient numerical methods capable of approximating the dynamics of QSDEs without compromising their intrinsic quantum properties.

This work focuses on the construction and analysis of numerical schemes for the approximate solution of the quantum stochastic differential equation (1.2) through its equivalent form (1.3). The study employs various numerical approaches, including the **Lagrangian Quadrature Method**, the **Linear Multistep Scheme**, and the **Newton–Cotes Method**. These schemes are designed to preserve the structural and noncommutative features inherent in QSDEs while ensuring computational stability and convergence. The goal is to establish robust numerical techniques that bridge the gap between theoretical formulations and practical computation in quantum stochastic analysis.

This work is organized into five chapters. **Chapter One** introduces the background of the study, highlighting the motivation for investigating quantum stochastic differential equations. It discusses the historical development and relevance of stochastic processes in both classical and quantum settings, emphasizing the importance of modeling random evolutions in quantum systems. The chapter also presents the statement of the problem, objectives of the study, significance, scope, and organization of the entire work.

Chapter Two presents a systematic literature review, establishing the background and theoretical foundations for the study. It examines the existence, uniqueness, and analytical properties of Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations (QSDEs), surveys numerical methods for classical and stochastic differential equations, and narrows the focus to the numerical approximation of QSDEs. A comparative analysis and discussion of stability considerations are provided, culminating in the identification of key research gaps and the primary motivation for this work.

Chapter Three details the essential mathematical preliminaries. It begins with fundamental concepts in operator theory, Fock spaces, exponential vectors, and relevant function spaces. The core framework of quantum stochastic integration is then constructed, covering foundational processes, integrators, and the fundamental theorem of quantum stochastic calculus. This framework is extended, and the formal definitions for Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations (QSDEs), along with the properties of their coefficient maps, are provided. The chapter concludes by discussing the conditions for the existence, uniqueness, and stability of solutions to QSDEs.

Chapter Four adapts Newton-Cotes numerical methods to the quantum stochastic setting. It introduces the general Newton-Cotes formula and derives the implicit trapezoidal method, first for classical ordinary differential equations and subsequently for QSDEs, detailing its integral approximation, algorithmic predictor-corrector form, and component-wise representation. The chapter then extends this approach to the implicit Simpson's method and its two-step variant for QSDEs. A convergence analysis for these methods, including remarks on initial error, is also presented.

Chapter Five investigates two advanced numerical techniques: the Lagrangian

Quadrature method and Linear Multi-step methods for QSDEs. For the Lagrangian method, the chapter covers the underlying assumptions, the choice of interpolants, the computation of quadrature coefficients, and a thorough error and convergence analysis. For Linear Multi-step methods, it defines the associated linear operator, establishes the order of the method, and provides a detailed convergence analysis, particularly for schemes classified as Class A.

Chapter Six applies the developed theoretical and numerical framework. It formulates Itô-type Stochastic Differential Equations within the quantum stochastic context and conducts comprehensive numerical experiments. The performance of the proposed schemes, including the Trapezoidal, Simpson's, Linear Multi-step, and Lagrangian Quadrature methods, is evaluated and demonstrated through a series of concrete computational examples.

Chapter 2

Systematic Literature Review

The study of quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs) and their numerical approximations has evolved from the broader theories of ordinary differential equations, stochastic calculus, and fuzzy differential equations. The central objective in this area is the construction of reliable, convergent, and computationally efficient numerical schemes for operator-valued stochastic systems defined on tensor products of Hilbert spaces, particularly the Boson Fock space. Over time, the literature has demonstrated a gradual but consistent transition from classical deterministic and stochastic numerical techniques to noncommutative frameworks capable of capturing quantum noise and operator dynamics.

This review systematically examines existing works relevant to the analytical and numerical treatment of fuzzy, stochastic, and quantum stochastic differential equations. The materials surveyed span foundational results in quantum probability and stochastic calculus, classical numerical integration theory, and modern developments in numerical schemes such as Lagrangian quadrature, one-step, multistep, block, and

Simpson-type methods.

2.1 Background and Theoretical Foundations

The mathematical roots of QSDEs lie in classical stochastic differential equations, extensively developed by Itô and later formalized in the works of Friedman (1975) and Protter (1985), who studied existence, uniqueness, and approximation of stochastic processes driven by semimartingales (Friedman, 1975; Protter, 1985). Numerical approximation of SDEs was further advanced by Rümelin (1982), Kloeden and Platen (1992), and Øksendal (1995), who established convergence frameworks and strong and weak approximation schemes for classical stochastic systems (Rümelin, 1982; Kloeden and Platen, 1992; Øksendal, 1995). These studies form the stochastic analogue upon which quantum stochastic methods are constructed.

The extension of stochastic calculus to the quantum domain was pioneered by Hudson and Parthasarathy (1984), who introduced the noncommutative Itô calculus and formulated the Hudson–Parthasarathy equation for quantum stochastic evolutions (Hudson and Parthasarathy, 1984; HP, 1984). Their framework rigorously defined creation, annihilation, and gauge processes on Boson Fock space and established the operator-theoretic foundation of QSDEs. Complementary developments by Parthasarathy (1985, 1992) and Meyer (1993) provided a systematic exposition of Boson stochastic calculus and its applications to quantum probability (Parthasarathy, 1985; Parthasarathy, 1992; Meyer, 1993). Lecture notes and modern introductions, such as Särkkä (2012), Caballero (2015), Evans (2013), and Lawler (2014), have also contributed to making QSDEs more accessible for applied numerical studies (Särkkä,

2012; Caballero, 2015; Evans, 2013; Lawler, 2014).

Meyer (1993) further enriched the theoretical landscape by presenting quantum probability from a probabilistic viewpoint, emphasizing the parallels between classical and quantum stochastic processes and the role of Fock space integration. Additional reviews by Sinha (1995) and Boukas (2006) highlighted applications of quantum stochastic calculus to operator theory, control, and quantum systems engineering (Sinha, 1995; Boukas, 2006). Works by Goodman and Kim (2002) also analyzed exponential martingales and time integrals in quantum stochastic processes, providing insight into Girsanov-type transformations (Goodman and Kim, 2002).

2.2 Existence, Uniqueness, and Analytical Properties of QSDEs

While the Hudson–Parthasarathy framework provides the formal structure of QSDEs, analytical challenges arise when dealing with unbounded operators and domain issues. Ekhaguere (1992) addressed these concerns by studying Lipschitzian quantum stochastic differential inclusions and establishing existence results under suitable continuity conditions (Ekhaguere, 1992).

Fagnola and Wills (2000) introduced the concept of mild solutions for QSDEs, providing sufficient conditions for existence and uniqueness in operator spaces (Fagnola and Wills, 2000). Subsequently, Fagnola (2003) extended these results to QSDEs with unbounded coefficients, ensuring contractivity and preserving domain properties of operators (Fagnola, 2003). These contributions are critical, as they provide the ana-

lytical justification for the convergence of numerical schemes applied to QSDEs.

2.3 Numerical Methods for Classical, Fuzzy, and Stochastic Differential Equations

Classical numerical analysis plays a foundational role in the development of quantum numerical schemes. Early works by Henrici (1962), Dahlquist (1963), Lambert (1991), and Nørsett (1969) established stability and convergence theories for linear multistep methods applied to ordinary differential equations and stiff problems (Henrici, 1962; Dahlquist, 1963; Lambert, 1991; Norsett, 1969).

Quadrature-based numerical integration methods were developed by Stroud (1974), Cheney (1966), Powell (1981), and Olaofe and Mason (1986), providing Newton–Cotes and Simpson-type rules that later influenced stochastic and quantum numerical techniques (Stroud, 1974; Cheney, 1966; Powell, 1981; Olaofe and Mason, 1986). These methods were adapted to uncertain systems through fuzzy differential equations, notably by Moghadam and Dahaghin (2004), who proposed two-step Simpson methods for fuzzy initial value problems (Moghadam and Dahaghin, 2004).

In stochastic contexts, Janicki, Michna, and Weron (1996) examined numerical approximation of SDEs driven by α -stable Lévy motions, highlighting challenges posed by non-Gaussian noise (Janicki et al., 1996). Lecture notes and introductions by Caballero (2015), Särkkä (2012), Evans (2013), and Lawler (2014) also provide modern perspectives on stochastic integration and Euler/Runge–Kutta type methods (Caballero, 2015; Särkkä, 2012; Evans, 2013; Lawler, 2014).

2.4 Numerical Approximation of Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations

A systematic numerical treatment of QSDEs was initiated by Ayoola (1998) in his doctoral thesis, where numerical procedures for Lipschitzian QSDEs were formulated (Ayoola, 1998). Ayoola (2000) subsequently developed convergent multistep schemes for weak solutions of QSDEs, demonstrating that matrix elements of operator-valued solutions could be approximated without explicit simulation of quantum noise (Ayoola, 2000). This approach represented a significant departure from classical stochastic Taylor expansions.

Further advancements were made by Ayoola (2001), who analyzed one-step schemes, including Euler and Runge–Kutta types, proving convergence in locally convex topological spaces (Ayoola, 2001). In Ayoola (2002), Lagrangian quadrature schemes were introduced for computing weak solutions of QSDEs, achieving improved accuracy and stability compared to Euler and two-step methods (Ayoola, 2002). The results demonstrated sensitivity to exponential vector choices and step lengths, underscoring the operator-dependent nature of quantum numerical computations.

Adeyeye (2007) proposed an implicit Simpson’s scheme for QSDEs, which reduced computational overhead by eliminating the need for starting values required in multistep methods (Adeyeye, 2007). Van Handel (2007) provided lecture notes on filtering and stochastic control approaches for QSDEs, complementing multistep and one-step numerical methods (van Handel, 2007). Modern works by Evans (2013) and Lawler (2014) also provide step-by-step methods suitable for simulation of quantum stochas-

tic processes (Evans, 2013; Lawler, 2014).

2.5 Comparative Analysis and Stability Considerations

The collective body of literature reveals a clear methodological evolution from classical quadrature and multistep methods to quantum-adapted numerical schemes. While Euler and basic one-step methods offer simplicity, Lagrangian quadrature schemes provide superior accuracy for weak solutions of QSDEs (Ayoola, 2002). Multistep schemes offer flexibility and computational efficiency, particularly when initialization costs are minimized through implicit formulations (Ayoola, 2000; Adeyeye, 2007).

Stability analysis, originally developed for deterministic systems by Dahlquist (1963) and Lambert (1991), remains relevant in quantum numerical analysis, particularly for stiff QSDEs and unbounded operator coefficients. Analytical works by Fagnola and Wills (2000, 2003) ensure that numerical convergence aligns with the underlying operator-theoretic structure of QSDEs.

2.6 Research Gaps and Motivation

Despite substantial progress, several challenges persist in the numerical analysis of QSDEs. Many existing schemes rely on Lipschitz continuity and boundedness assumptions, limiting their applicability to more realistic quantum systems with non-linear or unbounded coefficients. Error estimation, adaptive step-size control, and higher-order convergence techniques remain underexplored in the quantum setting.

Furthermore, computational dependence on exponential vectors and Fock space parametrization affects reproducibility and scalability. These limitations motivate the present research to develop enhanced numerical schemes with improved robustness, stability, and convergence properties, potentially integrating adaptive quadrature and multi-step strategies within the quantum stochastic framework.

2.7 Conclusion of Review

In summary, the study of **Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations (QSDEs)** represents a significant advancement in understanding stochastic dynamics within quantum systems. These equations extend the framework of classical stochastic differential equations (SDEs) by incorporating quantum noise processes on Hilbert spaces, particularly within the Boson Fock space structure. Unlike classical SDEs, which are driven by Wiener or Poisson processes, QSDEs involve quantum martingales and noncommutative stochastic integrals, thereby reflecting the probabilistic behavior of observables in quantum systems.

The literature in this review reflects a coherent progression from classical numerical analysis and stochastic calculus to specialized numerical methods for QSDEs. Foundational works by Hudson and Parthasarathy (1984), Parthasarathy (1992), and Meyer (1993) established the theoretical backbone of quantum stochastic calculus, while numerical innovations by Ayoola (1998–2002), Adeyeye (2007), and Van Handel (2007) translated these theories into computationally viable schemes. Complementary analytical results by Fagnola and Wills provide rigorous justification for numerical convergence.

The insights gained from these studies form the theoretical and methodological foundation upon which the present research is built, guiding the development of more general, efficient, and reliable numerical methods for quantum stochastic differential equations.

Chapter 3

Preliminaries

3.1 Fundamental Concepts and Structures

3.1.1 Basic Operator Space

Let D be an inner product space and H its Hilbert space completion. We define $L^+(D, H)$ as the collection of all linear operators $X : D \rightarrow H$ such that the domain of the adjoint operator X^* contains D . This space $L^+(D, H)$ forms a vector space under standard operator addition and scalar multiplication.

3.1.2 Fock Space and Exponential Vectors

In quantum theory, systems are often described by a Hilbert space H representing the state space of a single particle. However, in many physical situations, particularly in quantum field theory and quantum probability, the number of particles in the system is not fixed. We therefore require a larger Hilbert space that can accommodate states with any possible number of identical particles. This leads to the concept of a *Fock*

space.

Definition 1 (Fock Space). (*Brennecke, Example 2.4*). Let H be a Hilbert space. The **Fock space** $\mathcal{F}(H)$ over H is defined as the Hilbert space direct sum

$$\mathcal{F}(H) := \mathbb{C} \oplus \bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} H^{\otimes n},$$

where $H^{\otimes n}$ denotes the n -fold tensor product of H . Explicitly, it consists of sequences

$$\psi = (\psi_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0} = (\psi_0, \psi_1, \psi_2, \dots), \quad \psi_0 \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \psi_n \in H^{\otimes n} \text{ for } n \geq 1,$$

satisfying the square-summability condition

$$|\psi_0|^2 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \|\psi_n\|_{H^{\otimes n}}^2 < \infty.$$

The inner product on $\mathcal{F}(H)$ is given by

$$\langle \psi, \varphi \rangle_{\mathcal{F}(H)} = \bar{\psi}_0 \varphi_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \langle \psi_n, \varphi_n \rangle_{H^{\otimes n}}.$$

Definition 2 (Bosonic Fock Space). (*Brennecke, Example 2.6*).

Let H be a Hilbert space. The **bosonic Fock space** (or **symmetric Fock space**) is a subspace of the full Fock space $\mathcal{F}(H)$ consisting only of symmetric tensor components. It is denoted by $\Gamma(H)$ and defined as

$$\Gamma(H) := \bigoplus_{n=0}^{\infty} H^{(n)},$$

where $H^{(0)} = \mathbb{C}$ is the vacuum sector, and for $n \geq 1$,

$$H^{(n)} := (H^{\otimes n})_{\text{sym}}$$

is the **symmetric subspace** of the n -fold tensor product, i.e., the subspace of vectors invariant under any permutation of the tensor factors. Thus,

$$\Gamma(H) = \mathbb{C} \oplus \bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} H^{\otimes n} \subset \mathcal{F}(H).$$

A vector $\psi \in \Gamma(H)$ is a sequence $\psi = (\psi^{(0)}, \psi^{(1)}, \psi^{(2)}, \dots)$ with $\psi^{(n)} \in H^{(n)}$. The inner product is

$$\langle \psi, \phi \rangle_{\Gamma(H)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \langle \psi^{(n)}, \phi^{(n)} \rangle_{H^{(n)}},$$

and the norm condition is $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \|\psi^{(n)}\|_{H^{(n)}}^2 < \infty$.

3.1.3 Exponential vectors

In the context of bosonic Fock spaces, a particularly useful family of vectors are the *exponential vectors* (or *coherent vectors*). For a given single-particle state $f \in H$, the exponential vector $e(f)$ represents a coherent superposition of states with all possible numbers of bosons, each occupying the same single-particle state f .

Definition 3 (Exponential vector). (*Parthasarathy 1985*).

Let H be a Hilbert space and $\Gamma(H)$ the bosonic Fock space over H . For any element $f \in H$, the **exponential vector** $e(f) \in \Gamma(H)$ is defined by

$$e(f) := \bigoplus_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n!}} f^{\otimes n},$$

where $f^{\otimes n}$ denotes the n -fold symmetric tensor product of f with itself, and by convention $f^{\otimes 0} = 1$ (the vacuum scalar). Explicitly,

$$e(f) = 1 \oplus f \oplus \frac{1}{\sqrt{2!}} f^{\otimes 2} \oplus \frac{1}{\sqrt{3!}} f^{\otimes 3} \oplus \dots \in \Gamma(H).$$

Each term $\frac{1}{\sqrt{n!}} f^{\otimes n}$ is an element of the symmetric subspace $H^{(n)} = (H^{\otimes n})_{\text{sym}}$, and can be viewed as the normalized n -particle contribution of the vector f . The factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{n!}}$ ensures proper normalization with respect to the inner product on $\Gamma(H)$.

The exponential vector $e(f)$ represents a superposition of states containing zero, one, two, and arbitrarily many bosons, all occupying the same single-particle state f . Such vectors are central in the description of coherent states in quantum optics and in the construction of quantum stochastic calculus.

The vector $e(0) = 1 \oplus 0 \oplus 0 \oplus \dots$ is called the **vacuum vector** corresponding to the absence of particles. It satisfies $\|e(0)\|_{\Gamma(H)} = 1$.

3.1.4 Properties of Exponential Vectors

The exponential vectors possess several fundamental properties that make them indispensable in the study of Fock spaces. These properties can be found in standard references on quantum stochastic calculus and infinite-dimensional analysis.

(i) Density. The linear span of all exponential vectors,

$$\mathcal{E} = \text{span}\{e(f) : f \in H\},$$

is dense in $\Gamma(H)$. This means that any vector in the Fock space can be approximated arbitrarily closely by a finite linear combination of exponential vectors. In other words, exponential vectors form a total (complete) set in $\Gamma(H)$. This property allows one to define and analyze operators on Fock space simply by specifying their action on exponential vectors.

(ii) Inner Product Formula. For any $f, g \in H$, the inner product of their corresponding exponential vectors is given by the elegant identity

$$\langle e(f), e(g) \rangle = \exp(\langle f, g \rangle).$$

This exponential relationship reflects the deep analytic structure of Fock space and immediately yields the norm relation

$$\|e(f)\|^2 = e^{\|f\|^2}.$$

Consequently, the map $f \mapsto e(f)$ is highly nonlinear but analytic in nature.

(iii) Linear Independence. The family $\{e(f) : f \in H\}$ is linearly independent in $\Gamma(H)$. That is, no nontrivial finite linear combination of distinct exponential vectors can vanish. This fact ensures that exponential vectors provide a robust coordinate system for representing states and operators in Fock space.

(iv) Tensor Factorization. If the underlying Hilbert space H decomposes as a direct sum of orthogonal subspaces $H = H_1 \oplus H_2$, then the Fock space factorizes

correspondingly as a tensor product:

$$\Gamma(H) = \Gamma(H_1) \otimes \Gamma(H_2).$$

Moreover, for $f_1 \in H_1$ and $f_2 \in H_2$, the exponential vectors satisfy the multiplicative relation

$$e(f_1 \oplus f_2) = e(f_1) \otimes e(f_2).$$

This property mirrors the independence of quantum systems supported on orthogonal subspaces and plays a central role in the tensorial formulation of quantum stochastic processes.

(v) Operator Determination. Because of the linear independence and density of the set \mathcal{E} , any operator defined on \mathcal{E} is uniquely determined by its action on exponential vectors. This makes exponential vectors an ideal test domain for defining unbounded operators such as creation, annihilation, and number operators.

Hence, exponential vectors serve as a bridge between the abstract infinite-dimensional Hilbert space $\Gamma(H)$ and the more concrete, analytic representation of physical states. Their algebraic and analytic simplicity allows them to capture both the probabilistic and operator-theoretic structures underlying quantum systems with variable particle numbers.

3.1.5 Function Spaces and Framework (Ayoola 2002)

In the subsequent discussion, \mathbb{D} denotes an inner product space whose completion is the Hilbert space \mathcal{R} . Additionally, γ is a fixed separable Hilbert space.

(i) For $t \in \mathbb{R}_+ = [0, \infty)$, we define:

(a) $L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)$: The Hilbert space of square-integrable γ -valued map on $[0, \infty)$

(b) $L_\gamma^2([0, t])$: The Hilbert space of square-integrable γ -valued map on $[0, t)$.

(c) $L_\gamma^2([t, \infty))$: The Hilbert space of square-integrable γ -valued map on $[t, \infty)$.

(ii) The processes we consider are operators acting densely in $\mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+))$, whose inner product and norm are denoted $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and $\| \cdot \|$, respectively. For any $t > 0$, the decomposition

$$L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+) = L_\gamma^2([0, t]) \oplus L_\gamma^2([t, \infty))$$

induces a factorization of the Fock space:

$$\Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)) = \Gamma(L_\gamma^2([0, t])) \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2([t, \infty))).$$

(iii) Let us define the following dense subspaces generated by exponential vectors:

$$\mathbb{E} = \text{span}\{e(f) : f \in L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)\},$$

$$\mathbb{E}_t = \text{span}\{e(f) : f \in L_\gamma^2([0, t])\},$$

$$\mathbb{E}^t = \text{span}\{e(f) : f \in L_\gamma^2([t, \infty))\}.$$

Based on these, we introduce the operator spaces:

3.1.6 Operator Algebras and Topology.

We define the following families of operators, where $\underline{\otimes}$ denotes the algebraic tensor product:

- (i) $\mathcal{A} \equiv L^+(\mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}, \mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)))$
- (ii) $\mathcal{A}_t \equiv L^+(\mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}_t, \mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2([0, t])) \otimes \mathbf{1}^t)$
- (iii) $\mathcal{A}^t \equiv \mathbf{1}_t \otimes L^+(\mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}^t, \mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2([t, \infty))))$, $t > 0$

Here, \otimes denotes algebraic tensor product, $\mathbf{1}_t$ and $\mathbf{1}^t$ are the identity operators on $\mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2([0, t]))$ and $\Gamma(L_\gamma^2([t, \infty)))$, respectively. Note that \mathcal{A}_t and \mathcal{A}^t can be naturally viewed as subspaces of \mathcal{A} .

For any $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$, define the seminorm $\|\cdot\|_{\eta\xi}$ on \mathcal{A} by

$$\|x\|_{\eta\xi} = |\langle \eta, x\xi \rangle|, \quad x \in \mathcal{A}.$$

The family $\{\|\cdot\|_{\eta\xi} : \eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}\}$ induces a locally convex Hausdorff topology on \mathcal{A} , denoted τ_W .

3.1.7 Completions and Filtration.

Let $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_t$, and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}^t$ denote the completions of the spaces $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}_t$, and \mathcal{A}^t , respectively, with respect to the τ_W topology. The collection $\{\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_t : t \in \mathbb{R}_+\}$ forms a filtration of the space $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$, which will be fundamental for defining adapted processes.

3.2 Quantum Stochastic Integration Framework

3.2.1 Foundational Concepts and Processes

We begin by establishing the fundamental definitions and structures required for quantum stochastic integration, which will be utilized throughout this work.

Let I be a subset of the non-negative real numbers \mathbb{R}_+ . We define the following concepts:

- (i) A mapping $X : I \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is termed a *stochastic process* indexed by I .
- (ii) A stochastic process X is called *adapted* if $X(t) \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_t$ for every $t \in I$. The collection of all such adapted processes is denoted by $\text{Ad}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.
- (iii) For a process $X \in \text{Ad}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$, we define:
 - (a) *Weak absolute continuity (wac)* if for all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, the function $t \mapsto \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ is absolutely continuous on I . This subclass is denoted $\text{Ad}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})_{\text{wac}}$.
 - (b) *Local absolute p -integrability* if for each $t \in I$, $p \in (0, \infty)$, and all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, the function $\|X(\cdot)\|_{\eta\xi}^p$ is Lebesgue measurable and integrable on every compact subinterval $[t_0, t] \subseteq I$. This family is denoted $L_{\text{loc}}^p(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.

3.2.2 Stochastic Integrators and Basic Operators

Let $B(\gamma)$ represent the Banach space of bounded endomorphisms on the Hilbert space γ . We define the function spaces:

$$L_{\gamma, \text{loc}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+) = \{f : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \gamma \mid f \text{ is measurable and locally bounded}\},$$

$$L_{B(\gamma), \text{loc}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+) = \{\pi : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow B(\gamma) \mid \pi \text{ is measurable and locally bounded}\}.$$

For $f \in L_{\gamma, \text{loc}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$ and $\pi \in L_{B(\gamma), \text{loc}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$, we define the product $\pi f \in L_{\gamma, \text{loc}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$ pointwise by:

$$(\pi f)(t) = \pi(t)f(t), \quad t \in \mathbb{R}_+.$$

For $f \in L^2_\gamma(\mathbb{R}_+)$ and $\pi \in L^\infty_{B(\gamma),\text{loc}}(\mathbb{R}_+)$, we introduce the fundamental operators on the exponential domain:

$$\begin{aligned} a(f)e(g) &= \langle f, g \rangle_{L^2_\gamma(\mathbb{R}_+)} e(g), \\ a^+(f)e(g) &= \left. \frac{d}{d\sigma} e(g + \sigma f) \right|_{\sigma=0}, \\ \lambda(\pi)e(g) &= \left. \frac{d}{d\sigma} e(e^{\sigma\pi} g) \right|_{\sigma=0}, \quad \text{for } g \in L^2_\gamma(\mathbb{R}_+). \end{aligned}$$

These operators generate the stochastic processes:

$$\begin{aligned} A_f(t) &\equiv a(f\chi_{[0,t]}), \\ A_f^+(t) &\equiv a^+(f\chi_{[0,t]}), \\ \Lambda_\pi(t) &\equiv \lambda(\pi\chi_{[0,t]}), \quad t \in \mathbb{R}_+, \end{aligned}$$

where χ_I denotes the indicator function of the Borel set $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+$.

Remark 1

The operators $a(f)$, $a^+(f)$, and $\lambda(\pi)$ correspond to the annihilation, creation, and gauge operators in quantum field theory. The processes A_f , A_f^+ , and Λ_π serve as the fundamental stochastic integrators in the Hudson–Parthasarathy formulation of quantum stochastic calculus. Their action extends to the amplified space $\mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L^2_\gamma(\mathbb{R}_+))$ via:

$$r(t)(c \otimes e(\alpha)) = r(t)c \otimes e(\alpha), \quad \text{for } r \in \{A_f, A_f^+, \Lambda_\pi\}, \quad \eta = c \otimes e(\alpha).$$

3.2.3 Stochastic Integration for Simple Processes

Definition 4. A stochastic process $p \in Ad(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ is called simple if there exists an increasing sequence $\{t_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$, with $t_0 = 0$ and $t_n \rightarrow \infty$, such that for each $n \geq 0$,

$$p(t) = p(t_n) \quad \text{for all } t \in [t_n, t_{n+1}).$$

Definition 5. Let $p, q, u, v \in Ad(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ be simple adapted processes, and let $f, g \in L_{\gamma,loc}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$, $\pi \in L_{B(\gamma),loc}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$. The stochastic integral $M = \{M(t) : t \geq 0\}$ is defined recursively by $M(0) = 0$ and for $t \in (t_n, t_{n+1})$:

$$\begin{aligned} M(t) = M(t_n) + p(t_n) (\Lambda_\pi(t) - \Lambda_\pi(t_n)) + q(t_n) (A_f(t) - A_f(t_n)) \\ + u(t_n) (A_g^+(t) - A_g^+(t_n)) + v(t_n)(t - t_n). \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

This is expressed in integral and differential forms as:

$$\begin{aligned} M(t) &= \int_0^t (p(s) d\Lambda_\pi(s) + q(s) dA_f(s) + u(s) dA_g^+(s) + v(s) ds), \\ dM(t) &= p(t) d\Lambda_\pi(t) + q(t) dA_f(t) + u(t) dA_g^+(t) + v(t) dt, \quad M(0) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

3.2.4 Fundamental Theorem of Quantum Stochastic Calculus

We now present a fundamental result from Hudson and Parthasarathy concerning quantum stochastic integrals. Here, $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_\gamma$ denotes the inner product in the Hilbert space γ .

Theorem 1 (Ayoola 2002)

(a) Let p, q, u, v be simple processes in $\text{Ad}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ and let M be their stochastic integral.

For $\eta = c \otimes e(\alpha)$, $\xi = d \otimes e(\beta)$, with $c, d \in D$, $\alpha, \beta \in L_{\gamma, \text{loc}}^{\infty}(\mathbb{R}_+)$, and $t \geq 0$, we

have:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta, M(t)\xi \rangle = & \int_0^t \langle \eta, \{ \langle \alpha(s), \pi(s)\beta(s) \rangle_{\gamma} p(s) + \langle f(s), \beta(s) \rangle_{\gamma} q(s) \\ & + \langle \alpha(s), g(s) \rangle_{\gamma} u(s) + v(s) \} \xi \rangle ds. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

(b) The result in part (a) remains valid if for each integrand $F \in \{p, q, u, v\}$, the mapping $t \mapsto F(t)\xi$ is measurable and satisfies:

$$\int_0^t \|F(s)\xi\|^2 ds < \infty \quad \text{for all } t > 0 \text{ and all } \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}.$$

3.3 Extension of Quantum Stochastic Integrals

The extension of the stochastic integral to integrands in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ requires careful estimation within the family of seminorms $\{\|\cdot\|_{\eta, \xi} : \eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}\}$ that generate the topology of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. We begin with an approximation result.

Proposition 1 (Ayoola 2002)

Let $p \in L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. Then there exists a sequence $\{p^{(n)}\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ of simple adapted processes such that for every $t > 0$ and all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^t \|p(s) - p^{(n)}(s)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 ds = 0.$$

Proof

Let φ_n be the probability density function defined by $\varphi_n(s) = n\chi_{[0,1/n]}(s)$, and define the process p_n by

$$p_n(t)\eta = \int_0^t \varphi_n(t-s)(p(s)\eta) ds = n \int_{t-1/n}^t p(s)\eta ds,$$

where we set $p(s) \equiv 0$ for $s < 0$. Then p_n is a continuous adapted process and for any $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|(p_n(t) - p(t))\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 &= |\langle \eta, (p_n(t) - p(t))\xi \rangle|^2 \\ &= \left| \int_0^t \varphi_n(s) \langle \eta, (p(t-s) - p(t))\xi \rangle ds \right|^2 \\ &\leq \int_0^\infty |\langle \eta, (p(t-s) - p(t))\xi \rangle|^2 \varphi_n(s) ds \\ &\leq \sup \{ \|p(t-s) - p(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 : 0 \leq s \leq 1/n \}, \end{aligned}$$

where we used the fact that φ_n is a probability density and Jensen's inequality.

Hence for arbitrary $T > 0$,

$$\int_0^T \|p_n(t) - p(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 dt \leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq 1/n} \int_0^T \|p(t-s) - p(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 dt.$$

By the vector-valued version of Lebesgue's dominated convergence theorem, we conclude that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T \|p_n(t) - p(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 dt = 0. \quad (1)$$

Now define the sequence $p^{(n)}$ by $p^{(n)}(t) = p_n(m2^{-n})$ for $m2^{-n} \leq t < (m+1)2^{-n}$, $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Then each $p^{(n)}$ is a simple adapted process. Fix $t \in [m2^{-n}, (m+1)2^{-n})$. Since $\varphi_n(m2^{-n} - s) = 0$ for $s > m2^{-n}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|p^{(n)}(t) - p_n(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 \\
&= \left| \left\langle \eta, \left(\int_0^{m2^{-n}} \varphi_n(m2^{-n} - s)p(s) ds - \int_0^t \varphi_n(t - s)p(s) ds \right) \xi \right\rangle \right|^2 \\
&= \left| \int_0^t (\varphi_n(m2^{-n} - s) - \varphi_n(t - s)) \langle \eta, p(s)\xi \rangle ds \right|^2 \\
&\leq \left(\int_0^t |\varphi_n(m2^{-n} - s) - \varphi_n(t - s)|^2 ds \right) \left(\int_0^t \|p(s)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 ds \right) \\
&\leq \left(\int_0^T \|p(s)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 ds \right) n^2 2^{-n}
\end{aligned}$$

for all $t \in [0, T]$.

Together with equation (1), this implies that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T \|p^{(n)}(t) - p(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}^2 dt = 0,$$

which completes the proof.

This proposition facilitates the extension of the fundamental results to integrands in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. The following estimate is crucial for this extension.

Proposition 2 (Ayoola 2002)

Assume that:

- (i) p, q, u, v are simple processes in $\text{Ad}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.

(ii) For each $t \in [0, T]$ with $T > 0$,

$$M(t) = \int_0^t (p(s)d\Lambda_\pi(s) + q(s)dA_f(s) + u(s)dA_g^+(s) + v(s)ds).$$

Then, for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$ with $\eta = c \otimes e(\alpha)$, $\xi = d \otimes e(\beta)$, $c, d \in D$, $\alpha, \beta \in L_{\gamma, \text{loc}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$, and defining

$$K_{\eta, \xi, T} = \sup_{0 \leq s \leq T} \max \{ |\langle \alpha(s), \pi(s)\beta(s) \rangle_\gamma|, |\langle f(s), \beta(s) \rangle_\gamma|, |\langle \alpha(s), g(s) \rangle_\gamma|, 1 \},$$

we have the estimate

$$\|M(t)\|_{\eta, \xi} \leq K_{\eta, \xi, T} \int_0^T (\|p(s)\|_{\eta, \xi} + \|q(s)\|_{\eta, \xi} + \|u(s)\|_{\eta, \xi} + \|v(s)\|_{\eta, \xi}) ds.$$

3.3.1 Construction of the Extended Integral

Let $p, q, u, v \in L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. By Proposition 3.3, there exist sequences of simple adapted processes $\{p_n\}, \{q_n\}, \{u_n\}, \{v_n\}$ that approximate p, q, u, v respectively in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. Define the approximating integrals

$$M_n(t) = \int_0^t (p_n(s)d\Lambda_\pi(s) + q_n(s)dA_f(s) + u_n(s)dA_g^+(s) + v_n(s)ds).$$

Applying the estimate from Proposition 3.3 to the difference $M_n(t) - M_m(t)$ for $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, we find that $\{M_n(t)\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. By the completeness of this locally convex space, the sequence converges to a limit $M(t) \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. This limit is independent

of the choice of approximating sequences and is defined to be the stochastic integral

$$M(t) = \int_0^t (p(s)d\Lambda_\pi(s) + q(s)dA_f(s) + u(s)dA_g^+(s) + v(s)ds).$$

Due to the uniformity of convergence on finite intervals, we can pass to the limit in approximations by simple processes. Consequently, the fundamental formulae and estimates established for simple integrands remain valid for coefficients p, q, u, v belonging to $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.

3.4 Foundational Notations and Definitions

We now introduce several key concepts and notations essential for formulating quantum stochastic differential equations.

3.4.1 Spaces and Mappings

Definition 6. *The space of sesquilinear forms on $\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ is denoted by $\text{sesq}[\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}]$.*

Precisely,

$$\text{sesq}[\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}] = \{a : \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E} \times \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \mid$$

the map $(\eta, \xi) \mapsto a(\eta, \xi)$ is linear in ξ and conjugate linear in $\eta\}$.

Definition 7. *A stochastic process Φ is called locally absolutely p -integrable if for every $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ and $p \in (0, \infty)$, the function $t \mapsto \|\Phi(t)\|_{\eta, \xi}$ belongs to $L_{\text{loc}}^p(I)$.*

Definition 8. *For $p \in (0, \infty)$ and $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}_+$, the space $L_{\text{loc}}^p(I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ consists of all maps*

$\Phi : I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that for every $X \in L_{loc}^p(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$, the map $t \mapsto \Phi(t, X(t))$ lies in $L_{loc}^p(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.

3.4.2 Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations

In the subsequent analysis, we fix $f, g \in L_{\gamma, loc}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$, $\pi \in L_{B(\gamma), loc}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$, and let $\mathbf{1}$ denote the identity operator on $\mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+))$. The fundamental integrators are the processes A_f (annihilation), A_g^+ (creation), Λ_π (gauge), and the deterministic process $s \mapsto s\mathbf{1}$.

Definition 9 (Ayoola 2002). Let $E, F, G, H \in L_{loc}^2(I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ and let $(t_0, X_0) \in I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. A stochastic integral equation with coefficients E, F, G, H and initial data (t_0, X_0) is a relation of the form

$$X(t) = X_0 + \int_{t_0}^t (E(s, X(s))d\Lambda_\pi(s) + F(s, X(s))dA_f(s) + G(s, X(s))dA_g^+(s) + H(s, X(s))ds), \quad t \in I \quad (3.3)$$

with the initial condition $X(t_0) = X_0$.

In differential form, this equation is abbreviated as:

$$\begin{aligned} dX(t) &= E(t, X(t))d\Lambda_\pi(t) + F(t, X(t))dA_f(t) + G(t, X(t))dA_g^+(t) + H(t, X(t))dt, \\ X(t_0) &= X_0, \quad \text{for almost all } t \in I. \end{aligned}$$

We refer to this as a *stochastic differential equation (SDE)*.

Definition 10 (Ayoola 2002). A solution of the SDE is a weakly absolutely contin-

uous stochastic process $\phi \in L_{loc}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ satisfying

$$d\phi(t) = E(t, \phi(t))d\Lambda_\pi(t) + F(t, \phi(t))dA_f(t) + G(t, \phi(t))dA_g^+(t) + H(t, \phi(t))dt,$$

with $\phi(t_0) = X_0$, for almost all $t \in I$.

3.4.3 Properties of Coefficient Maps

Definition 11. Let $\Phi : I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow \text{sesq}[\mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}]$. The value of $\Phi(t, x)$ at $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$ is denoted $\Phi(t, x)(\eta, \xi)$.

1. The map Φ is called Lipschitzian if for all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$, there exists a locally integrable function $K_{\eta, \xi}^\Phi(t)$ on I such that for all $x, y \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and almost all $t \in I$,

$$|\Phi(t, x)(\eta, \xi) - \Phi(t, y)(\eta, \xi)| \leq K_{\eta, \xi}^\Phi(t) \|x - y\|_{\eta, \xi}.$$

2. The map Φ is called continuous if the mapping $(t, x) \mapsto \Phi(t, x)(\eta, \xi)$ from $I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ to \mathbb{C} is continuous.

3.4.4 Auxiliary Functions and the Associated Sesquilinear Form

Unless stated otherwise, we assume $E, F, G, H \in L_{loc}^2(I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ and fix a point $(t_0, x_0) \in I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

For $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$ with $\eta = c \otimes e(\alpha)$, $\xi = d \otimes e(\beta)$, we define the scalar functions

$\mu_{\alpha\beta}, \gamma_\beta, \sigma_\alpha : I \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ by:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\alpha\beta}(t) &= \langle \alpha(t), \pi(t)\beta(t) \rangle_\gamma, \\ \gamma_\beta(t) &= \langle f(t), \beta(t) \rangle_\gamma, \\ \sigma_\alpha(t) &= \langle \alpha(t), g(t) \rangle_\gamma, \quad t \in I.\end{aligned}$$

Using these, we construct maps $\mu_E, \gamma_F, \sigma_G, P$ from $I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ into $\text{sesq}[\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}]$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}(\mu_E)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) &= \langle \eta, \mu_{\alpha\beta}(t)E(t, x)\xi \rangle, \\ (\gamma_F)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) &= \langle \eta, \gamma_\beta(t)F(t, x)\xi \rangle, \\ (\sigma_G)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) &= \langle \eta, \sigma_\alpha(t)G(t, x)\xi \rangle,\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}P(t, x)(\eta, \xi) &= (\mu_E)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) + (\gamma_F)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) \\ &\quad + (\sigma_G)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) + H(t, x)(\eta, \xi),\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

where $H(t, x)(\eta, \xi) := \langle \eta, H(t, x)\xi \rangle$.

The map P inherits Lipschitz and continuity properties from the coefficients E, F, G, H . It is known that if these coefficients belong to $L^2_{\text{loc}}(I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$, then the stochastic integral equation (3.3) is equivalent to a certain integral form involving P . Moreover, if the coefficients are Lipschitzian, then for any initial data (t_0, X_0) , there exists a unique weakly absolutely continuous solution $\phi \in \text{Ad}(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})_{\text{wac}}$ to the equation (3.3).

3.5 Equivalent Form of Quantum Stochastic Differential Equation

This section presents a summary of results concerning equivalent forms of quantum stochastic differential inclusions, adapted to the context of quantum stochastic differential equations.

Throughout this section, unless stated otherwise, we assume that $E, F, G, H \in L_{\text{loc}}^2(I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$, and (t_0, x_0) denotes a fixed point in $I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

For vectors $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ with $\eta = c \otimes e(\alpha)$ and $\xi = d \otimes e(\beta)$, we define the functions $\mu_{\alpha\beta}, \gamma_{\beta}, \sigma_{\alpha} : I \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. Associated with these functions, we introduce the maps $\mu E, \gamma F, \sigma G, P$ from $I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ into the space of sesquilinear forms on $\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$:

$$P(t, x)(\eta, \xi) = (\mu E)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) + (\gamma F)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) + (\sigma G)(t, x)(\eta, \xi) + H(t, x)(\eta, \xi),$$

for $\xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, $(t, x) \in I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. The complete expressions for these maps are provided in the reference.

Sometimes it is convenient to express P in the form $P(t, x)(\eta, \xi) = \langle \eta, P_{\alpha\beta}(t, x)\xi \rangle$, where $P_{\alpha\beta} : I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is defined by

$$P_{\alpha\beta}(t, x) = \mu_{\alpha\beta}(t)E(t, x) + \gamma_{\beta}(t)F(t, x) + \sigma_{\alpha}(t)G(t, x) + H(t, x)$$

for $(t, x) \in I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

The map P plays a fundamental role in the subsequent analysis. The requisite properties of P have been established in Ekaghuere 1992. The following theorem presents the equivalent form of the quantum stochastic differential equation, summarizing the general case as it applies to stochastic differential equations.

Theorem 2 (Adeyeye 2007)

Let $E, F, G, H \in L^2_{\text{loc}}(I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ and let (t_0, x_0) be a fixed point in $I \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then the stochastic integral equation

$$X(t) = X_0 + \int_{t_0}^t (E(s, X(s)) d\Lambda_\pi(s) + F(s, X(s)) dA_f(s) + G(s, X(s)) dA_g^+(s) + H(s, X(s)) ds), \quad t \in I$$

is equivalent to the initial value nonclassical ordinary differential equation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \langle \eta, X(t) \xi \rangle &= P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \\ X(t_0) &= X_0, \end{aligned}$$

for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ and almost all $t \in I$.

3.6 Existence, Uniqueness and Stability of Solutions

This section presents fundamental results concerning the existence, uniqueness, and stability of solutions to the quantum stochastic differential equation (QSDE) given

by Equation (2.4) and its equivalent forms. The foundational Equation (2.2) plays a critical role in establishing Theorem 3, a result attributed to Ekhaguere, 1992.

Theorem 3 (Ayoola 2000)

Suppose that the coefficients E, F, G, H appearing in Equation (3.3) belong to $L^2_{\text{loc}}(I \times \bar{\mathcal{A}})$. Then Equation (3.3) is equivalent to Equation (1.3), where the map P is given by Equation (3.4).

The following theorem establishes that under suitable conditions on the coefficients, namely, that they are Lipschitz continuous and locally square-integrable, the initial value problem for the QSDE (2.4) admits a unique, adapted, and weakly absolutely continuous solution.

Theorem 4 (Ayoola 1998, 2000)

Suppose that the coefficients E, F, G, H appearing in Equation (3.3) are Lipschitzian and belong to $L^2_{\text{loc}}(I \times \bar{\mathcal{A}})$. Then for any fixed point (t_0, X_0) of $I \times \bar{\mathcal{A}}$, there exists a unique, adapted and weakly absolutely continuous solution Φ of quantum stochastic differential Equation (3.3) satisfying $\Phi(t_0) = X_0$.

Proof

The proof will be accomplished by constructing a τ_W -Cauchy sequence $\{\Phi_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ of successive approximations of Φ in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Let $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$ be arbitrary. Fix $T > t_0$ and let $t \in [t_0, T]$. Define the initial

approximation $\Phi_0(t) = X_0$, and for $n \geq 0$, define recursively:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{n+1}(t) = X_0 + \int_{t_0}^t (E(s, \Phi_n(s))d \wedge_{\pi}(s) + F(s, \Phi_n(s))dA_f(s) \\ + G(s, \Phi_n(s))dA_g^+(s) + H(s, \Phi_n(s))ds) . \end{aligned}$$

We claim that each $\Phi_n(t)$, $n \geq 1$ defines an adapted weakly absolutely continuous process in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.

By hypothesis, $E(s, X_0), F(s, X_0), G(s, X_0)$ and $H(s, X_0)$ belong to $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_s$ for $s \in [t_0, T]$ and $E(\cdot, X_0), F(\cdot, X_0), G(\cdot, X_0)$ and $H(\cdot, X_0)$ lie in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. Hence, the quantum stochastic integral defining $\Phi_1(t)$ exists for $t_0 \leq t \leq T$.

By Equation (3.2), $\Phi_1(t)$ is weakly absolutely continuous and hence locally square integrable. Now if $\Phi_n(t)$ is assumed to be adapted and weakly absolutely continuous, then as above, each $E(s, \Phi_n(s)), F(s, \Phi_n(s)), G(s, \Phi_n(s))$ and $H(s, \Phi_n(s))$ is adapted and lies in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. Thus $\Phi_{n+1}(t)$ is adapted and well defined.

Again by Equation (3.2), $\Phi_{n+1}(t)$ is a weakly absolutely continuous process in $L_{\text{loc}}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$. Hence we have proved our claim by induction.

We now consider the convergence of the successive approximations. Using Equation (3.2) and the definition of the map P , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi_{n+1}(t) - \Phi_n(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &= |\langle \eta, (\Phi_{n+1}(t) - \Phi_n(t))\xi \rangle| \\ &= \left| \int_{t_0}^t (P(s, \Phi_n(s))(\eta, \xi) - P(s, \Phi_{n-1}(s))(\eta, \xi)) ds \right|. \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

Since the coefficients E, F, G, H are Lipschitzian, then P is also Lipschitzian with Lipschitz functions $K_{\eta\xi}^P : [t_0, T] \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ lying in $L_{\text{loc}}^1([t_0, T])$, i.e.,

$$|P(t, x)(\eta, \xi) - P(t, y)(\eta, \xi)| \leq K_{\eta\xi}^P(t) \|(x - y)\|_{\eta\xi}, \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}, t \in [t_0, T].$$

Hence,

$$\|\Phi_{n+1}(t) - \Phi_n(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) \|\Phi_n(s) - \Phi_{n-1}(s)\|_{\eta\xi} ds. \quad (2)$$

Since the map $s \rightarrow \|\Phi_1(s) - X_0\|_{\eta\xi}$ is continuous on $[t_0, T]$, we define:

$$R_{\eta\xi} = \sup_{s \in [t_0, T]} \|\Phi_1(s) - X_0\|_{\eta\xi}$$

and

$$M_{\eta\xi}(t) = \int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) ds.$$

Then from (2),

$$\|\Phi_{n+1}(t) - \Phi_n(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \frac{R_{\eta\xi} (M_{\eta\xi}(t))^n}{n!}, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (3)$$

This can be proved by induction as follows. For $n = 1$, inequality (3) holds by considering (2). Assume that (3) holds for $n = k$, i.e.,

$$\|\Phi_{k+1}(t) - \Phi_k(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \frac{R_{\eta\xi} (M_{\eta\xi}(t))^k}{k!}. \quad (4)$$

Then by (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi_{k+2}(t) - \Phi_{k+1}(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq \int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) \|\Phi_{k+1}(s) - \Phi_k(s)\|_{\eta\xi} ds \\ &\leq \frac{R_{\eta\xi}}{k!} \int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) (M_{\eta\xi}(s))^k ds \quad \text{by (4)}. \end{aligned}$$

By applying integration by parts, we obtain:

$$\int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) (M_{\eta\xi}(s))^k ds = \frac{(M_{\eta\xi}(t))^{k+1}}{k+1}, \quad (5)$$

therefore,

$$\|\Phi_{k+2}(t) - \Phi_{k+1}(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \frac{R_{\eta\xi} (M_{\eta\xi}(t))^{k+1}}{(k+1)!},$$

so that (3) holds for $n = k + 1$ and thus holds for all $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Therefore, for any $n > k$:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi_{n+1}(t) - \Phi_{k+1}(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &= \left\| \sum_{m=k+1}^n (\Phi_{m+1}(t) - \Phi_m(t)) \right\|_{\eta\xi} \\ &\leq \sum_{m=k+1}^n \|\Phi_{m+1}(t) - \Phi_m(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \\ &\leq \sum_{m=k+1}^n \frac{R_{\eta\xi} (M_{\eta\xi}(T))^m}{m!}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $\{\Phi_n(t)\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and converges uniformly to some $\Phi(t)$. Since each $\Phi_n(t)$ is adapted and weakly absolutely continuous, the same is true of $\Phi(t)$.

Next, we show that $\Phi(t)$ satisfies the quantum stochastic differential equation (3.3).

Clearly, $\Phi(t_0) = X_0$.

Again, by Equation (3.2):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| \int_{t_0}^t [E(s, \Phi_n(s))d\wedge_\pi(s) + F(s, \Phi_n(s))dA_f(s) + G(s, \Phi_n(s))dA_g^+(s) + H(s, \Phi_n(s))ds] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \int_{t_0}^t [E(s, \Phi(s))d\wedge_\pi(s) + F(s, \Phi(s))dA_f(s) + G(s, \Phi(s))dA_g^+(s) + H(s, \Phi(s))ds] \right\|_{\eta\xi} \\
&= \left| \int_{t_0}^t [P(s, \Phi_n(s))(\eta, \xi) - P(s, \Phi(s))(\eta, \xi)] ds \right| \\
&\leq \int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) \|\Phi_n(s) - \Phi(s)\|_{\eta\xi} ds \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty,
\end{aligned}$$

since $\Phi_n(s) \rightarrow \Phi(s)$ in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ uniformly on $[t_0, T]$.

Thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi(t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Phi_{n+1}(t) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(X_0 + \int_{t_0}^t (E(s, \Phi_n(s))d\wedge_\pi(s) + F(s, \Phi_n(s))dA_f(s) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + G(s, \Phi_n(s))dA_g^+(s) + H(s, \Phi_n(s))ds) \right) \\
&= X_0 + \int_{t_0}^t (E(s, \Phi(s))d\wedge_\pi(s) + F(s, \Phi(s))dA_f(s) + G(s, \Phi(s))dA_g^+(s) + H(s, \Phi(s))ds),
\end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\Phi(t)$, $t \in [t_0, T]$ is a solution of Equation (3.3).

Uniqueness

To establish the uniqueness of the solution, suppose that $Y(t)$, $t \in [t_0, T]$ is another adapted weakly absolutely continuous solution with $Y(t_0) = X_0$. Then, by Equation

(3.2), we obtain as before:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi(t) - Y(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &= \left| \int_{t_0}^t [P(s, \Phi(s))(\eta, \xi) - P(s, Y(s))(\eta, \xi)] ds \right| \\ &\leq \int_{t_0}^t K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) \|\Phi(s) - Y(s)\|_{\eta\xi} ds. \end{aligned}$$

Since $s \rightarrow K_{\eta\xi}^P(s)$ is integrable on $[t_0, t]$, it is essentially bounded on the interval.

Hence, there exists a constant $C_{\eta\xi, t}^P$ such that:

$$\text{ess sup } K_{\eta\xi}^P(s) = C_{\eta\xi, t}^P.$$

Thus:

$$\|\Phi(t) - Y(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq C_{\eta\xi, t}^P \int_{t_0}^t \|\Phi(s) - Y(s)\|_{\eta\xi} ds.$$

We conclude by applying Gronwall's inequality that $\Phi(t) = Y(t)$ for all $t \in [t_0, T]$.

Hence, the solution is unique.

3.6.1 Stability

A key property of differential equations is the continuous dependence of their solutions on the initial conditions. The next theorem demonstrates that the solutions to the stochastic differential equation (3.3) are stable. This means that a small perturbation in the initial condition results in only a small change in the solution over any given finite time interval, uniformly for each pair of elements η, ξ in the dense domain $\mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$.

To formulate this precisely, let the coefficients E, F, G, H and the quantum stochastic

integrators \wedge_π , A_f , A_g^+ be as defined in Theorem 3. Consider two solutions, $X(t)$ and $Y(t)$ for $t \in [t_0, T]$, to Equation (3.3) corresponding to the initial conditions $X(t_0) = X_0$ and $Y(t_0) = Y_0$, respectively, where $X_0, Y_0 \in \bar{\mathcal{A}}$. The stability of the solution $X(t)$ with respect to changes in its initial value X_0 is characterized as follows:

Theorem 5 (Ayoola 1998)

For given $T > t_0$ and $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $\partial > 0$ such that if $\|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} < \partial$, then $\|X(t) - Y(t)\|_{\eta\xi} < \epsilon$ for all $t \in [t_0, T]$ and for each pair of $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$.

Proof

As in the proof of Theorem 4, let $X_n(t)$, for $n = 0, 1, \dots$ and $Y_n(t)$, for $n = 0, 1, \dots$ be the iterates corresponding to initial conditions X_0 and Y_0 respectively, so that $X_0(t) = X_0$ and $Y_0(t) = Y_0$ for all $t_0 \leq t \leq T$.

Using the definition of P and Equation (3.2) as in the proof of uniqueness of solution, we obtain the following estimate:

$$\begin{aligned} \|X_{n+1}(t) - Y_{n+1}(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} + \int_{t_0}^t |P(s, X_n(s))(\eta, \xi) - P(s, Y_n(s))(\eta, \xi)| ds \\ &\leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} + C_{\eta\xi, t} \int_{t_0}^t \|X_n(s) - Y_n(s)\|_{\eta\xi} ds, \end{aligned}$$

where $C_{\eta\xi, t}$ is the essential supremum of $K_{\eta\xi}^P(t)$ on $[t_0, t]$.

By iteration, we obtain for $t_0 \leq t \leq T$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\|X_{n+1}(t) - Y_{n+1}(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} + C_{\eta\xi,t} \left[\int_{t_0}^t \left(\|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + C_{\eta\xi,t_1} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \|X_{n-1}(t_2) - Y_{n-1}(t_2)\|_{\eta\xi} dt_2 \right) dt_1 \right] \\
&\leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} + l_{\eta\xi}(t - t_0) \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \\
&\quad + l_{\eta\xi}^2 \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \|X_{n-1}(t_2) - Y_{n-1}(t_2)\|_{\eta\xi} dt_2 dt_1,
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$l_{\eta\xi} = \max\{C_{\eta\xi,t}, C_{\eta\xi,t_1}\}.$$

Continuing the iteration and putting

$$L_{\eta\xi} = \max\{C_{\eta\xi,t}, C_{\eta\xi,t_j}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n\},$$

we obtain the estimate:

$$\begin{aligned}
\|X_{n+1}(t) - Y_{n+1}(t)\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} + L_{\eta\xi}(t - t_0) \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} + \dots \\
&\quad + L_{\eta\xi}^n \frac{(t - t_0)^n}{n!} \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \\
&\quad + L_{\eta\xi}^{n+1} \int_{t_0}^t \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \dots \int_{t_0}^{t_n} \|X_0(t_{n+1}) - Y_0(t_{n+1})\|_{\eta\xi} dt_1 dt_2 \dots dt_{n+1} \\
&\leq \sum_{m=0}^{n+1} \frac{L_{\eta\xi}^m}{m!} (t - t_0)^m \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \\
&\leq \sum_{m=0}^{n+1} \frac{(L_{\eta\xi} T)^m}{m!} \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \\
&\leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \exp(L_{\eta\xi} T).
\end{aligned}$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$, we conclude that

$$\|X(t) - Y(t)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \|X_0 - Y_0\|_{\eta\xi} \exp(L_{\eta\xi}T),$$

for all $t_0 \leq t \leq T$, and the result now follows.

Chapter 4

Newton–Cotes Method for Quantum Stochastic Differential Equation

4.1 Introduction

The Newton–Cotes methods form a family of numerical integration techniques that approximate an integral by replacing the integrand with an interpolating polynomial passing through equally spaced points. These methods are particularly useful in the numerical solution of differential equations where analytical integration is difficult or impossible.

In the context of Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations (QSDEs), the Newton–Cotes formulas provide a systematic approach for approximating expectations, operator-valued integrals, or other quantities that arise in the evolution of quantum systems

driven by stochastic processes. Because QSDEs often involve highly oscillatory or nonlinear terms, exact analytical solutions are rarely attainable; hence, numerical techniques such as the Newton–Cotes approach become indispensable.

The basic idea is to discretize the time interval of interest, approximate the integrand at discrete points, and use a polynomial of degree n to interpolate between them. By integrating this polynomial exactly, one obtains a numerical approximation to the original stochastic integral. Depending on the choice of n , different Newton–Cotes formulas emerge, for instance, the Trapezoidal rule ($n = 1$), Simpson’s rule ($n = 2$), or higher-order formulas.

In the subsequent sections, we shall present various Newton–Cotes schemes and demonstrate their applications to the numerical solution of Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations. Each method will be derived, analyzed, and applied to some specific QSDE formulations to illustrate their efficiency and convergence properties.

4.1.1 General Representation of the Newton–Cotes Formula

The Newton–Cotes formulas are an extremely useful and straightforward family of numerical integration techniques. To integrate a function $f(x)$ over some interval $[a, b]$, the interval is divided into n equal parts such that $f_i = f(x_i)$ and $h = (b - a)/n$. The basic idea is to find polynomials which approximate the tabulated function and then integrate them to estimate the area under the curve. To obtain these fitting polynomials, the Lagrange interpolating polynomials are employed. The resulting formulas are known as the *Newton–Cotes formulas*, or simply, *quadrature formulas*.

The Newton–Cotes formulas may be classified as *closed* if the endpoints $[x_0, x_n]$ are

included in the fit, or *open* if the interior points $[x_1, x_{n-1}]$ are used instead. There exist variations that combine these two ideas. When the formula uses n points (closed or open), the coefficients of the terms sum to $n - 1$.

If the function $f(x)$ is given explicitly rather than being known only at discrete points x_i , a more efficient and accurate numerical integration method known as *Gaussian Quadrature* is often used. In Gaussian Quadrature, the points at which the function is evaluated are chosen optimally, which yields higher accuracy, although the method is considerably more complex to implement compared to the Newton–Cotes approach.

Let the integral

$$I = \int_a^b f(x) dx$$

be approximated by dividing the interval $[a, b]$ into n equal subintervals of width

$$h = \frac{b - a}{n}.$$

Let the equally spaced nodes be $x_i = a + ih$, for $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$.

The general **Newton–Cotes formula** is expressed as

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx h \sum_{i=0}^n C_i f(x_i),$$

where C_i are the *weights* defined by

$$C_i = \frac{1}{h} \int_a^b \ell_i(x) dx,$$

and $\ell_i(x)$ is the Lagrange interpolating polynomial given by

$$\ell_i(x) = \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^n \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j}.$$

Hence, the complete representation including the error term is

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = h \sum_{i=0}^n C_i f(x_i) + R_n,$$

where

$$R_n = \frac{(b-a)^{n+2}}{(n+2)!} f^{(n+1)}(\xi) \int_0^n t \prod_{i=0}^n (t-i) dt, \quad \xi \in (a, b).$$

4.2 Implicit Trapezoidal Method for Classical Ordinary Differential Equations

4.3 Derivation of the Trapezoidal Rule

The 2-point closed Newton-Cotes formula is called the trapezoidal rule because it approximates the area under a curve using a trapezoid with horizontal base and sloped top connecting the endpoints (x_1, f_1) and (x_2, f_2) .

Given equally spaced points with spacing h , the second point is located at:

$$x_2 = x_1 + h \tag{4.1}$$

The Lagrange interpolating polynomial through the points (x_1, f_1) and (x_2, f_2) is:

$$P_2(x) = \frac{x - x_2}{x_1 - x_2} f_1 + \frac{x - x_1}{x_2 - x_1} f_2 \quad (4.2)$$

Substituting $x_2 = x_1 + h$ and $x_1 - x_2 = -h$, $x_2 - x_1 = h$ gives:

$$P_2(x) = \frac{x - x_1 - h}{-h} f_1 + \frac{x - x_1}{h} f_2 \quad (4.3)$$

This can be rearranged as:

$$P_2(x) = \frac{x}{h}(f_2 - f_1) + \left(f_1 + \frac{x_1}{h}f_1 - \frac{x_1}{h}f_2\right) \quad (4.4)$$

Now integrating over the interval $[x_1, x_2]$ to find the area under the approximating polynomial:

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} f(x)dx \approx \int_{x_1}^{x_1+h} P_2(x)dx \quad (4.5)$$

Substituting equation (4) and integrating term by term:

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} P_2(x)dx = \frac{1}{2h}(f_2 - f_1) [x^2]_{x_1}^{x_2} + \left(f_1 + \frac{x_1}{h}f_1 - \frac{x_1}{h}f_2\right) [x]_{x_1}^{x_2} \quad (4.6)$$

Evaluating the limits and using $x_2 = x_1 + h$:

$$= \frac{1}{2h}(f_2 - f_1)(x_2 + x_1)(x_2 - x_1) + (x_2 - x_1) \left(f_1 + \frac{x_1}{h}f_1 - \frac{x_1}{h}f_2\right) \quad (4.7)$$

Substituting $x_2 - x_1 = h$ and $x_2 + x_1 = 2x_1 + h$:

$$= \frac{1}{2}(f_2 - f_1)(2x_1 + h) + f_1 h + x_1(f_1 - f_2) \quad (4.8)$$

Expanding and simplifying:

$$= x_1(f_2 - f_1) + \frac{1}{2}h(f_2 - f_1) + hf_1 - x_1(f_2 - f_1) \quad (4.9)$$

The $x_1(f_2 - f_1)$ terms cancel, leaving:

$$= \frac{1}{2}h(f_1 + f_2) - \frac{1}{12}h^3 f''(\xi) \quad (4.10)$$

This final result is the trapezoidal rule with its error term, where $x_1 \leq \xi \leq x_2$. The error term shows that the trapezoidal rule is exact for linear functions and has error proportional to $h^3 f''(\xi)$ for other functions.

4.3.1 Application to Classical Initial Value Problem

Consider the classical initial value problem

$$x'(t) = f(t, x(t)), \quad x(t_0) = x_0, \quad (4.11)$$

where the function $f(t, x)$ is continuous and satisfies the necessary Lipschitz condition for the existence and uniqueness of the solution.

We are interested in finding the approximate value of the solution $x(T)$ at $t = T$. To achieve this, we divide the time interval $[t_0, T]$ into N equal subintervals with step

size

$$h = \frac{T - t_0}{N}, \quad \text{and} \quad t_i = t_0 + ih, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (4.12)$$

Integrating both sides of the differential equation over the interval $[t_i, t_{i+1}]$, we have

$$x(t_{i+1}) - x(t_i) = \int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} f(t, x(t)) dt. \quad (4.13)$$

Using the Trapezoidal Rule to approximate the integral on the right-hand side, we obtain

$$\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} f(t, x(t)) dt \approx \frac{h}{2} [f(t_i, x(t_i)) + f(t_{i+1}, x(t_{i+1}))]. \quad (4.14)$$

Therefore, the numerical approximation becomes

$$x_{i+1} = x_i + \frac{h}{2} [f(t_i, x_i) + f(t_{i+1}, x_{i+1})]. \quad (4.15)$$

This is called the **implicit trapezoidal method** because the unknown value x_{i+1} appears on both sides of the equation.

Because x_{i+1} appears on both sides, we can't compute it directly, so we use a predictor-corrector or iterative form.

We can obtain an initial approximation for x_{i+1} using the explicit Euler method:

$$x_{i+1}^{(0)} = x_i + hf(t_i, x_i).$$

For subsequent iterations, we update x_{i+1} using the iterative (corrected) trapezoidal form:

$$x_{i+1}^{(m+1)} = x_i + \frac{h}{2} \left[f(t_i, x_i) + f(t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}^{(m)}) \right],$$

for $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$ and $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

This means we start with

$$x_{i+1}^{(0)} = x_i + hf(t_i, x_i),$$

then repeatedly correct it using the above formula until convergence, that is,

$$\left| x_{i+1}^{(m+1)} - x_{i+1}^{(m)} \right| < \varepsilon.$$

for a small tolerance ε .

The iterative algorithmic form of the method is thus given as

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 &= x(t_0), \\ x_1^{(0)} &= x_0 + hf(t_0, x_0), \\ x_{i+1}^{(m+1)} &= x_i + \frac{h}{2} \left[f(t_i, x_i) + f(t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}^{(m)}) \right], \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1; m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

Here, m denotes the iteration index, and the iteration continues until convergence.

The implicit trapezoidal scheme thus provides a stable and accurate numerical approach for solving first-order ordinary differential equations, balancing computational efficiency and convergence reliability.

4.4 Implicit Trapezoidal Method for QSDEs

We seek a numerical solution to the quantum stochastic differential equation written in its weak (pairing) form:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle = P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad \langle\eta, X(t_0)\xi\rangle = \langle\eta, X_0\xi\rangle, \quad t \in [t_0, T],$$

where $P(t, X)$ is the appropriate (possibly complex) operator pairing appearing in the QSDE. The integral form of the pairing is

$$\langle\eta, X(t_{i+1})\xi\rangle - \langle\eta, X(t_i)\xi\rangle = \int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi) ds.$$

4.4.1 Trapezoidal approximation of the integral

Apply the 2-point closed Newton–Cotes (trapezoidal) rule to the integral on the right.

With step size

$$h = t_{i+1} - t_i,$$

and denoting

$$P_i := P(t_i, X(t_i)), \quad P_{i+1} := P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})),$$

the trapezoidal rule yields (for some $\xi_i \in (t_i, t_{i+1})$)

$$\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi) ds = \frac{h}{2}[P_i(\eta, \xi) + P_{i+1}(\eta, \xi)] - \frac{h^3}{12}\partial_s^2(P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi))\Big|_{s=\xi_i},$$

so neglecting the $O(h^3)$ remainder we obtain the trapezoidal (implicit) discrete relation

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2} \left[P(t_i, X_i)(\eta, \xi) + P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1})(\eta, \xi) \right], \quad (4.16)$$

where for brevity we write $X_i := X(t_i)$ and $X_{i+1} := X(t_{i+1})$.

Equation (4.16) is implicit because the unknown pairing $\langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle$ appears on both sides (inside $P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1})(\eta, \xi)$). We therefore solve it by iteration.

4.4.2 Algorithmic (predictor–corrector) form

We now present the computational algorithm that implements (4.16). The algorithm mirrors the classical trapezoidal predictor–corrector but applied to the pairing $\langle \eta, X \cdot \xi \rangle$.

Assume the pairing $\langle \eta, X_0 \xi \rangle$ is known from the initial condition.

Predictor (explicit Euler as initial guess):

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(0)} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + h P(t_i, X_i)(\eta, \xi).$$

Corrector (trapezoidal fixed-point iteration):

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2} \left[P(t_i, X_i)(\eta, \xi) + P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}^{(m)})(\eta, \xi) \right], \quad (4.17)$$

for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ until

$$|\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m)} \xi \rangle| < \varepsilon,$$

at which point set $\langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle$.

Thus, the full algorithm reads:

$$\langle \eta, X_0 \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X(t_0) \xi \rangle$$

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(0)} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + h P(t_i, X_i)(\eta, \xi)$$

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2} \left[P(t_i, X_i)(\eta, \xi) + P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}^{(m)})(\eta, \xi) \right]$$

$$i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1 \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$$

4.4.3 Real and imaginary component form

Since the map $(t, x) \longrightarrow P(t, x)(\eta, \xi)$ is complex valued, it is often convenient to split into real and imaginary parts. Write

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle = \operatorname{Re} \langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle + i \operatorname{Im} \langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle,$$

and denote

$$P_i(\eta, \xi) = \operatorname{Re} P_i(\eta, \xi) + i \operatorname{Im} P_i(\eta, \xi).$$

Then the iterative update (4.17) is equivalent to the pair

$$\operatorname{Re} \langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle = \operatorname{Re} \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2} \left[\operatorname{Re} P_i(\eta, \xi) + \operatorname{Re} P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}^{(m)})(\eta, \xi) \right],$$

$$\operatorname{Im} \langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle = \operatorname{Im} \langle \eta, X_i \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2} \left[\operatorname{Im} P_i(\eta, \xi) + \operatorname{Im} P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}^{(m)})(\eta, \xi) \right].$$

These component equations are suitable for numerical implementation when P is given in terms of its real and imaginary contributions.

4.4.4 Remarks on accuracy and initialization

The trapezoidal approximation omitted a remainder of order $O(h^3)$ per step; therefore the local truncation error of the implicit trapezoidal QSDE scheme is $O(h^3)$, and the global error (over the interval $[t_0, T]$) is $O(h^2)$ under the usual smoothness assumptions on P and the solution. The predictor (explicit Euler) gives an $O(h)$ initial guess; often one or two corrector iterations are sufficient in practice to obtain the desired tolerance, or a Newton iteration may be used for faster convergence when $P(t, \cdot)$ is nonlinear in X .

This trapezoidal method is the natural two-point (one-step) scheme: it uses a linear interpolant on each subinterval, produces an implicit one-step relation, and is implemented via the predictor–corrector iterations above.

We now establish key technical lemmas that will be used in the convergence proof of our numerical method.

Lemma 1 (Adeyeye (2007))

Suppose that the sequence of non-negative numbers $\{Q_n\}$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$ satisfies $Q_{n+1} \leq AQ_n + B$, $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$ for some positive constants A, B . Then $Q_{n+1} \leq A^n Q_1 + B \frac{A^n - 1}{A - 1}$, $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$.

Proof

We prove the inequality by mathematical induction on n for $n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$.

For the base case $n = 0$ the claimed inequality (when $A \neq 1$) reads

$$Q_1 \leq A^0 Q_1 + B \frac{A^0 - 1}{A - 1}.$$

Because $A^0 = 1$ and $(A^0 - 1)/(A - 1) = 0$, the right-hand side equals Q_1 , so the inequality holds as an equality:

$$Q_1 \leq Q_1.$$

Thus the base case holds.

Assume now that for some fixed n with $0 \leq n \leq N - 2$ the inequality holds at index n , i.e.

$$Q_{n+1} \leq A^n Q_1 + B \frac{A^n - 1}{A - 1} \quad (\text{when } A \neq 1),$$

Starting from the recurrence relation and applying the induction hypothesis yields

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{n+2} &\leq A Q_{n+1} + B \\ &\leq A \left(A^n Q_1 + B \frac{A^n - 1}{A - 1} \right) + B \\ &= A^{n+1} Q_1 + B \left(\frac{A(A^n - 1)}{A - 1} + 1 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Computing the expression in parentheses with a common denominator:

$$\frac{A(A^n - 1)}{A - 1} + 1 = \frac{A(A^n - 1) + (A - 1)}{A - 1} = \frac{A^{n+1} - A + A - 1}{A - 1} = \frac{A^{n+1} - 1}{A - 1}.$$

Substituting back gives

$$Q_{n+2} \leq A^{n+1}Q_1 + B \frac{A^{n+1} - 1}{A - 1},$$

which is exactly the desired inequality at index $n + 1$ for $A \neq 1$.

Therefore, by the principle of mathematical induction, the stated inequalities hold for every integer n with $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$.

Lemma 2 (Adeyeye 2007)

Suppose $\{P_n\}_{n=0}^N$ is a sequence of nonnegative real numbers which satisfies

$$P_{n+1} \leq AP_n + BP_{n-1} + C, \quad 1 \leq n \leq N - 1,$$

for some fixed positive constants A, B, C . Define

$$\alpha := \frac{A + \sqrt{A^2 + 4B}}{2}.$$

Then for every $1 \leq n \leq N - 1$ we have

$$P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n \leq \alpha^n [P_1 + (\alpha - A)P_0] + C \frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1},$$

Proof

We proceed by the same clever algebraic trick used in many second-order recurrence estimates: create an auxiliary quantity by adding a carefully chosen multiple of P_n to both sides of the given inequality so the right-hand side factors with a common

multiplicative constant.

Observe that

$$\frac{\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} + A}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} - A}{2} = \frac{(\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} + A) - (\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} - A)}{2} = \frac{2A}{2} = A.$$

Thus indeed

$$A = \frac{\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} + A}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} - A}{2}.$$

We will use the two halves

$$\alpha := \frac{\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} + A}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha - A = \frac{\sqrt{A^2 + 4B} - A}{2},$$

so the splitting is simply $A = \alpha - (\alpha - A)$. This choice is not arbitrary: it prepares the algebraic factorization below.

From the definition of α we have

$$2\alpha - A = \sqrt{A^2 + 4B}.$$

Square both sides to remove the square root:

$$(2\alpha - A)^2 = A^2 + 4B.$$

Expanding the left-hand side gives

$$4\alpha^2 - 4A\alpha + A^2 = A^2 + 4B.$$

Subtracting A^2 from both sides and dividing by 4, we obtain

$$\alpha^2 - A\alpha = B.$$

This identity is crucial: it is equivalent to saying α is a root of $x^2 - Ax - B = 0$.

Now start from the hypothesis

$$P_{n+1} \leq AP_n + BP_{n-1} + C.$$

Add $(\alpha - A)P_n$ to both sides. This is the key designed move — we add exactly the multiple of P_n that will make factorization possible:

$$P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n \leq (AP_n + BP_{n-1} + C) + (\alpha - A)P_n.$$

Combine like terms on the right:

$$(AP_n + (\alpha - A)P_n) + BP_{n-1} + C = \alpha P_n + BP_{n-1} + C.$$

So we have

$$P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n \leq \alpha P_n + BP_{n-1} + C.$$

Substituting $B = \alpha^2 - A\alpha$ into the right-hand side, we have

$$\alpha P_n + BP_{n-1} = \alpha P_n + (\alpha^2 - A\alpha)P_{n-1}.$$

Grouping the terms and factoring α

$$\alpha P_n + \alpha^2 P_{n-1} - A\alpha P_{n-1} = \alpha(P_n + (\alpha - A)P_{n-1}).$$

Thus the inequality becomes

$$P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n \leq \alpha(P_n + (\alpha - A)P_{n-1}) + C.$$

Let

$$T_n := P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n, \quad n \geq 0.$$

Then the inequality above is compactly written as the first-order inhomogeneous inequality

$$T_n \leq \alpha T_{n-1} + C, \quad 1 \leq n \leq N - 1,$$

with initial value

$$T_0 = P_1 + (\alpha - A)P_0.$$

We claim that for every integer $n \geq 0$,

$$T_n \leq \alpha^n T_0 + C \frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1},$$

with the understanding that when $\alpha = 1$ the right-hand side should be interpreted as $\alpha^n T_0 + Cn = T_0 + Cn$. We prove the claim by induction on n .

Base case $n = 0$: the inequality reads $T_0 \leq \alpha^0 T_0 + C \frac{\alpha^0 - 1}{\alpha - 1}$. Since $\alpha^0 = 1$ and the geometric term is zero when $n = 0$, the base case is $T_0 \leq T_0$, which is true.

Inductive step: assume the formula holds for some $n - 1 \geq 0$, i.e.

$$T_{n-1} \leq \alpha^{n-1}T_0 + C\frac{\alpha^{n-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1}.$$

Using the recurrence $T_n \leq \alpha T_{n-1} + C$, we get

$$T_n \leq \alpha\left(\alpha^{n-1}T_0 + C\frac{\alpha^{n-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1}\right) + C = \alpha^n T_0 + C\left(\alpha\frac{\alpha^{n-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1}\right) + C.$$

Simplifying the geometric part:

$$\alpha\frac{\alpha^{n-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1} + 1 = \frac{\alpha^n - \alpha}{\alpha - 1} + \frac{\alpha - 1}{\alpha - 1} = \frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1}.$$

Multiplying by C yields

$$C\left(\alpha\frac{\alpha^{n-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1}\right) + C = C\frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1},$$

so altogether

$$T_n \leq \alpha^n T_0 + C\frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1},$$

which proves the inductive step. By induction the claim holds for all $n \geq 0$.

Recall $T_n = P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n$ and $T_0 = P_1 + (\alpha - A)P_0$. Substituting these into the bound for T_n gives the desired inequality:

$$P_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)P_n \leq \alpha^n [P_1 + (\alpha - A)P_0] + C\frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1},$$

for every n with $1 \leq n \leq N - 1$.

This completes the proof.

Squeeze Theorem (Dawkins, Calculus Notes)

Suppose that for all x on $[a, b]$ (except possibly at $x = c$) we have,

$$f(x) \leq h(x) \leq g(x)$$

Also suppose that,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow c} f(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow c} g(x) = L$$

for some $a \leq c \leq b$. Then,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow c} h(x) = L$$

Theorem 6

If $hL < 2$ then the trapezoidal approximation rule for the QSDE problem converges to the exact solution, where $L = \max_{t \in [t_0, T]} |K_{\eta\xi}(t)|$.

Proof

Let

$$H_i = |\langle \eta, X(t_i)\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_i\xi \rangle|.$$

Here, $X(t_i)$ is the exact solution of the integral equation, while X_i denotes the numerical solution given by the trapezoidal rule. From the integral form of the QSDE,

the exact solution satisfies

$$\langle \eta, X(t_{i+1})\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X(t_i)\xi \rangle + \int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi) ds.$$

So, the increment is given by the exact integral.

The trapezoidal rule says

$$\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi) ds \approx \frac{h}{2} \left(P(t_i, X(t_i)) + P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) \right) (\eta, \xi).$$

This is the approximation step. The remainder term is

$$R = -\frac{h^3}{12} P^{(2)}(\tau)(\eta, \xi), \quad \tau \in [t_i, t_{i+1}],$$

and we let

$$M = \max_{\tau \in [t_0, T]} \left| \frac{1}{12} X_{\eta\xi}^{(3)}(\tau) \right|.$$

The trapezoidal scheme replaces $X(t_j)$ by the approximations X_j :

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1}\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_i\xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2} \left(P(t_i, X_i) + P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}) \right) (\eta, \xi).$$

Now, subtracting the numerical scheme from the exact equation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta, X(t_{i+1})\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{i+1}\xi \rangle &= (\langle \eta, X(t_i)\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_i\xi \rangle) + \frac{h}{2} \left((P(t_i, X(t_i)) - P(t_i, X_i))(\eta, \xi) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) - P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}))(\eta, \xi) \right) + R. \end{aligned}$$

Taking absolute values, at this point we apply the **triangle inequality**

$$|a + b + c + R| \leq |a| + |b| + |c| + |R|,$$

Hence, we get;

$$\begin{aligned} H_{i+1} &\leq |\langle \eta, X(t_i)\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_i\xi \rangle| \\ &\quad + \frac{h}{2} \left(|P(t_i, X(t_i)) - P(t_i, X_i)| + |P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) - P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1})| \right) + h^3 M. \end{aligned}$$

Since $P(t, x)$ is Lipschitz continuous in x with constant L , we have

$$|P(t, X(t)) - P(t, X_i)| \leq L|X(t) - X_i| = LH_i.$$

So,

$$H_{i+1} \leq H_i + \frac{hL}{2} (H_i + H_{i+1}) + h^3 M.$$

Rearranging,

$$H_{i+1} - \frac{hL}{2} H_{i+1} \leq H_i + \frac{hL}{2} H_i + h^3 M.$$

Simplifying, we have

$$\left(1 - \frac{hL}{2}\right) H_{i+1} \leq \left(1 + \frac{hL}{2}\right) H_i + h^3 M.$$

Thus,

$$H_{i+1} \leq \frac{\left(1 + \frac{hL}{2}\right) H_i + h^3 M}{1 - \frac{hL}{2}}.$$

Multiplying top and bottom by 2 to simplify denominators, we get

$$H_{i+1} \leq \frac{2 + hL}{2 - hL} H_i + \frac{2h^3 M}{2 - hL}.$$

Where

$$M = \max_{\tau \in [t_0, T]} \left| \frac{1}{12} X_{\eta\xi}^{(3)}(\tau) \right|.$$

This gives us a one-step recurrence relation:

$$H_{i+1} \leq AH_i + C,$$

where

$$A = \frac{2 + hL}{2 - hL}, \quad C = \frac{2h^3M}{2 - hL}.$$

Applying Lemma 1 with $H_0 = 0$ (exact initial condition), we have:

$$H_n \leq A^{n-1}H_1 + C \cdot \frac{A^{n-1} - 1}{A - 1}.$$

For $n = N$, we have:

$$H_N \leq A^{N-1}H_1 + C \cdot \frac{A^{N-1} - 1}{A - 1}.$$

As $h \rightarrow 0$,

$$A = \frac{2 + hL}{2 - hL} \rightarrow 1, \quad C = \frac{2h^3M}{2 - hL} \rightarrow 0,$$

and we have;

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left[A^{N-1}H_1 + C \cdot \frac{A^{N-1} - 1}{A - 1} \right] = 0.$$

Since $H_N \geq 0$, we have

$$0 \leq H_N \leq (\text{quantity tending to } 0).$$

By the squeeze theorem, it follows that

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} H_N = 0.$$

4.4.5 Initial error

At the initial step, we have $H_0 = 0$. This follows directly from the definition

$$H_i = |X(t_i) - X_i|,$$

where $X(t_i)$ is the exact solution at t_i and X_i is the numerical approximation. At $i = 0$, both the exact and numerical solutions start from the same initial condition $X(t_0) = X_0$. Hence,

$$H_0 = |X(t_0) - X_0| = 0.$$

This vanishing initial error is crucial when applying Lemma 4.1, since it simplifies the recurrence relation significantly.

4.5 Implicit Simpson's Method for Classical Ordinary Differential Equations

4.5.1 Derivation of Simpson's Rule

The 3-point quadrature rule is known as Simpson's rule. Consider three equally spaced points with spacing h :

$$x_2 = x_1 + h$$

$$x_3 = x_1 + 2h$$

The function $f(x)$ is approximated by the Lagrange interpolating polynomial through these three points:

$$P_3(x) = \frac{(x - x_2)(x - x_3)}{(x_1 - x_2)(x_1 - x_3)}f_1 + \frac{(x - x_1)(x - x_3)}{(x_2 - x_1)(x_2 - x_3)}f_2 + \frac{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)}{(x_3 - x_1)(x_3 - x_2)}f_3$$

Substituting the differences:

$$x_1 - x_2 = -h,$$

$$x_1 - x_3 = -2h$$

$$x_2 - x_1 = h,$$

$$x_2 - x_3 = -h$$

$$x_3 - x_1 = 2h,$$

$$x_3 - x_2 = h$$

we obtain:

$$P_3(x) = \frac{(x-x_2)(x-x_3)}{2h^2}f_1 - \frac{(x-x_1)(x-x_3)}{h^2}f_2 + \frac{(x-x_1)(x-x_2)}{2h^2}f_3$$

Expanding the numerators:

$$(x-x_2)(x-x_3) = x^2 - x(x_2+x_3) + x_2x_3$$

$$(x-x_1)(x-x_3) = x^2 - x(x_1+x_3) + x_1x_3$$

$$(x-x_1)(x-x_2) = x^2 - x(x_1+x_2) + x_1x_2$$

Substituting $x_2 = x_1 + h$ and $x_3 = x_1 + 2h$:

$$x_2 + x_3 = 2x_1 + 3h,$$

$$x_2x_3 = (x_1 + h)(x_1 + 2h)$$

$$x_1 + x_3 = 2x_1 + 2h,$$

$$x_1x_3 = x_1(x_1 + 2h)$$

$$x_1 + x_2 = 2x_1 + h,$$

$$x_1x_2 = x_1(x_1 + h)$$

Thus the polynomial becomes:

$$P_3(x) = \frac{1}{h^2} \left\{ x^2 \left(\frac{1}{2}f_1 - f_2 + \frac{1}{2}f_3 \right) + x \left[-\frac{1}{2}(2x_1 + 3h)f_1 + (2x_1 + 2h)f_2 - \frac{1}{2}(2x_1 + h)f_3 \right] + \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_1 + h)(x_1 + 2h)f_1 - x_1(x_1 + 2h)f_2 + \frac{1}{2}x_1(x_1 + h)f_3 \right] \right\}$$

Now integrate from x_1 to $x_3 = x_1 + 2h$:

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_3} f(x) dx \approx \int_{x_1}^{x_1+2h} P_3(x) dx$$

Using the antiderivatives:

$$\int x^2 dx = \frac{1}{3}x^3, \quad \int x dx = \frac{1}{2}x^2, \quad \int 1 dx = x$$

and evaluating from x_1 to $x_1 + 2h$, after considerable algebraic simplification, we obtain the final result:

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_3} f(x) dx = \frac{1}{3}h(f_1 + 4f_2 + f_3) - \frac{1}{90}h^5 f^{(4)}(\xi) \quad (4.18)$$

where $\xi \in [x_1, x_3]$. This is Simpson's rule with its error term.

4.6 Implicit Simpson's Method for Classical Ordinary Differential Equations

We consider the classical initial value problem:

$$\begin{cases} x'(t) = f(t, x(t)), \\ x(t_0) = x_0. \end{cases} \quad (4.19)$$

Let us replace the interval $[t_0, T]$ by a set of discrete equally spaced grid points:

$$t_0 < t_1 < t_2 < \cdots < t_N; \quad h = \frac{T - t_0}{N}, \quad t_i = t_0 + ih \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \quad (4.20)$$

To obtain Simpson's method for numerical integration, we integrate the system from t_{i-1} to t_{i+1} and apply the classical Simpson's rule to the right-hand side integral:

$$\int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_{i+1}} x'(s) ds = \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_{i+1}} f(s, x(s)) ds, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \quad (4.21)$$

Therefore,

$$x(t_{i+1}) - x(t_{i-1}) = \frac{h}{3} [f(t_{i-1}, x(t_{i-1})) + 4f(t_i, x(t_i)) + f(t_{i+1}, x(t_{i+1}))]. \quad (4.22)$$

Equation (4.19) is an implicit equation in terms of $x(t_{i+1})$.

The derived implicit scheme is the following:

$$\begin{cases} x_0 = x(t_0), \\ x_1 = x_0 + hf(t_0, x_0) + \frac{h^2}{2} f'(t_0, x_0), \\ x_{i+1}^{(m+1)} = x_{i-1} + \frac{h}{3} f(t_{i-1}, x_{i-1}) + \frac{4h}{3} f(t_i, x_i) + \frac{h}{3} f(t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}^{(m)}), \\ i = 1, 2, \dots; \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{cases} \quad (4.23)$$

In order to avoid dealing with an implicit equation, we may replace $x_{i+1} = x_i + hf(t_i, x_i) + \frac{h^2}{2} f'(t_i, x_i)$, with a second order Taylor approximation.

Error Analysis

The error in the difference equation corresponding to our recursive relation and the continuous equation is called the local truncation error (LTE). This is the next term in the Taylor series which corresponds to the derived discrete method or the cut-off term. The global truncation error on the other hand is the accumulated error in the final result $x(T)$. Thus, if the LTE is $O(h^m)$, then it is easy to show that the global

error is $O(h^{m-1})$ and we say that the method is of order $(m - 1)$.

4.7 Implicit Simpson's Two-Step Method for QSDEs

This section focuses on constructing a numerical solution for quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs) of the form

$$\frac{d}{dt}\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle = P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T],$$

which can be written in integral form as

$$\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle = \langle\eta, X_0\xi\rangle + \int_{t_0}^t P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi)ds. \quad (4.24)$$

A numerical method is derived by applying Simpson's rule to the integral in the above equation. Since the problem is nonclassical, the right-hand side function cannot be differentiated directly. To overcome this, we assume the exact solution $X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ is of class $C^5[t_0, T]$, allowing a Taylor expansion up to fifth order.

The exact solution at t_{i+1} satisfies:

$$\langle\eta, X(t_{i+1})\xi\rangle = \langle\eta, X(t_{i-1})\xi\rangle + \frac{h}{3}X'_{\eta\xi}(t_{i-1}) + \frac{4h}{3}X'_{\eta\xi}(t_i) + \frac{h}{3}X'_{\eta\xi}(t_{i+1}) - \frac{h^5}{90}X^{(5)}_{\eta\xi}(\tau_1),$$

with $t_{i-1} \leq \tau_1 \leq t_{i+1}$. Substituting the derivative using the QSDE yields the scheme:

$$\langle\eta, X(t_{i+1})\xi\rangle = \langle\eta, X(t_{i-1})\xi\rangle + \frac{h}{3}P(t_{i-1}, X(t_{i-1})) + \frac{4h}{3}P(t_i, X(t_i)) + \frac{h}{3}P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) - \frac{h^5}{90}X^{(5)}_{\eta\xi}(\tau_1).$$

The computational algorithm is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \eta, X_0 \xi \rangle &= \langle \eta, X(t_0) \xi \rangle, \\
\langle \eta, X_1 \xi \rangle &= \langle \eta, X_0 \xi \rangle + hP(t_0, X_0)(\eta, \xi) + \frac{h^2}{2}P(t_0, X_0)(\eta, \xi), \\
\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle &= \langle \eta, X_{i-1} \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{3}P(t_{i-1}, X_{i-1})(\eta, \xi) + \frac{4h}{3}P(t_i, X_i)(\eta, \xi) \\
&\quad + \frac{h}{3}P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}^{(m)})(\eta, \xi), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots; \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (4.25)
\end{aligned}$$

This method is inherently implicit, unlike classical cases where explicit rules might apply. Whether a well-defined explicit rule exists for QSDEs remains an open problem.

The iteration proceeds as: $\langle \eta, X_2 \xi \rangle$ is computed from $\langle \eta, X_0 \xi \rangle$ and $\langle \eta, X_1 \xi \rangle$, $\langle \eta, X_3 \xi \rangle$ from $\langle \eta, X_1 \xi \rangle$ and $\langle \eta, X_2 \xi \rangle$, and so on.

Since $P(t, X)(\eta, \xi)$ and $\langle \eta, X \xi \rangle$ are complex-valued, the scheme can be split into real and imaginary parts:

$$\begin{aligned}
\operatorname{Re} \langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle &= \operatorname{Re} \langle \eta, X_{i-1} \xi \rangle + h \sum_{j=1}^{i+1} W_{ij} \operatorname{Re} P(t_j, X_j)(\eta, \xi), \\
\operatorname{Im} \langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle &= \operatorname{Im} \langle \eta, X_{i-1} \xi \rangle + h \sum_{j=1}^{i+1} W_{ij} \operatorname{Im} P(t_j, X_j)(\eta, \xi).
\end{aligned}$$

A convergence analysis for this two-step method will be developed, building on two key lemmas from the literature (Moghadam 2004)

4.8 Convergence Analysis

Theorem 7 (Adeyeye 2007)

If $hL < 3$ then the Simpson's approximation rule (4.25) for the QSDE problem (4.24) converges to the exact solution, where $L = \max_{t \in [t_0, T]} |K_{\eta\xi}(t)|$.

Proof

Let

$$H_i = |\langle \eta, X(t_i)\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_i\xi \rangle|.$$

Here, $X(t_i)$ is the exact solution of the integral equation (4.24), while X_i denotes the numerical solution given by Simpson's rule (4.25). From (4.24), the exact solution satisfies

$$\langle \eta, X(t_{i+1})\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X(t_{i-1})\xi \rangle + \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_{i+1}} P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi) ds.$$

So, the increment is given by the exact integral.

Simpson's rule says

$$\int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_{i+1}} P(s, X(s))(\eta, \xi) ds \approx \frac{h}{3} \left(P(t_{i-1}, X(t_{i-1})) + 4P(t_i, X(t_i)) + P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) \right) (\eta, \xi).$$

This is the approximation step. The remainder term is

$$R = \frac{h^5}{90} P^{(4)}(\tau)(\eta, \xi), \quad \tau \in [t_{i-1}, t_{i+1}],$$

and we let

$$M = \max_{\tau \in [t_0, T]} \left| \frac{1}{90} X_{\eta\xi}^{(5)}(\tau) \right|.$$

The scheme (4.25) replaces $X(t_j)$ by the approximations X_j :

$$\langle \eta, X_{i+1}^{(m+1)} \xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_{i-1} \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{3} \left(P(t_{i-1}, X_{i-1}) + 4P(t_i, X_i) + P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1}^{(m)}) \right) (\eta, \xi).$$

Now, subtracting the numerical scheme from the exact equation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta, X(t_{i+1}) \xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{i+1} \xi \rangle &= (\langle \eta, X(t_{i-1}) \xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{i-1} \xi \rangle) + \frac{h}{3} \left((P(t_{i-1}, X(t_{i-1})) - P(t_{i-1}, X_{i-1})) (\eta, \xi) \right. \\ &\quad + 4(P(t_i, X(t_i)) - P(t_i, X_i)) (\eta, \xi) \\ &\quad \left. + (P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) - P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1})) (\eta, \xi) \right) + R. \end{aligned}$$

Taking absolute values, at this point we apply the **triangle inequality**

$$|a + b + c + R| \leq |a| + |b| + |c| + |R|,$$

Hence, we get;

$$\begin{aligned} H_{i+1} &\leq |\langle \eta, X(t_{i-1}) \xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{i-1} \xi \rangle| \\ &\quad + \frac{h}{3} \left(|P(t_{i-1}, X(t_{i-1})) - P(t_{i-1}, X_{i-1})| \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 4|P(t_i, X(t_i)) - P(t_i, X_i)| + |P(t_{i+1}, X(t_{i+1})) - P(t_{i+1}, X_{i+1})| \right) + h^5 M. \end{aligned}$$

Since $P(t, x)$ is Lipschitz continuous in x with constant L , we have

$$|P(t, X(t)) - P(t, X_i)| \leq L|X(t) - X_i| = LH_i.$$

So,

$$H_{i+1} \leq H_{i-1} + \frac{hL}{3} \left(H_{i-1} + 4H_i + H_{i+1} \right) + h^5 M.$$

Rearranging,

$$H_{i+1} - \frac{hL}{3} H_{i+1} \leq \frac{4hL}{3} H_i + H_{i-1} + \frac{hL}{3} H_{i-1} + h^5 M.$$

Simplifying, we have

$$\left(1 - \frac{hL}{3} \right) H_{i+1} \leq \frac{4hL}{3} H_i + \left(1 + \frac{hL}{3} \right) H_{i-1} + h^5 M.$$

Thus,

$$H_{i+1} \leq \frac{\frac{4hL}{3} H_i + \left(1 + \frac{hL}{3} \right) H_{i-1} + h^5 M}{1 - \frac{hL}{3}}.$$

Dividing through by $\left(1 - \frac{hL}{3} \right)$, the inequality becomes

$$H_{i+1} \leq \frac{\frac{4hL}{3}}{1 - \frac{hL}{3}} H_i + \frac{1 + \frac{hL}{3}}{1 - \frac{hL}{3}} H_{i-1} + \frac{h^5 M}{1 - \frac{hL}{3}}.$$

Multiplying top and bottom by 3 to simplify denominators, we get

$$H_{i+1} \leq \frac{4hL}{3 - hL} H_i + \frac{3 + hL}{3 - hL} H_{i-1} + \frac{3h^5 M}{3 - hL}.$$

Where

$$M = \max_{\tau \in [t_0, T]} \left| \frac{1}{90} X_{\eta\xi}^{(5)}(\tau) \right|.$$

Applying Lemma 2 with

$$A = \frac{4hL}{3-hL}, \quad B = \frac{3+hL}{3-hL}, \quad C = \frac{3h^5M}{3-hL}, \quad \alpha = \frac{A + \sqrt{A^2 + 4B}}{2}$$

We have,

$$H_{n+1} + (\alpha - A)H_n \leq \alpha^n [H_1 + (\alpha - A)H_0] + C \cdot \frac{\alpha^n - 1}{\alpha - 1}.$$

Now, for $n = N - 1$, we have the recurrence relation:

$$H_N + (\alpha - A)H_{N-1} \leq \alpha^{N-1} [H_1 + (\alpha - A)H_0] + C \cdot \frac{\alpha^{N-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1}.$$

Since $H_0 = 0$, as $h \rightarrow 0$,

$$A = \frac{4hL}{3-hL} \rightarrow 0, \quad B = \frac{3+hL}{3-hL} \rightarrow 1, \quad C = \frac{3h^5M}{3-hL} \rightarrow 0, \quad \alpha = \frac{A + \sqrt{A^2 + 4B}}{2} \rightarrow 1$$

and we have;

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left[\alpha^{N-1} [H_1 + (\alpha - A)H_0] + C \cdot \frac{\alpha^{N-1} - 1}{\alpha - 1} \right] = 0.$$

Since $H_N \geq 0$ and $H_{N-1} \geq 0$, the left-hand side is nonnegative:

$$H_N + (\alpha - A)H_{N-1} \geq 0.$$

Therefore we have

$$0 \leq H_N + (\alpha - A)H_{N-1} \leq (\text{quantity tending to } 0).$$

By the squeeze theorem, it follows that

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} (H_N + (\alpha - A)H_{N-1}) = 0.$$

Finally, since $\alpha - A \rightarrow 1$ as $h \rightarrow 0$, the perturbation term $(\alpha - A)H_{N-1}$ is of the same order as H_{N-1} , which also vanishes in the limit. Hence

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} H_N = 0.$$

4.8.1 Initial error

At the initial step, we have $H_0 = 0$. This follows directly from the definition

$$H_i = |X(t_i) - X_i|,$$

where $X(t_i)$ is the exact solution at t_i and X_i is the numerical approximation. At $i = 0$, both the exact and numerical solutions start from the same initial condition $X(t_0) = X_0$. Hence,

$$H_0 = |X(t_0) - X_0| = 0.$$

This vanishing initial error is crucial when applying Lemma 2, since it simplifies the recurrence relation significantly.

Chapter 5

Lagrangian Quadrature and Linear Multi-step Methods for Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations

The numerical solution of quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs) presents unique challenges that stem from the non-commutative structure of quantum noise and the operator-valued nature of the processes involved. While classical stochastic numerical schemes have been extensively studied, their direct extension to the quantum setting requires careful consideration of the Hudson–Parthasarathy calculus and the preservation of quantum probabilistic properties.

This chapter explores the formulation and implementation of **Lagrangian quadrature techniques** and **linear multi-step methods** tailored specifically for QSDEs. By leveraging interpolation principles and multi-step discretization within the quantum Itô framework, we develop numerical schemes that achieve higher-order conver-

gence while maintaining stability and physical consistency.

We begin by introducing the theoretical foundations of Lagrangian quadrature in the context of quantum stochastic integrals, followed by the construction of Linear Multi-step method adapted to the quantum setting. Through numerical experiments and error analysis, we demonstrate the efficacy of these methods in simulating open quantum systems and quantum stochastic processes, providing a robust toolkit for the computational study of quantum dynamics driven by bosonic fields.

5.1 Lagrangian Quadrature Method for QSDEs

In this section, we present the Lagrangian quadrature approach, which provides an efficient and accurate scheme for approximating solutions of quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs). Since the existence results hold under the general Carathéodory conditions, we assume the following hypotheses in what follows.

5.1.1 Preliminaries and Basic Assumptions

- (a) The map $(t, X) \mapsto P(t, X)(\eta, \xi)$ of $I \times A \rightarrow C$ is continuous for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$. This ensures that the problem is well-defined.
- (b) P is Lipschitzian with continuous Lipschitz function $K_{\eta\xi}^p(t)$ on $[0, T] = I$, for $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$.
- (c) The unique exact solution $X(t)$ of the differential problem (1.3) is such that the map

$$t \mapsto \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = X_{\eta\xi}(t)$$

is of class $C^1(I)$ for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$; that is, $X(t)$ is continuously differentiable, and hence $X_{\eta\xi}(t) \in C^1(I)$.

Let t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N be N distinct points of the interval $[t_0, T]$ for some positive integer N . We seek an interpolating approximation to the value $X(t)$ of the exact solution in the form

$$X(t) \cong \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X(t_p), \quad (5.1)$$

where $L_p(t)$ are the *Lagrange basis functions* defined by

$$L_p(t) = \prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq p}}^N \frac{(t - t_k)}{(t_p - t_k)}, \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad t \neq t_p. \quad (5.2)$$

The function $L_p(t)$ is associated with the p^{th} interpolation node. Alternatively, it can be expressed as

$$L_p(t) = \frac{T_N(t)}{(t - t_p) T'_N(t_p)},$$

where

$$T_N(t) = (t - t_1)(t - t_2) \cdots (t - t_N).$$

The Lagrange basis functions satisfy the property

$$L_k(t_p) = \begin{cases} 1, & p = k, \\ 0, & p \neq k. \end{cases}$$

This means that at its own node, the function L_k takes the value 1, and at all other nodes, it takes the value 0.

5.2 Quadrature Coefficients and Derivatives

We define the quadrature coefficient $a_{pk}^{(n)}$ by

$$\left. \frac{d^n}{dt^n} L_k(t) \right|_{t=t_p} = a_{pk}^{(n)}. \quad (5.3)$$

At the interpolation nodes t_p , $p = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the Lagrangian interpolants satisfy $L_k(t_p) = \delta_{pk}$, where δ_{pk} is the Kronecker delta. This property remains valid under any linear transformation of the form $t = au + b$.

In most applications, it is convenient to transform the interval $I = [t_0, T]$ into, say, the standard interval $[-1, 1]$ by writing

$$u = \frac{2t - T - t_0}{T - t_0}.$$

Lemma 3 (Ayoola 2002)

For each $p, m = 1, 2, \dots, N$,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} L_p(t) = -a_{mp}^{(1)} L_m(t),$$

where $a_{mp}^{(1)} = L_p'(t_m)$.

Proof

We begin with the definition of the Lagrange basis function:

$$L_p(t) = \prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq p}}^N \frac{t - t_k}{t_p - t_k}.$$

Let us compute the partial derivative of $L_p(t)$ with respect to one of the nodes, say t_m .

Case 1: When $m \neq p$

Here, t_m appears both in the numerator and denominator of the product. Differentiating $L_p(t)$ with respect to t_m gives

$$\frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_m} = L_p(t) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \ln \left(\prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq p}}^N \frac{t - t_k}{t_p - t_k} \right) \right].$$

Since only the term $k = m$ depends on t_m , we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \ln \left(\frac{t - t_m}{t_p - t_m} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} [\ln(t - t_m) - \ln(t_p - t_m)] = \left(-\frac{1}{t - t_m} \right) - \left(-\frac{1}{t_p - t_m} \right) = \frac{1}{t_p - t_m} - \frac{1}{t - t_m}.$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_m} = L_p(t) \left(\frac{1}{t_p - t_m} - \frac{1}{t - t_m} \right).$$

Simplifying, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_m} = L_p(t) \cdot \frac{t - t_p}{(t_p - t_m)(t - t_m)}.$$

Now recall that for $m \neq p$,

$$L_m(t) = \frac{t - t_p}{t_m - t_p} \prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq m, p}}^N \frac{t - t_k}{t_m - t_k},$$

and

$$L'_p(t_m) = \prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq p, m}}^N \frac{t_m - t_k}{t_p - t_k} \cdot \frac{1}{t_p - t_m}.$$

By comparing both expressions, we find that

$$\frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_m} = -L'_p(t_m)L_m(t).$$

That is,

$$\frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_m} = -a_{mp}^{(1)}L_m(t).$$

Case 2: When $m = p$

In this case, all t_k with $k \neq p$ are independent of t_p , so differentiation gives

$$\frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_p} = - \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq p}}^N \frac{\partial L_p(t)}{\partial t_m} = - \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq p}}^N (-a_{mp}^{(1)}L_m(t)) = \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq p}}^N a_{mp}^{(1)}L_m(t).$$

Thus, the identity holds for all $p, m = 1, 2, \dots, N$.

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} L_p(t) = -a_{mp}^{(1)}L_m(t), \quad \text{where } a_{mp}^{(1)} = L'_p(t_m).}$$

This ends the proof.

We shall write $X(t_p)$ for the value of the exact solution $X(t)$ at $t = t_p$, and X_p as

its approximate value at the same point. For non-nodal points $t \in [t_0, T]$, X_t denotes the approximate value of $X(t)$.

The global error at t_p is given by $\|e_p\|_{\eta\xi} = \|X(t_p) - X_p\|_{\eta\xi}$, while the local error at any point t is

$$\|e_t\|_{\eta\xi} = \|X(t) - X_t\|_{\eta\xi},$$

for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$.

5.3 Interpolation and Error Analysis

Ordinarily, equation (5.1) may be used to interpolate $\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ when $\langle \eta, X(t_p)\xi \rangle$ are given for $p = 1, 2, \dots, N$. During computation, X_p approximates $X(t_p)$, so that (5.1) becomes

$$\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle \cong \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \langle \eta, X_p\xi \rangle.$$

Definition 12. Let $L, R : \mathbb{N} \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \mapsto \text{sesq}[\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}]$; then, the quantities $|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|$ and $|R(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|$ are called the local truncation error and the round-off error, respectively.

If the exact representation for $\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ is given by

$$\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \langle \eta, X(t_p)\xi \rangle + L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad (5.4)$$

and the computed representation by

$$\langle \eta, X_t\xi \rangle = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \langle \eta, X_p\xi \rangle + R(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad (5.5)$$

then the local truncation error $L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ arises from the polynomial interpolation itself, while the round-off error $R(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ is due to numerical computation.

The complex-valued map $X_{\eta\xi}(t) : [t_0, T] \rightarrow C$ is defined by

$$X_{\eta\xi}(t) = \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$$

for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, where $X(t)$ is the exact solution of the underlying quantum stochastic differential equation. Let

$$e_{\eta\xi}(t) = \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_t\xi \rangle.$$

Then, the global error satisfies

$$\|e_{\eta\xi}\|_\infty \leq \sum_{p=1}^N |L_p(t)| \|e_p\|_{\eta\xi} + |L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| + |R(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|. \quad (5.6)$$

At the nodal points t_k , $L(N, X(t_k))(\eta, \xi) = 0$. This implies that the local truncation error due to interpolation vanishes at each interpolation node.

5.4 Chebyshev Minimax Approximation

Next, we introduce the notion of the Chebyshev minimax best approximation of continuous complex-valued functions.

Let $C[t_0, T]$ denote the space of continuous complex-valued functions on $[t_0, T]$ equipped

with the uniform norm (or supremum norm)

$$\|f\|_\infty = \max_{t \in [t_0, T]} |f(t)|.$$

For each positive integer N , let U_N denote the linear subspace of $C[t_0, T]$ consisting of all polynomials of degree at most N (i.e., $\deg P \leq N$). For $f \in C[t_0, T]$, define the distance from f to U_N by

$$\text{dist}(f, U_N) = \min_{u \in U_N} \|f - u\|_\infty.$$

We refer to the element $u \in U_N$ as the best approximation of f if and only if

$$\|f - u\|_\infty = \text{dist}(f, U_N).$$

By the Chebyshev minimax theory, for any real or complex-valued continuous function f on $[t_0, T]$ and for each positive integer N , there exists a polynomial P_N of degree N which gives the best approximation to f in the minimax sense.

Hence, for suitable nodal points t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N , the Lagrangian interpolating polynomial will provide a best approximation in the minimax sense, and the local truncation error $L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ will vanish at these nodes.

To this end, suitable points t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N in $[t_0, T]$ can be found at which the error function

$$R_N(t) = f(t) - P_N(t) \tag{5.7}$$

has alternate equal and opposite constant values. This condition is satisfied if and only if

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_j} [R_N(t)]^2 = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (5.8)$$

Theorem 8 (Ayoola 2002)

Let $X(t)$ be the exact solution of problem (1.3) and let $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$. Then, for a suitable choice of nodes t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N in $[t_0, T]$, the Lagrangian interpolating projection

$$X_{\eta\xi}(t) \cong \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \quad (5.9)$$

satisfies

$$\max_{[t_0, T]} \left| X_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right| = \text{dist}(X_{\eta\xi}, U_N) \quad (5.10)$$

if and only if

$$X'_{\eta\xi}(t_m) = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (5.11)$$

For each non-nodal point $t \in [t_0, T]$ and $\forall \eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$.

Proof

For $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, we have from equation (5.4)

$$|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| = \left| \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \langle \eta, X(t_p)\xi \rangle \right|, \quad (5.12)$$

where $L_p(t) = L_p(t; t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N)$ is the Lagrange polynomial defined earlier.

Let us define

$$\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = X_{\eta\xi}(t) = U_{\eta\xi}(t) + iV_{\eta\xi}(t), \quad (5.13)$$

for some real-valued functions $U_{\eta\xi}(t)$ and $V_{\eta\xi}(t)$. Then,

$$L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \left(U_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)U_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right) + i \left(V_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)V_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right). \quad (5.14)$$

Hence,

$$|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|^2 = \left(U_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)U_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right)^2 + \left(V_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)V_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right)^2. \quad (5.15)$$

Since $U_{\eta\xi}(t)$ and $V_{\eta\xi}(t)$ are continuous functions on $[t_0, T]$, the Chebyshev minimax theory ensures that

$$\max_{[t_0, T]} |L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| \quad (5.16)$$

is minimized for a suitable choice of nodes t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N if and only if

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} |L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|^2 = 0, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (5.17)$$

Expanding the derivative, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} |L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|^2 &= 2 \left(U_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)U_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right) \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)U_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right) \\ &\quad + 2 \left(V_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)V_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right) \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)V_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.18)$$

Now, the functions $U_{\eta\xi}(t)$ and $V_{\eta\xi}(t)$ depend on t but not on the nodes t_m . Hence,

their partial derivatives with respect to t_m vanish, meaning that only the derivatives of $L_p(t)$ contribute. Therefore,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \left(\sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) U_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \left(\sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) V_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \right) = 0. \quad (5.19)$$

This implies that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) = 0. \quad (5.20)$$

Applying the product rule, we obtain

$$\sum_{p=1}^N \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} L_p(t) \right) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) + \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) = 0. \quad (5.21)$$

Hence,

$$L_m(t) \left[\sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) - X'_{\eta\xi}(t_m) \right] = 0. \quad (5.22)$$

Since $L_m(t) \neq 0$, it follows that

$$X'_{\eta\xi}(t_m) = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (5.23)$$

Remark 1. Applying equation (5.23) at each of the nodes transforms the quantum stochastic differential equation (1.3) into a purely algebraic system given by

$$\sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) = P(t_m, X(t_m))(\eta, \xi), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

with initial condition transforming to

$$\sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t_0) X_{n\varepsilon}(t_p) \cong X_{n\varepsilon}(t_0).$$

Therefore, instead of solving a differential equation, we now solve a system of algebraic equations in the unknowns $X_{\eta\xi}(t_p)$. This significantly reduces computational complexity while maintaining the accuracy and stability of the Lagrangian quadrature approximation.

(ii) If we express

$$X_{n\varepsilon}(t) = U_{n\varepsilon}(t) + iV_{n\varepsilon}(t)$$

and

$$P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \text{Re}[P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi)] + i\text{Im}[P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi)],$$

for some real-valued functions $t \mapsto U_{n\varepsilon}(t)$ and $t \mapsto V_{n\varepsilon}(t)$, then the system of algebraic equations in (i) above may be decomposed into real and imaginary parts as follows:

$$\sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} U_{n\varepsilon}(t_p) = \text{Re}[P(t_m, X(t_m))(\eta, \xi)],$$

$$\sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t_0) U_{n\varepsilon}(t_p) \cong U_{n\varepsilon}(t_0),$$

and

$$\sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} V_{n\varepsilon}(t_p) = \text{Im}[P(t_m, X(t_m))(\eta, \xi)],$$

$$\sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t_0) V_{n\varepsilon}(t_p) \cong V_{n\varepsilon}(t_0), \quad m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N.$$

It is observed that each of these systems consists of $N + 1$ algebraic equations in N unknowns. Hence, the system is overdetermined. The details of how such systems are solved will be discussed in section 5.6

(iii) The quadrature coefficients $a_{mp}^{(s)}$ defined by (5.3), satisfy

$$a_{mp}^{(s)} = \sum_{k=1}^N a_{mk}^{(s-q)} a_{kp}^{(q)},$$

for every $q = 1, 2, \dots, s - 1$, with $s < N$.

The numerical solution of the systems (i) and (ii) above can be efficiently handled by modern computers. This is achieved by employing standard algorithms that minimize both computation time and memory usage for the $N \times N$ matrix $[a_{ij}^{(1)}]$.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the computational cost of constructing Lagrange polynomials can become very high due to the large number of multiplications and additions involved. In practice, a relatively low order of quadrature (typically $3 \leq N \leq 15$) is usually sufficient to maintain efficiency while minimizing computational effort and storage space.

The following result is the direct consequence of the preceding theorem

Corollary 1 (Ayoola 2002)

Assume that for each pair of $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, the exact solution $X(t)$ of problem (1.3) is such that

$$X_{\eta\xi}(\cdot) \in C^{s+1}[t_0, T], \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Then, the representation

$$X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t) \cong \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t_p)$$

satisfies

$$\max_{t \in [t_0, T]} \left| X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t_p) \right| = \text{dist}(X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}, U_N)$$

if and only if

$$X_{\eta\xi}^{(s+1)}(t_m) = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(s+1)} X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t_p),$$

where the coefficients $a_{mp}^{(s+1)}$ depend on the degree of approximation.

Proof

Using the inner product form of equation (5.1), if $X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ is replaced by its derivative, then by Theorem 7 we have

$$X'_{\eta\xi}(t) \cong \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X'_{\eta\xi}(t_p)$$

as the best approximation of $X'_{\eta\xi}(t)$, provided that

$$X''_{\eta\xi}(t_m) = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X'_{\eta\xi}(t_p), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

From equation (5.23), we know that

$$X'_{\eta\xi}(t_p) = \sum_{k=1}^N a_{pk}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_k).$$

Substituting this into the previous equation gives

$$\begin{aligned}
X_{\eta\xi}''(t_m) &= \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} \sum_{k=1}^N a_{pk}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_k) \\
&= \sum_{p=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} a_{pk}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_k) \\
&= \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(2)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p),
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$a_{mp}^{(2)} = \sum_{k=1}^N a_{mk}^{(1)} a_{kp}^{(1)}.$$

By Remark 2(iii), this recursive relation generalizes to

$$a_{mp}^{(s+1)} = \sum_{k=1}^N a_{mk}^{(1)} a_{kp}^{(s)}.$$

Hence, it follows that the representation

$$X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t) \cong \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t_p)$$

is the best approximation of $X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t)$ if and only if

$$X_{\eta\xi}^{(s+1)}(t_m) = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}^{(s)}(t_p),$$

that is,

$$X_{\eta\xi}^{(s+1)}(t_m) = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(s+1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p),$$

where q can take any value from 1 to $s - 1$, with $s < N$.

5.5 The Choice of Lagrangian Interpolants and Computation of Quadrature Coefficients $a_{ij}^{(1)}$

In this section, we present the computation of the Lagrangian interpolants $L_p(t)$ and the quadrature coefficients $a_{ij}^{(k)}$. These computations are universal and independent of the specific choice of parameters $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, following the same methodology as in classical approximation theory.

5.5.1 Orthogonal Lagrangian Interpolants

For reasons of mathematical convenience and numerical stability, we choose the set of Lagrangian interpolants $\{L_p(t)\}$ to be orthogonal on the interval $[t_0, T]$ with respect to an appropriate weight function $w(t)$. This orthogonality condition ensures that if K_p is a normalization constant and δ_{pq} denotes the Kronecker delta, then the following relation holds:

$$\int_{t_0}^T L_p(t)L_q(t)w(t) dt = K_p\delta_{pq} \quad (5.24)$$

Since orthogonal polynomials with respect to specific weight functions on well-defined intervals are unique and have special names in mathematical literature, we consider the following important cases:

Legendre Polynomials ($w(t) = 1$)

For the unit weight function, the natural interval is $[-1, 1]$, which can be transformed to the general interval $[t_0, T]$ via the linear transformation:

$$t' = \frac{1}{2}(T - t_0)t + \frac{1}{2}(T + t_0)$$

In this case, equation (5.24) reduces to:

$$\sum_{s=0}^{N-2} c_s \int_{-1}^1 t^s \prod_{k=1}^N (t - t_k) dt = K_p \delta_{pq} \quad (5.25)$$

Equation (5.25) implies that the product polynomial $T_N(t)$ associated with $L_p(t)$ is the Legendre polynomial $P_N(t)$ of degree N .

Laguerre Polynomials ($w(t) = e^{-t}$, $t \in [0, \infty)$)

Applying this weight function in (5.24), we find that the product polynomial associated with $L_p(t)$ is the Laguerre polynomial:

$$G_N(t) = e^t \frac{d^N}{dt^N} (e^{-t} t^N) \quad (5.26)$$

Chebyshev Polynomials ($w(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-t^2}}$, $t \in [-1, 1]$)

The product polynomial associated with $L_p(t)$ is the Chebyshev polynomial:

$$T_N(t) = \cos(N \cos^{-1} t)$$

with nodes given by:

$$t_j = \cos \left[\frac{(2j-1)\pi}{2N} \right], \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

Hermite Polynomials ($w(t) = e^{-t^2}$; $-\infty < t < \infty$)

The product polynomial is the Hermite polynomial $H_N(t)$ where:

$$H_N(t) = (-1)^N e^{t^2} \frac{d^N}{dt^N} e^{-t^2} \quad (5.27)$$

5.5.2 Computation of Quadrature Coefficients $a_{ij}^{(k)}$

For the remainder of this section, we focus specifically on the case of the unit weight function in the interval $[-1, 1]$ with the product polynomial $T_N(t)$ identified as the Legendre polynomial $P_N(t)$ of degree N .

The Lagrangian interpolants are given by:

$$L_p(t) = \frac{T_N(t)}{(t - t_p)T'_N(t_p)}$$

Differentiating this expression yields:

$$L'_p(t) = \frac{(t - t_p)T'_N(t_p)T''_N(t) - T_N(t)T''_N(t_p)}{[(t - t_p)T'_N(t_p)]^2} \quad (5.28)$$

The quadrature coefficients $a_{mp}^{(1)}$ are defined as the derivatives of the Lagrangian interpolants at the nodes:

$$a_{mp}^{(1)} := L'_p(t_m)$$

For $m \neq p$, we obtain:

$$a_{mp}^{(1)} = \frac{(t_m - t_p)T'_N(t_p)T''_N(t_m) - T_N(t_m)T''_N(t_p)}{(t_m - t_p)^2[T'_N(t_p)]^2} = \frac{T'_N(t_m)}{(t_m - t_p)T'_N(t_p)} \quad (5.29)$$

From equations (5.25) and (5.29), we derive the expression for off-diagonal coefficients:

$$a_{pq}^{(1)} = \frac{P'_N(t_p)}{(t_p - t_q)P'_N(t_q)}, \quad p \neq q \quad (5.30)$$

For the diagonal elements $a_{pp}^{(1)}$, we apply L'Hôpital's rule:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{pp}^{(1)} &= \lim_{t \rightarrow t_p} L'_p(t) \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow t_p} \frac{T'_N(t_p)[T'_N(t) + (t - t_p)T''_N(t) - T'_N(t)]}{2(t - t_p)[T'_N(t_p)]^2} \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow t_p} \frac{T''_N(t)}{2T'_N(t_p)} \\ &= \frac{T''_N(t_p)}{2T'_N(t_p)} = \frac{P''_N(t_p)}{2P'_N(t_p)} \end{aligned} \quad (5.31)$$

By equation (5.25), $T_N(t) = P_N(t)$ where the Legendre polynomial is defined as:

$$P_N(t) = \frac{1}{2^N N!} \frac{d^N}{dt^N} (t^2 - 1)^N, \quad t \in [-1, 1]$$

Using known properties of Legendre polynomials, we can simplify the diagonal coefficients to:

$$a_{pp}^{(1)} = \frac{P''_N(t_p)}{2P'_N(t_p)} = \frac{t_p}{1 - t_p^2}$$

Additionally, the quadrature coefficients exhibit the following symmetry property:

$$a_{pq}^{(1)} = -a_{N+1-p, N+1-q}^{(1)}$$

This symmetry property is particularly useful for reducing computational costs in practical implementations.

5.6 Bounds for the Local and Global Truncation Errors, Convergence, and Application to Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations

We now establish a bound for the local truncation error by assuming sufficient smoothness conditions on the map $t \mapsto \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ for each pair $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$. Using these assumptions, we aim to prove that

$$|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } N \rightarrow \infty.$$

To proceed, we assume that the mappings $(\mu(E)(\cdot, X(\cdot))(\eta, \xi))$, $(\gamma^F(\cdot, X(\cdot))(\eta, \xi))$, $((\sigma G)(\cdot, X(\cdot))(\eta, \xi))$, and $(H(\cdot, X(\cdot))(\eta, \xi))$ defining $(P(\cdot, X(\cdot))(\eta, \xi))$ are of class $C^N[t_0, T]$. This ensures that the map $t \mapsto X_{\eta\xi}(\cdot)$ is also of class $C^N[t_0, T]$.

Theorem 9 (Ayoola 2002)

Suppose X is the exact solution of problem (1.3) such that $X_{\eta\xi}(\cdot)$ is of class $C^N[t_0, T]$ for each $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ and N a positive integer. Then the local truncation error

$L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ satisfies

$$|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| \leq \frac{1}{N!} \max_{[t_0, T]} \left[\left| X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(t) \right| \cdot \left| t^N - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N \right| \right] \quad (5.32)$$

Proof

By equation (5.4) in the earlier section, we have

$$L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \langle \eta, X(t_p)\xi \rangle. \quad (5.33)$$

Equivalently,

$$L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = X_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p). \quad (5.34)$$

We now express $X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ as a complex-valued function of the form

$$X_{\eta\xi}(t) = U_{\eta\xi}(t) + iV_{\eta\xi}(t), \quad (5.35)$$

where $U_{\eta\xi}(t)$ and $V_{\eta\xi}(t)$ are real-valued functions. Since $X_{\eta\xi}(\cdot)$ is of class $C^N[t_0, T]$, it follows that both $U_{\eta\xi}(\cdot)$ and $V_{\eta\xi}(\cdot)$ belong to $C^N[t_0, T]$.

By Taylor's theorem, for $0 \leq t \leq 1$ and $0 < \theta < 1$,

$$U_{\eta\xi}(t) = \sum_{p=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^p}{p!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(p)}(0) + \frac{t^N}{N!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t), \quad (5.36)$$

and similarly,

$$V_{\eta\xi}(t) = \sum_{p=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^p}{p!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(p)}(0) + \frac{t^N}{N!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t), \quad (5.37)$$

both expanded about $t = 0$.

Substituting these expansions into $L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + \frac{t^N}{N!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \\
&\quad + i \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + i \frac{t^N}{N!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \\
&\quad - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + \frac{t_p^N}{N!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p) \right] \\
&\quad - i \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + \frac{t_p^N}{N!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \\
&\quad + i \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{t^N}{N!} \left(U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) + i V_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \right) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{N!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p) \\
&\quad - \frac{i}{N!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N V_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p).
\end{aligned}$$

Now observe that the expressions

$$P_U(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \quad \text{and} \quad P_V(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0)$$

are polynomials in t of degree at most $N - 1$. By the exactness property of Lagrangian interpolation, for any polynomial $Q(t)$ of degree $\leq N - 1$, we have

$$Q(t) = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)Q(t_p) \quad \text{for all } t.$$

Now, observe that

$$P_U(t_p) = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \quad \text{and} \quad P_V(t_p) = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0).$$

Therefore, we obtain the following

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \\ &= P_U(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)P_U(t_p) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

and similarly for the imaginary part:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \\ &= P_V(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)P_V(t_p) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the first two lines of the expansion vanish identically, and we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \frac{t^N}{N!} \left(U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) + iV_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{N!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p) \\ &\quad - \frac{i}{N!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N V_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p). \end{aligned}$$

Combining the real and imaginary parts, this simplifies to:

$$L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \frac{1}{N!} \left[t^N X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t_p) \right]. \quad (5.38)$$

If we now employ the integral form of the remainder term in Taylor's theorem, we have

$$X_{\eta\xi}(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + i \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \int_0^t (t-r)^{N-1} \left[U_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) + iV_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) \right] dr. \quad (5.39)$$

Recall that

$$L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = X_{\eta\xi}(t) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) \quad (5.40)$$

Substituting (5.39) back into (5.40), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + i \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{t^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \int_0^t (t-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr \\
&\quad - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \left[\sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} U_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) + i \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{t_p^j}{j!} V_{\eta\xi}^{(j)}(0) \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_0^{t_p} (t_p-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr
\end{aligned}$$

By the exactness theorem of Lagrangian interpolation formula for polynomials of degree less than or equal to $N-1$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \int_0^t (t-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_0^{t_p} (t_p-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr.
\end{aligned} \tag{5.41}$$

Letting $r = ts$, with $r \in [0, t]$ and $dr = t ds$, we note that when $r = 0$, $s = 0$, and when $r = t$, $s = 1$. Thus $0 < s < 1$. This substitution yields

$$\begin{aligned}
L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \frac{t^N}{(N-1)!} \int_0^1 (1-s)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(ts) ds \\
&\quad - \frac{t^N}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_0^1 (1-s)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(t_p s) ds.
\end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \int_0^1 (1-s)^{N-1} \left[t^N X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(ts) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(t_p s) \right] ds,$$

Now, by (5.38), we get

$$N!L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \left[t^N X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(ts) - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(t_p s) \right], \quad (5.42)$$

where $0 < s = \theta < 1$.

From (5.41), splitting the second integral into appropriate subintervals $[0, t_p]$ and $[t, t_p]$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \int_0^t (t-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_0^t (t_p-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_t^{t_p} (t_p-r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr. \end{aligned} \quad (5.43)$$

At this stage, we observe that the first two integrals are both taken over the same interval $[0, t]$. To analyze them, recall that the Lagrange basis polynomials $L_p(t)$ satisfy the interpolation or **exactness property**, which states that for any polynomial $Q(t)$ of degree not exceeding $N-1$,

$$Q(t) = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) Q(t_p).$$

This means that the interpolation reproduces all polynomials of degree less than or equal to $N-1$ exactly.

Now, in our expression, for each fixed r , the quantity $(t-r)^{N-1}$ is a polynomial in t

of degree $N - 1$. Therefore, by the property above,

$$(t - r)^{N-1} = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)(t_p - r)^{N-1}.$$

Substituting this equality into the first integral gives

$$\int_0^t (t - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr = \int_0^t \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t)(t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr.$$

Since $L_p(t)$ does not depend on r , we can take it outside the integral to obtain

$$\int_0^t (t - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_0^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr.$$

Now substituting this result back into the expression for $L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)$ in (5.43), we find that the first two terms cancel exactly, leaving only the third term:

$$\begin{aligned} L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= -\frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_t^{t_p} (t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr \\ &= \frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \int_{t_p}^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr. \end{aligned} \tag{5.44}$$

To analyze (5.44), consider the integral for each fixed p :

$$\int_{t_p}^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr.$$

By the Mean Value Theorem for Integrals, there exists $\theta_p \in [\min(t_p, t), \max(t_p, t)]$

such that

$$\int_{t_p}^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr = X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta_p) \int_{t_p}^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} dr.$$

Now, evaluating the polynomial integral. Let $u = t_p - r$, so that $du = -dr$. When $r = t_p$, $u = 0$; when $r = t$, $u = t_p - t$. Then

$$\int_{t_p}^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} dr = - \int_0^{t_p-t} u^{N-1} du = - \left[\frac{u^N}{N} \right]_0^{t_p-t} = - \frac{(t_p - t)^N}{N}.$$

Substituting back, we obtain for each p :

$$\int_{t_p}^t (t_p - r)^{N-1} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(r) dr = - \frac{(t_p - t)^N}{N} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta_p).$$

By the continuity of the N -th derivative $X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}$ and since the nodes t_p are sufficiently clustered, we may approximate $\theta_p \approx \theta t$ for some $\theta \in (0, 1)$ common to all p . Then

$$X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta_p) \approx X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \quad \text{for all } p.$$

Substituting into the original expression and simplifying the constants:

$$\frac{1}{(N-1)!} \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) \left[- \frac{(t_p - t)^N}{N} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \right] = - \frac{1}{N!} X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(\theta t) \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) (t_p - t)^N,$$

Therefore,

$$|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| \leq \frac{1}{N!} \max_{[t_0, T]} \left[\left| X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(t) \right| \cdot \left| t^N - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N \right| \right]$$

Consequently, $|L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$, for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, and

$$L(N, X(t_k))(\eta, \xi) = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Remark 3

(i) Upon application of equation (5.23) at each of the N nodes to problem (1.3), the following system of difference equations is obtained:

$$\sum_{p=1}^N a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi}(t_p) = P(t_m, X(t_m))(\eta, \xi), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (5.45)$$

The initial condition yields the quadrature equation:

$$X_{\eta\xi}(t_0) = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t_0) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p). \quad (5.46)$$

Putting $Z_{\eta,\xi,m} = P(t_m, X(t_m))(\eta, \xi)$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, N$, equations (5.45) and (5.46) lead to a system of $N + 1$ equations in N unknown approximate nodal values $X_{\eta,\xi,p}$, $p = 1, 2, \dots, N$, which are to be determined. In matrix form, this system becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{11}^{(1)} & a_{12}^{(1)} & \cdots & a_{1N}^{(1)} \\ a_{21}^{(1)} & a_{22}^{(1)} & \cdots & a_{2N}^{(1)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{N1}^{(1)} & a_{N2}^{(1)} & \cdots & a_{NN}^{(1)} \\ L_1(t_0) & L_2(t_0) & \cdots & L_N(t_0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{\eta,\xi,1} \\ X_{\eta,\xi,2} \\ \vdots \\ X_{\eta,\xi,N} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{\eta,\xi,1} \\ Z_{\eta,\xi,2} \\ \vdots \\ Z_{\eta,\xi,N} \\ X_{\eta,\xi,0} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5.47)$$

Considering the matrix coefficients in the form:

$$a_{ii}^{(1)} = \sum_{\substack{p=1 \\ p \neq i}}^N \frac{1}{t_i - t_p}$$

and

$$a_{ij}^{(1)} = \frac{P_N(t_i)}{(t_i - t_j)P'_N(t_j)}, \quad i \neq j$$

it has been shown that the rank of the $N \times N$ matrix $[a_{ij}^{(1)}]$ is exactly $N - 1$. The matrix is singular. Hence equation (5.46) is chosen together with any $N - 1$ equations of (5.45). The remaining N th equation of (5.45) is regarded as superfluous. Since the remaining equation must also be satisfied by the computed solutions, the measure of accuracy of the numerical result is given by the residual

$$R_{r,\eta,\xi} = \sum_{p=1}^N a_{rp}^{(1)} X_{\eta,\xi,p} - P(t_r, X(t_r))(\eta, \xi) \quad (5.48)$$

at the superfluous node $t = t_r$.

The superfluous error equation (5.48) is a practical method of estimating the accuracy of the numerical solution given by the Lagrangian quadrature method.

(ii) By Definition 9, the global error $\|e_t\|_{\eta\xi}$ satisfies

$$\|e_t\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{p=1}^N |L_p(t)| \|e_p\|_{\eta\xi} + |L(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)| + |R(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)|. \quad (5.49)$$

If we now put $e_{\eta\xi} = \max\{\|e_p\|_{\eta\xi}, p = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$, then by inequality (5.32):

$$\|e_t\|_{\eta\xi} \leq e_{\eta\xi} \sum_{p=1}^N |L_p(t)| + \frac{1}{N!} \max_{[t_0, T]} [|X_{\eta\xi}^{(N)}(t)|] \left| t^N - \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t) t_p^N \right| + \|R(N, X(t))(\eta, \xi)\|. \quad (5.50)$$

By continuity of the Lagrangian interpolant, the first term above is bounded. The global error increases due to truncation error, as well as due to round-off error. The

truncation error decreases as N increases. The actual behavior of the round-off error will be determined in the investigation of numerical stability of the quadrature method.

Remark 4 (Application to Quantum Stochastic Differential Equation)

Let problem (1.3) be given:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad \eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}, \quad t \in [t_0, T]. \quad (5.51)$$

The application of the Lagrangian quadrature method to quantum stochastic differential equations follows the same procedure outlined in Remark 5.6, with the inner product form $\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ replacing $X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ throughout the analysis. The resulting numerical scheme and error analysis remain valid for this important class of quantum evolution equations.

5.7 Linear Multistep Methods for Quantum Stochastic Differential Equations

In this section, we introduce the class of linear multistep methods as numerical schemes for solving quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs) of the form (1.3). The development here provides a foundation for analyzing the accuracy and error bounds of such methods. To ensure generality, we assume that for arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, the mapping

$$(t, x) \longmapsto P(t, x)(\eta, \xi)$$

is continuous for all $(t, x) \in [t_0, T] \times \mathcal{A}$, and that the exact solution $X(t)$ of the QSDE satisfies $X_{\eta, \xi}(\cdot) \in C^q[t_0, T]$ for some integer $q \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

For numerical discretization, we consider a uniform partition $\{t_n\} \subset I$ of time interval $[t_0, T]$ defined by

$$t_n = t_0 + nh, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

where $h > 0$ denotes the constant step size. The use of a uniform step size h simplifies the analysis and implementation of multistep methods. Let $X(t)$ be the exact solution of the continuous problem (1.3) and let $\{X_n\}$ denote the corresponding discrete approximations that lie on the trajectory of $X(t)$ at the discretization points $\{t_n\}$ within the interval $[t_0, T]$. Our objective in this section is to establish a lower bound for the local discretization error of the scheme.

Definition 13. *A general linear multistep scheme for determining a sequence of approximations $\{X_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ to $\{X(t_n)\}_{n \geq 0}$ is defined by the relation*

$$\sum_{j=0}^k a_j \langle \eta, X_{n+j} \xi \rangle = h \sum_{j=0}^k b_j P(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j})(\eta, \xi), \quad (5.52)$$

where $a_j, b_j \in \mathbb{R}$ for $j = 0, 1, \dots, k$, and k is a nonnegative integer representing the number of steps. The coefficients a_j and b_j determine the specific type and properties of the multistep scheme.

Remark 5

- (i) Without loss of generality, we may assume that $a_k = 1$, and that a_0 and b_0 are not both zero.

- (ii) Although the constants a_j and b_j can, in principle, be complex, for simplicity we restrict our analysis to real coefficients. This restriction ensures that the multistep equation can be split conveniently into its real and imaginary components when necessary.
- (iii) By applying equation (3.2), the discrete multistep scheme (5.52) can be rewritten equivalently in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=0}^k a_j X_{n+j} = & b_0 \int_{t_n}^{t_{n+1}} [E(t_n, X_n) d\Lambda_\pi(s) + F(t_n, X_n) dA_f(s) \\
& + G(t_n, X_n) dA_g^+(s) + H(t_n, X_n) ds] \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{j} b_j \int_{t_n}^{t_{n+j}} [E(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j}) d\Lambda_\pi(s) \\
& + F(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j}) dA_f(s) + G(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j}) dA_g^+(s) \\
& + H(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j}) ds], \tag{5.53}
\end{aligned}$$

where the operators E, F, G, H correspond to the coefficients in the quantum stochastic differential equation (3.3).

This discrete formulation represents a generalization of multistep schemes for Itô equations (see Kloeden 1999) when expressed in the framework of weak convergence.

5.7.1 The Associated Linear Operator

Let the map $t \mapsto X_{\eta\xi}(t) := \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ be such that $X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ is of class $C^q(I)$ for any integer $q \geq 1$. Then, for the linear multistep method (5.52), we associate the linear

difference operator

$$L : \mathbb{R} \times \mathcal{A} \longrightarrow \text{sesq}(\mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}) \quad (5.54)$$

defined by

$$L(h, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \sum_{j=0}^k \left[a_j X_{\eta\xi}(t + jh) - hb_j X'_{\eta\xi}(t + jh) \right]. \quad (5.55)$$

Expanding $X_{\eta\xi}(t + jh)$ and $X'_{\eta\xi}(t + jh)$ in Taylor series around t , we obtain

$$L(h, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = C_0 X_{\eta\xi}(t) + C_1 h X'_{\eta\xi}(t) + C_2 h^2 X''_{\eta\xi}(t) + \cdots + C_q h^q X_{\eta\xi}^{(q)}(t) + \cdots, \quad (5.56)$$

where C_q are constants that depend on the coefficients a_j and b_j .

The constants C_q are given by:

$$C_0 = \sum_{j=0}^k a_j, \quad C_1 = \sum_{j=0}^k (ja_j - b_j), \quad C_q = \frac{1}{q!} \sum_{j=0}^k (j^q a_j - qj^{q-1} b_j) \text{ for } q \geq 2. \quad (5.57)$$

The result follows by expanding $X_{\eta\xi}(t + jh)$ and $X'_{\eta\xi}(t + jh)$ in Taylor series about t :

$$\begin{aligned} X_{\eta\xi}(t + jh) &= \sum_{q=0}^{\infty} \frac{(jh)^q}{q!} X_{\eta\xi}^{(q)}(t), \\ X'_{\eta\xi}(t + jh) &= \sum_{q=0}^{\infty} \frac{(jh)^q}{q!} X_{\eta\xi}^{(q+1)}(t), \end{aligned}$$

substituting into the definition of L , and collecting like powers of h .

5.7.2 Order of the Multistep Method

The difference operator $L(h, X(t))$ and the corresponding multistep scheme are said to be of order ρ if

$$C_0 = C_1 = C_2 = \cdots = C_\rho = 0, \quad C_{\rho+1} \neq 0. \quad (5.58)$$

As in the deterministic case, the coefficients C_q in equation (5.56) are expressible in terms of the scheme coefficients a_j and b_j .

The **local discretization error** at t_{n+k} is defined as the real quantity

$$|L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)|. \quad (5.59)$$

This error is termed *local* because it measures how well the multistep scheme approximates the exact solution over a single step under the assumption

$$\langle \eta, X_{n+j}\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1. \quad (5.60)$$

Proposition 3 (Ayoola 2000)

Suppose that the multistep scheme defined by equation (5.52) is of order ρ , and that the equality

$$\langle \eta, X_{n+j}\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1,$$

holds for all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}}$. Then, the local discretization error satisfies

$$[1 - h|b_k||K'_{\eta\xi}(t_{n+k})|]|X(t_{n+k}) - X_{n+k}|_{\eta\xi} \leq |L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)|. \quad (5.61)$$

Furthermore, if the exact solution $X(t)$ is of class $C^{(\rho+1)}[t_0, T]$, then

$$[1 - h|b_k|K'_{\eta\xi}(t_{n+k})] \|X(t_{n+k}) - X_{n+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq |C_{\rho+1}h^{\rho+1}X_{\eta\xi}^{(\rho+1)}(t_n)| + |O(h^{\rho+2})(\eta, \xi)|. \quad (5.62)$$

Proof

The proof follows similar arguments to those in Lambert 1991, Section 2.7, utilizing equations (5.60) and (5.55), together with the fact that the mapping P is Lipschitz continuous.

Remark 6

If we define the coefficient

$$C_{\eta\xi, n+k} = 1 - h|b_k| |K'_{\eta\xi}(t_{n+k})|,$$

and substitute it into (5.60) and (5.55), then the inequalities become

$$C_{\eta\xi, n+k} \|X(t_{n+k}) - X_{n+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq |L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)| \quad (5.63)$$

where the constant $C_{\eta\xi, n+k}$ takes the value 1 for explicit methods (when $b_k = 0$) and differs from 1 for implicit methods (when $b_k \neq 0$), provided that $K_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+k}) \neq 0$. It is important to note that the bounds in equations (5.61) and (5.62) are valid only under the localizing assumption (5.60).

When the approximation errors at previous steps are non-zero, that is, when

$$\|X(t_{n+j}) - X_{n+j}\|_{n\xi} \neq 0$$

for $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ and $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$, the quantity

$$\|X(t_{n+k}) - X_{n+k}\|_{n\xi} = \|e_{n+k}\|_{n\xi}$$

represents the global absolute error incurred at each application of the numerical method.

5.8 Convergence Analysis of Multistep Schemes

The concepts of convergence and consistency for the linear multistep method (5.52) applied to a stochastic process $X(t)$ are defined as follows. For arbitrary $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$:

$$\lim_{\substack{h \rightarrow 0 \\ n \rightarrow \infty \\ nh = t - t_0}} \|X_n - X(t)\|_{n\xi} = 0 \tag{5.64}$$

for all $t \in [t_0, T]$, and

$$\lim_{\substack{h \rightarrow 0 \\ n \rightarrow \infty}} \|X_j - X_0\|_{n\xi} = 0$$

for all $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$.

The method (5.52) is considered consistent if it achieves an order of accuracy $\rho \geq 1$. From the first two equations in (5.58), it follows that the method is consistent if and

only if the following conditions are satisfied:

$$\sum_{j=0}^k a_j = 0, \quad \sum_{j=0}^k j a_j = \sum_{j=0}^k b_j \quad (5.65)$$

Theorem 10 (Ayoola 2000)

If the linear multistep method (5.52) is both consistent and convergent to a stochastic process $X : I \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$, then X satisfies the quantum stochastic differential equation (1.3).

Proof

The proof follows by adapting standard arguments from the literature. Given that

$$\lim_{\substack{h \rightarrow 0 \\ n \rightarrow \infty \\ nh = t - t_0}} \|X_n - X(t)\|_{\eta\xi} = 0$$

and since k remains fixed, we deduce that

$$X_{n+j} \longrightarrow X(t), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, k \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty, \quad h \rightarrow 0$$

which implies

$$\lim_{\substack{h \rightarrow 0 \\ n \rightarrow \infty}} |\langle \eta, (X_{n+j} - X(t))\xi \rangle| = 0$$

or equivalently,

$$\lim_{\substack{h \rightarrow 0 \\ n \rightarrow \infty}} \langle \eta, X_{n+j}\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle \quad (5.66)$$

By expressing the inner products in terms of their real and imaginary components:

$$\langle \eta, X_n \xi \rangle = U_{\eta\xi, n} + iV_{\eta\xi, n}$$

and

$$\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = U_{\eta\xi}(t) + iV_{\eta\xi}(t)$$

the proof is established by extending the convergence arguments to the sequences $\{U_{\eta\xi,n}\}$ and $\{V_{\eta\xi,n}\}$ of real numbers and their corresponding real-valued functions $t \rightarrow U_{\eta\xi}(t)$ and $t \rightarrow V_{\eta\xi}(t)$.

Remark 7

- (a) Various stability concepts for the multistep method (5.52) can be introduced, analogous to those used in multistep schemes for deterministic initial value problems. These aspects will be explored in a separate treatment.
- (b) Our subsequent result establishes a bound for the discretization error $|L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)|$, as defined in equation (5.56), under appropriate smoothness conditions on $X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ and consistency requirements of the linear multistep method (5.52). To facilitate this analysis, we introduce the following functions and notations, assuming the multistep method (5.52) has order ρ and step number $k \geq 1$. For $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k$ and $s \in [0, k]$:

- (i) The truncated power function:

$$(j - s)_+ = \begin{cases} j - s & \text{if } j - s \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } j - s < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5.67)$$

(ii) The influence function:

$$G(s) = \sum_{j=0}^k [a_j(j-s)_+^\rho - \rho b_j(j-s)_+^{\rho-1}] \quad (5.68)$$

(iii) If the exact solution X of problem (1.3) satisfies that the map $t \rightarrow \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle := X_{\eta\xi}(t)$ belongs to $C^{p+1}[t_0, T]$ for all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$, then we define

$$Y_{\eta\xi} = \max_{[t_0, T]} |X_{\eta\xi}^{(\rho+1)}(t)|$$

(iv) The error constant:

$$G = \frac{1}{\rho!} \int_0^k |G(s)| ds$$

where $G(s)$ is given by equation (5.68). The function $G(s)$ represents the influence function of method (5.52) and depends on the coefficients a_j, b_j for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Theorem 11 (Ayoola 2000)

Under the following assumptions:

- (i) The multistep scheme (5.52) is consistent and has order ρ ;
- (ii) The exact solution X of problem (1.3) is such that the map $t \rightarrow \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ belongs to $C^{p+1}[t_0, T]$ for all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$; the discretization error $|L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)|$ satisfies the bound

$$|L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)| \leq h^{p+1} G Y_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.69)$$

Proof

Let $Y(t) = \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$. By assumption, $Y \in C^{\rho+1}[t_0, T]$. The local truncation error is given by

$$L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi) = \sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j Y(t_n + jh) - h \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j Y'(t_n + jh).$$

Since Y is $C^{\rho+1}$, we employ Taylor expansions about t_n with integral remainders:

$$Y(t_n + jh) = \sum_{m=0}^{\rho} \frac{(jh)^m}{m!} Y^{(m)}(t_n) + \frac{1}{\rho!} \int_{t_n}^{t_n+jh} (t_n + jh - s)^{\rho} Y^{(\rho+1)}(s) ds,$$

$$Y'(t_n + jh) = \sum_{m=0}^{\rho-1} \frac{(jh)^m}{m!} Y^{(m+1)}(t_n) + \frac{1}{(\rho-1)!} \int_{t_n}^{t_n+jh} (t_n + jh - s)^{\rho-1} Y^{(\rho+1)}(s) ds.$$

Substituting into the local error expression yields

$$L = \sum_{m=0}^{\rho} \frac{Y^{(m)}(t_n)}{m!} \sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j (jh)^m - h \sum_{m=0}^{\rho-1} \frac{Y^{(m+1)}(t_n)}{m!} \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j (jh)^m + E_R,$$

where the remainder term is

$$E_R = \sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j R_j^{(Y)} - h \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j R_j^{(Y')}$$

with

$$R_j^{(Y)} = \frac{1}{\rho!} \int_{t_n}^{t_n+jh} (t_n + jh - s)^{\rho} Y^{(\rho+1)}(s) ds, \quad R_j^{(Y')} = \frac{1}{(\rho-1)!} \int_{t_n}^{t_n+jh} (t_n + jh - s)^{\rho-1} Y^{(\rho+1)}(s) ds.$$

The order conditions for a method of order ρ imply that the coefficients of $Y^{(m)}(t_n)$ vanish for $m = 0, \dots, \rho$. Therefore, $L = E_R$.

Let $M_{\eta\xi} = \max_{s \in [t_0, T]} |Y^{(\rho+1)}(s)|$. Then

$$|R_j^{(Y)}| \leq \frac{M_{\eta\xi}}{\rho!} \int_{t_n}^{t_n+jh} (t_n + jh - s)^\rho ds = \frac{M_{\eta\xi} j^{\rho+1} h^{\rho+1}}{\rho! (\rho + 1)},$$

$$|R_j^{(Y')}| \leq \frac{M_{\eta\xi}}{(\rho - 1)!} \int_{t_n}^{t_n+jh} (t_n + jh - s)^{\rho-1} ds = \frac{M_{\eta\xi} j^\rho h^\rho}{\rho!}.$$

Thus,

$$|L| \leq \sum_{j=0}^k |\alpha_j| |R_j^{(Y)}| + h \sum_{j=0}^k |\beta_j| |R_j^{(Y')}| \leq \frac{M_{\eta\xi} h^{\rho+1}}{\rho!} \left[\sum_{j=0}^k |\alpha_j| \frac{j^{\rho+1}}{\rho + 1} + \sum_{j=0}^k |\beta_j| j^\rho \right].$$

Taking $G = \frac{1}{\rho!} \left[\sum_{j=0}^k |\alpha_j| \frac{j^{\rho+1}}{\rho+1} + \sum_{j=0}^k |\beta_j| j^\rho \right]$ and $Y_{\eta\xi} = M_{\eta\xi}$, we have

$$|L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)| \leq h^{\rho+1} G Y_{\eta\xi}$$

This completes the proof.

5.9 CONVERGENCE OF MULTISTEP SCHEMES OF CLASS A

In this section, we shall prove convergence of multistep schemes of class A for solving problem (1.3). In so doing, we prove existence of bounds for global absolute errors. We note that it is the global absolute error which convergence of the scheme demands should tend to zero in the limit.

5.9.1 Notation

Let $a_j, b_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, k$ be constants appearing in equation (5.52) and $K_{\eta\xi}^p(t)$ the continuous Lipschitz functions for P in problem (1.3), then we adopt the following notations.

(i)

$$K_{\eta\xi,n} = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} K_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+j}) |b_j| \quad (5.70)$$

(ii)

$$K_{\eta\xi} = \max_{n=0,1,2,\dots,N-k} \{K_{\eta\xi,n}\} \quad (5.71)$$

where N is the total partition points of $[t_0, T]$.

(iii)

$$\partial_{\eta\xi} = \max_{\mu=0,1,2,\dots,k-1} \{\|e_\mu\|_{\eta\xi}\}, \quad \text{where } e_n = X(t_n) - X_n. \quad (5.72)$$

(iv)

$$G = \frac{1}{\rho!} \int_0^k |G(s)| ds \quad (5.73)$$

(v)

$$Y_{\eta\xi} = \max_{[t_0, T]} |X_{\eta\xi}^{(p+1)}(t)| \quad (5.74)$$

Theorem 12 (Ayoola 2000)

Assume that the following conditions hold

- (i) The multistep method (5.52) is consistent, explicit, has order ρ , of class A and has step number $k \geq 1$.

- (ii) The exact solution $X(t)$ of problem (1.3) is such that the map, $t \rightarrow \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle$ is of class $C^{p+1}[t_0, T]$ for all $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$.

Then the global absolute error satisfies

$$\|X(t_n) - X_n\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \partial_{\eta\xi} e^{(T-t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} + \frac{h^p GY_{\eta\xi}}{K_{\eta\xi}} [e^{(T-t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} - 1] \quad (5.75)$$

Proof

The exact solution $X(t)$ of problem (1.3) satisfies

$$\sum_{j=0}^k a_j \langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle - h \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} b_j \langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle' = L(h, X(t_n))(\eta\xi) \quad (5.76)$$

or

$$\langle \eta, X(t_{n+k})\xi \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} [-a_j \langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle + hb_j P(t_{n+j}, X(t_{n+j}))(\eta, \xi)] + L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi) \quad (5.77)$$

Also, the sequence $\{X_n\}$ generated by equation (5.52) satisfies

$$\langle \eta, X_{n+k}\xi \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} [a_j \langle \eta, X_{n+j}\xi \rangle + hb_j P(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j})(\eta, \xi)] \quad (5.78)$$

Subtracting equation (5.78) from (5.77) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta, X(t_{n+k})\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{n+k}\xi \rangle &= \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \{-a_j (\langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{n+j}\xi \rangle) \\ &\quad + hb_j [P(t_{n+j}, X(t_{n+j}))(\eta, \xi) - P(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j})(\eta, \xi)]\} + L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
|\langle \eta, X(t_{n+k})\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{n+k}\xi \rangle| &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} |-a_j| |\langle \eta, X(t_{n+j})\xi \rangle - \langle \eta, X_{n+j}\xi \rangle| \\
&\quad + h|b_j| | [P(t_{n+j}, X(t_{n+j}))(\eta, \xi) - P(t_{n+j}, X_{n+j})(\eta, \xi)] | \\
&\quad + |L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)|
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the Lipschitz condition for the map P , we have

$$\|e_{n+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} |-a_j| \|e_{n+j}\|_{\eta\xi} + h|b_j| K_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+j}) \|X(t_{n+j}) - X_{n+j}\|_{\eta\xi} + |L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)| \quad (5.79)$$

Since the method is of class A, we have

$$|-a_j| = -a_j, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \quad (5.80)$$

Using (5.74) we have

$$|L(h, X(t_n))(\eta, \xi)| \leq h^{p+1} G Y_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.81)$$

From (5.79) we have

$$\|e_{n+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-a_j + hK_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+j})|b_j|) \|e_{n+j}\|_{\eta\xi} + h^{p+1} G Y_{\eta\xi}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-k \quad (5.82)$$

We now introduce some simplifying notations. Let

$$P_{j,n,\eta,\xi} = -a_j + hK_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+j})|b_j| \quad (5.83)$$

$$P_{n,\eta\xi} = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,n,\eta\xi}, \quad q_{\eta\xi} = h^{p+1}GY_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.84)$$

Now since $a_k = 1$ and $\sum_{j=0}^k a_j = 0$ then

$$-\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} a_j = 1 \quad (5.85)$$

$$\therefore P_{n,\eta\xi} = -\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} a_j + h \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} K_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+j})|b_j| = 1 + hK_{\eta\xi,n} \quad (5.86)$$

where

$$K_{\eta\xi,n} = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} K_{\eta\xi}^p(t_{n+j})|b_j| \quad (5.87)$$

Let $\partial_{\eta\xi}(h)$ be the maximum error in the starting values, that is

$$\partial_{\eta\xi}(h) = \max_{\mu=0,1,2,\dots,k-1} \|e_\mu\|_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.88)$$

We deduce from (5.83), (5.84), (5.86), (5.87) and (5.88) that

$$P_{j,n,\eta\xi} \geq 0, \quad P_{n,\eta\xi} \geq 1, \quad q_{\eta\xi} \geq 0, \quad \partial_{\eta\xi}(h) \geq 0 \quad (5.89)$$

The inequality (5.82) may now be written

$$\|e_{n+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,n,\eta\xi} \|e_{n+j}\|_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - k \quad (5.90)$$

Setting $n = 0$ in (5.90) and in view of (5.88) and (5.89) we get

$$\|e_k\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,0,\eta\xi} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} = P_{0,\eta\xi} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.91)$$

where

$$P_{\eta\xi} = \max_{n=0,1,2,\dots,N-k} P_{n,\eta\xi} \quad (5.92)$$

Setting $n = 1$ in (5.90) we have

$$\|e_{k+1}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,1,\eta\xi} \|e_{j+1}\|_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.93)$$

Now by (5.88)

$$\|e_{j+1}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \partial_{\eta\xi}, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-2 \quad (5.94)$$

and by (5.91)

$$\|e_k\|_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.95)$$

However by (5.89)

$$P_{\eta\xi} = \max_{n=0,1,\dots,N-k} P_{n,\eta\xi} \geq 1 \quad (5.96)$$

so that

$$\partial_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.97)$$

Combining (5.94),(5.95) and (5.97), we write

$$\|e_{j+1}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi}, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \quad (5.98)$$

Substituting this inequality in (5.93) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\|e_{k+1}\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,1,\eta\xi}(P_{\eta\xi}\partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi}) + q_{\eta\xi} \\
&= P_{1,\eta\xi}(P_{\eta\xi}\partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi}) + q_{\eta\xi} \\
&\leq P_{\eta\xi}(P_{\eta\xi}\partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi}) + q_{\eta\xi} \\
&= P_{\eta\xi}^2\partial_{\eta\xi} + (P_{\eta\xi} + 1)q_{\eta\xi}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.98.1}$$

We now apply mathematical induction by making the induction hypothesis that

$$\|e_{l+k}\|_{\eta\xi} < P_{\eta\xi}^{l+1}\partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^l P_{\eta\xi}^s, \quad l = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1 \tag{5.99}$$

Expression (5.95) and (5.98.1) verify that (5.99) holds for $m = 1, 2$. By (5.90),

$$\|e_{m+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,m,\eta\xi}\|e_{m+j}\|_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \tag{5.100}$$

By induction hypothesis (5.99), we have

$$\|e_{m+j}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi}^{m-k+j+1}\partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{m-k+j} P_{\eta\xi}^s, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, k-1 \tag{5.101}$$

$$\leq P_{\eta\xi}^m\partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} P_{\eta\xi}^s \tag{5.102}$$

(5.102) holds since each of the terms in the right hand side of (5.101) has its maximum

when $j = k - 1$ in view of (5.89). Thus from (5.100), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|e_{m+k}\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,m,\eta\xi} (P_{\eta\xi}^m \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} P_{\eta\xi}^s) + q_{\eta\xi} \\ &\leq P_{\eta\xi} (P_{\eta\xi}^m \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} P_{\eta\xi}^s) + q_{\eta\xi} \end{aligned}$$

(since $\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_{j,m,\eta\xi} = P_{m,\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi}$)

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \|e_{m+k}\|_{\eta\xi} &\leq P_{\eta\xi}^{m+1} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} P_{\eta\xi}^{s+1} + q_{\eta\xi} \\ &= P_{\eta\xi}^{m+1} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} (1 + \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} P_{\eta\xi}^{s+1}) \\ &= P_{\eta\xi}^{m+1} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^m P_{\eta\xi}^s \end{aligned}$$

Thus (5.99) holds when $l = m$ and so holds for all m , and the induction proof is complete. Therefore,

$$\|e_{n+k}\|_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi}^{n+1} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^n P_{\eta\xi}^s, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5.103)$$

$$\leq P_{\eta\xi}^{n+k} \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{m+k-1} P_{\eta\xi}^s, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5.104)$$

since $k \geq 1$. Equivalently, we may write

$$\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi}^n \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} P_{\eta\xi}^s = P_{\eta\xi}^n \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \left(\frac{P_{\eta\xi}^n - 1}{P_{\eta\xi} - 1} \right), \quad n = k, k+1, \dots, N-k \quad (5.105)$$

The same bounds hold when $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$ since for such n ,

$$\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \partial_{\eta\xi} \leq P_{\eta\xi}^n \partial_{\eta\xi} + q_{\eta\xi} \frac{P_{\eta\xi}^n - 1}{P_{\eta\xi} - 1}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1 \quad (5.106)$$

in view of (5.89). Thus combining (5.105) and (5.106) and using (5.83) - (5.89) we have the following bound for the global discretization error $\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi}$

$$\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \partial_{\eta\xi} (1 + hK_{\eta\xi})^n + \frac{h^\rho GY_{\eta\xi}}{K_{\eta,\xi}} [(1 + hK_{\eta\xi})^n - 1], \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5.107)$$

where

$$P_{\eta\xi} = 1 + hK_{\eta\xi} \quad (5.108)$$

Since

$$1 + hK_{\eta\xi} \leq e^{hK_{\eta\xi}} \quad (5.109)$$

then

$$(1 + hK_{\eta\xi})^n \leq e^{nhK_{\eta\xi}} = e^{(t_n - t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} \leq e^{(T - t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} \quad (5.110)$$

Substituting in (5.107), we have

$$\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi} \leq \partial_{\eta\xi} e^{(T - t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} + \frac{h^\rho GY_{\eta\xi}}{K_{\eta\xi}} |e^{(T - t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} - 1| \quad (5.111)$$

This completes the proof.

Remark 8

- (i) The second term in the right hand side of the last inequality is of the form $O(h^\rho)(\eta, \xi)$ as $h \rightarrow 0$.

(ii) Using the inequality $e^z - 1 < ze^z$ for any real z , we have

$$e^{(T-t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} - 1 < (T - t_0)K_{\eta\xi}e^{(T-t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} \quad (5.112)$$

Substituting in inequality (5.76), we get

$$\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi} < [\partial_{\eta\xi} + (T - t_0)h^\rho GY_{\eta\xi}]e^{(T-t_0)K_{\eta\xi}} \quad (5.113)$$

It follows from inequality (5.76) and (5.113) that if $\rho \geq 1$, $\partial_{\eta\xi}(h) \rightarrow 0$ as $h \rightarrow 0$, then $\|e_n\|_{\eta\xi} \rightarrow 0$. As $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is τ_w complete and in view of Theorem (10), $X_n \rightarrow X(t)$ as $\partial_{\eta\xi} \rightarrow 0$, $h \rightarrow 0$, $n \rightarrow \infty$, $nh = t - t_0$.

Chapter 6

Quantum Formulation of Stochastic Differential Equations of Ito Types and Some Numerical Examples

In this section, following the approach of reference (Hudson and Parasarathy 1984), we take $\gamma = \mathcal{R} = \mathbb{C}$ and write

$$A(t) = A_f(t), \quad \Lambda_g^\dagger(t) = A^\dagger(t), \quad f(t) = g(t) \equiv 1 \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}_+.$$

As a consequence, the Fock space becomes

$$\mathcal{R} \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)) \equiv \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)).$$

It is well known that the creation and annihilation operators $A^\dagger(t)$ and $A(t)$ satisfy the commutation relations

$$[A(s), A(t)] = [A^\dagger(s), A^\dagger(t)] = 0,$$

$$[A(s), A^\dagger(t)] = \min\{s, t\} \cdot \mathbf{1},$$

on the dense subspace \mathbb{E} of $\Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+))$ spanned by the exponential vectors. Moreover, the self-adjoint operator-valued adapted process Q defined by

$$Q(t) = A(t) + A^\dagger(t)$$

is a quantum Brownian motion.

The Fock space $\Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+))$ can be realized as $L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, W)$, where (Ω, \mathcal{F}, W) is the classical Wiener space (see references: Boukas 2006, Meyer 1993, Parthasarathy 1992, Parthasarathy 1985). Under this realization, the Fock vacuum $e(0)$ corresponds to the constant function 1 on the Wiener space of continuous trajectories, and $Q(t)$ becomes the operator of multiplication by the canonical Brownian motion. For further details, we refer to (Boukas 2006, Parthasarathy 1992, Parthasarathy 1985).

In this picture, each random variable X is identified with the multiplication operator by X , so that

$$(Q(t)F)(\omega) = X(t)(\omega) F(\omega) = \omega(t) F(\omega), \quad F \in L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, W),$$

which implies

$$Q(t) = A(t) + A^\dagger(t) = \omega(t), \quad (6.1)$$

where $\omega(t)$ denotes the evaluation of the Brownian path ω at time t .

As an element of $L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, W)$, the exponential vector is expressed as

$$e(\alpha)(\omega) = \exp \left(\int_0^\infty \alpha(s) d\omega(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \alpha^2(s) ds \right), \quad (6.2)$$

where $\int_0^\infty \alpha(s) d\omega(s)$ denotes the Wiener integral and α is a purely imaginary function in $L^2_{\mathbb{C}}(\mathbb{R}_+)$.

We now present a result concerning the quantum analogue of the classical Itô integral for Brownian motion. In what follows, \mathbb{E} denotes the expectation functional.

Theorem 13 (Ayoola 2000)

Let F and H be nonanticipating Brownian functionals and \mathbb{E} be an expected value function such that

$$\int_0^t \mathbb{E}[F(s, \cdot)^2] ds < \infty \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^t \mathbb{E}[H(s, \cdot)^2] ds < \infty.$$

Then, as multiplication operator valued processes,

$$F = (F(t, \cdot); t \geq 0) \quad \text{and} \quad H = (H(t, \cdot) : t \geq 0)$$

belong to the space $L^2_{\text{loc}}(\tilde{A})$.

Proof

The proof follows directly from Proposition 5.1 in (Hudson and Parthasarathy 1984). Full details are available in (Ayoola 1998).

Remark 9

(i) Define

$$m(t, w) = \int_0^t F(s, w)dw(s) + \int_0^t H(s, w)ds,$$

where the first term is the standard Itô–Doob mean square integral of F . Then, by Theorem 13 and equation (6.1), we can express $m(t, \cdot)$ as

$$m(t, \cdot) = \int_0^t (F(s, \cdot)dA(s) + F(s, \cdot)dA^+(s) + H(s, \cdot)ds). \quad (6.3)$$

(ii) Based on equation (6.3), the classical Itô stochastic differential equation (1) in integral form has the following quantum analogue:

$$X(t, \cdot) = X_0(\cdot) + \int_{t_0}^t (F(s, X(s, \cdot))dA(s) + F(s, X(s, \cdot))dA^+(s) + H(s, X(s, \cdot))ds). \quad (6.4)$$

(iii) For $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ with $\eta = e(\alpha)$, $\xi = e(\beta)$, where $\alpha, \beta : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ are bounded functions in $L^2_{\mathbb{C}}(\mathbb{R}_+)$ taking purely imaginary values, we use the functions $\mu_{\alpha\beta}, \gamma_{\beta}$,

and σ_α introduced in Chapter 3 to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\alpha\beta}(t) &= 0, \\ \gamma_\beta(t) &= \langle 1, \beta(t) \rangle_{\mathbb{C}} = \beta(t), \\ \sigma_\alpha(t) &= \langle \alpha(t), 1 \rangle_{\mathbb{C}} = \bar{\alpha}(t).\end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}\mu E(t, X)(\eta, \xi) &= 0, \\ \gamma F(t, X)(\eta, \xi) &= \langle \eta, \gamma_\beta(t)F(t, X)\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, \beta(t)F(t, X)\xi \rangle_{\Gamma(L_{\mathbb{C}}^2(\mathbb{R}_+)) \cong L^2(\Omega, W)} \\ &= \mathbb{E} [\beta(t)F(t, X)e(\alpha)e(\beta)], \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\beta(t)F(t, X(t)) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s))dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s))ds \right\} \right], \\ \alpha F(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \langle \eta, \sigma_\alpha(t)F(t, X(t))\xi \rangle = \langle e(\alpha), \bar{\alpha}(t)F(t, X(t))e(\beta) \rangle \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\bar{\alpha}(t)F(t, X(t)) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s))dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s))ds \right\} \right] \\ H(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \langle \eta, H(t, X(t))\xi \rangle \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[H(t, X(t)) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s))dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s))ds \right\} \right].\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= \mu E(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) + \gamma F(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) + \sigma F(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) + H(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[\beta(t)F(t, X(t)) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s))dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s))ds \right\} \right] \\ &+ \mathbb{E} \left[\bar{\alpha}(t)F(t, X(t)) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s))dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s))ds \right\} \right]\end{aligned}$$

$$+\mathbb{E} \left[H(t, X(t)) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s)) dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s)) ds \right\} \right].$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle &= \langle e(\alpha), X(t)e(\beta) \rangle, \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[X(t, w) \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s)) dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s)) ds \right\} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Define

$$z(w) = \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s)) dw(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s)) ds \right\}. \quad (6.5)$$

Then, the equivalent form of equation (6.4) is given by

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{E} (X(t, w)z(w)) = \mathbb{E} [\beta(t)F(t, X(t))z(w)] + \mathbb{E} [\bar{\alpha}(t)F(t, X(t))z(w)] + \mathbb{E} [H(t, X(t))z(w)], \quad (6.6)$$

with initial condition

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t_0)z(w)) = \mathbb{E}(X_0z(w)), \quad \text{for almost all } t \in [t_0, T]. \quad (6.7)$$

6. Examples of quantum stochastic differential equations

We begin by presenting examples of the quantum stochastic integral equation (3.3) that fulfill the Lipschitz condition as defined in this work.

- (a) Consider the following quantum stochastic differential equation for $t \in [0, T]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
X(t) = I + \int_0^t & [(L(s)X(s) + \lambda \exp[pA(s) + qA^+(s) + rs]) d\Lambda(s) + U(s)X(s) dA(s) \\
& + V(s)X(s) dA^+(s) + (Z(s)X(s) + Q(s)) ds],
\end{aligned} \tag{6.8}$$

where the operators are denoted by

$$A(t) = A_f(t), \quad A^+(t) = A_f^+(t), \quad \Lambda_\pi(t) = \Lambda(t),$$

with the choices

$$f(t) \equiv g(t) \equiv \pi(t) \equiv 1, \quad \mathcal{R} = \gamma = \mathbb{C}.$$

Here, L, U, V, Z are continuous complex-valued functions defined on the interval $[0, T]$, $Q : [0, T] \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is an adapted process, and λ, p, q, r are complex constants.

From these definitions, it follows that

$$R \otimes \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+)) \equiv \Gamma(L_Y^2(\mathbb{R}_+))$$

and

$$\mathbb{D} \otimes \underline{\mathbb{E}} \equiv \mathbb{E}, \quad \mathcal{A} = L_W^+(\mathbb{E}, \Gamma(L_\gamma^2(\mathbb{R}_+))).$$

The coefficients of the equation are given by:

$$E(t, X(t)) = L(t)X(t) + \lambda \exp(pA(t) + qA^+(t) + rt),$$

$$F(t, X(t)) = U(t)X(t),$$

$$G(t, X(t)) = V(t)X(t),$$

$$H(t, X(t)) = Z(t)X(t) + Q(t), \quad \text{for } X(t) \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}.$$

These coefficient functionals are Lipschitz continuous, with the respective Lipschitz functions being:

$$K_{\eta\xi}^E(t) = |L(t)|, \quad K_{\eta\xi}^F(t) = |U(t)|, \quad K_{\eta\xi}^G(t) = |V(t)|, \quad K_{\eta\xi}^H(t) = |Z(t)|.$$

That is, for each functional $M \in \{E, F, G, H\}$, the following inequality holds for all $x, y \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$:

$$\|M(t, x) - M(t, y)\|_{\eta\xi} \leq K_{\eta\xi}^M(t) \|x - y\|_{\eta\xi},$$

and each M belongs to $L_{loc}^2([0, T] \times \tilde{\mathcal{A}})$ whenever $X \in L_{loc}^2(\tilde{\mathcal{A}})$.

In the special case where $\lambda = 0$ and $Q(t) \equiv 0$, the well-established results guarantee the existence and uniqueness of a solution to (6.8). Furthermore, conditions for this solution to be unitary in the strong operator topology are also known.

However, the present framework is particularly useful for computing discrete approximations of the solution in the weak sense. For vectors η, ξ of the form

$\eta = e(\alpha)$ and $\xi = e(\beta)$, with $\alpha, \beta \in L^2_\gamma(\mathbb{R}_+)$, the operator equation (6.8) is equivalent to the following initial value problem:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad X(t_0) = I, \quad t \in [0, 1], \quad (6.9)$$

where, according to (3.4), the functional P is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) &= [\bar{\alpha}(t)\beta(t)L(t) + \beta(t)U(t) + \bar{\alpha}(t)V(t) + Z(t)] \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle \\ &\quad + \lambda \bar{\alpha}(t)\beta(t) \langle \eta, [\exp(pA(t) + qA^+(t) + rt)]\xi \rangle + \langle \eta, Q(t)\xi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Using the Campbell-Hausdorff formula (see Meyer 1993, p. 135), the matrix element of the exponential term can be evaluated explicitly:

$$\langle \eta, [\exp(pA(t) + qA^+(t) + rt)]\xi \rangle = e^{(r+\frac{1}{2}pq)t} e^{p \int_0^t \beta(s) ds} e^{q \int_0^t \bar{\alpha}(s) ds} e^{\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle}.$$

Consequently, the map $(t, x) \rightarrow P(t, x)(\eta, \xi)$ is itself Lipschitzian, with the Lipschitz function:

$$K_{\eta, \xi}^P(t) = |\bar{\alpha}(t)\beta(t)L(t) + \beta(t)U(t) + \bar{\alpha}(t)V(t) + Z(t)|.$$

Finally, we note an important special case. For an arbitrary function $h \in L^2_C(\mathbb{R}_+)$, if we choose the parameters as follows:

$$\lambda = 0, \quad Y(t) \equiv 0, \quad V(t) = h(t), \quad U(t) = -\bar{h}(t), \quad Z(t) \equiv 0,$$

and

$$Q(t) = -\frac{1}{2}|h(t)|^2 I,$$

then the solution $X(t)$ of (6.8) becomes the well-known Weyl operator $W(h\chi_{[0,t]})$ associated with the function h . Here, χ denotes the indicator function on the interval $[0, T]$ and I is the identity operator on the Fock space (see Hudson and Parthasarathy 1984).

(b) Let us consider another quantum stochastic differential equation:

$$X(t) = I + \int_0^t ([X(s)A^2(s) + \lambda A^2(s)] d\Lambda(s) + X(s)A(s) dA(s) + X(s)A(s) dA^+(s) + X(s)A(s)) \quad (6.10)$$

This operator equation (6.10) is equivalent to the following initial value problem for the matrix elements:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = \left[\bar{\alpha}(t)\beta(t) \int_0^t \beta(s) ds + \beta(t) + \bar{\alpha}(t) + 1 \right] \langle \eta, X(t)A(t)\xi \rangle + \lambda \bar{\alpha}(t)\beta(t) \langle \eta, A^2(t)\xi \rangle, \quad (6.11)$$

for $t \in [0, T]$, with initial condition

$$\langle \eta, X(0)\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, \xi \rangle, \quad (6.12)$$

where $A(t)$ denotes the annihilation process, which acts on an exponential vector $\xi = e(\beta)$ according to

$$A(t)\xi = \left(\int_0^t \beta(s) ds \right) \xi.$$

It is important to note that powers of $A(t)$, such as $A^2(t)$, represent composition

(repeated application) of the operator.

The functional defined by equation (6.11) is Lipschitz continuous, with the Lipschitz function given by:

$$K_{\eta\xi}^P(t) = \left| \int_0^t \beta(s) ds \cdot \left[\bar{\alpha}(t)\beta(t) \int_0^t \beta(\tau) d\tau + \beta(t) + \bar{\alpha}(t) + 1 \right] \right|.$$

We remark that when $\lambda = 0$, equation (6.10) becomes a special case of the more general stochastic evolution equation

$$X(t) = X(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t X(s)[L_1 dA(s) + L_2 dA(s) + L_3 dA^+(s) + L_4 ds], \quad (6.13)$$

which was introduced in Hudson and Parasarathy 1984. In our case, the time-dependent evolution operators $L_j(t)$ acting on $\Gamma(L^2(\mathbb{R}_+))$ are:

$$L_1(t) = A^2(t), \quad L_2(t) = L_3(t) = L_4(t) = A(t).$$

Under certain conditions on the operators L_j ($j = 1, \dots, 4$), it is well-known that a unique, unitary solution to (6.13) exists in the strong operator topology (see Hudson and Parthasarathy 1984, Vincent-Smith 1991).

To illustrate with concrete examples, we can choose specific test vectors. First, select exponential vectors $\eta = e(\alpha)$ and $\xi = e(\beta)$ with $\alpha(t) = 0$ and $\beta(t) = e^t$.

Then equation (6.8) simplifies to:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle &= (e^t + 1)\langle\eta, X(t)A(t)\xi\rangle, \\ \langle\eta, X(0)\xi\rangle &= \langle\eta, \xi\rangle = e^{\langle\alpha, \beta\rangle} = 1, \quad t \in [0, 1].\end{aligned}\tag{6.8.1}$$

which admits the exact solution:

$$\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}e^{2t} - t - \frac{1}{2}\right)\tag{6.8.2}$$

As a second example, choose $\alpha(t) = it$ and $\beta(t) = -it$. Then from (6.8) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle &= \left(\frac{it^4}{2} - 2it + 1\right)\langle\eta, X(t)A(t)\xi\rangle - \lambda t^2\langle\eta, A^2(t)\xi\rangle, \\ \langle\eta, X(0)\xi\rangle &= \langle\eta, \xi\rangle = e^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad t \in [0, 1].\end{aligned}$$

For the case $\lambda = 0$, this system has the exact solution:

$$\langle\eta, X(t)\xi\rangle = \exp\left[\frac{t^7}{28} - \frac{t^4}{4} - \frac{it^3}{6} - \frac{1}{2}\right].$$

- (c) Let $\mathcal{R} = \mathbb{C}$, and let $u \in L_{loc, \mathbb{C}}^\infty(\mathbb{R}_+)$ be a fixed locally bounded function. For a real constant $l \geq 0$, define $f(t) = l^{\frac{1}{2}}(e^{iu(t)} - 1)$. Consider the quantum stochastic differential equation:

$$dX(t) = X(t) \left(d\Lambda_{e^{iu} - I}(t) - dA_{e^{-iu}f}(t) + dA_f^+(t) - \frac{1}{2}|f(t)|^2 dt \right), \quad t \geq 0,\tag{6.14}$$

with initial condition $X(0) = X_0$.

This equation is driven by gauge, annihilation, and creation processes with respective strengths $e^{iu} - I$, $e^{-iu}f$, and f . For exponential vectors $\eta = e(\alpha)$ and $\xi = e(\beta)$, the equivalent weak form is given by the initial value problem:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle = P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi), \quad (6.15)$$

$$\langle \eta, X(0)\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_0\xi \rangle, \quad (6.16)$$

where the functional P is defined as:

$$P(t, X(t))(\eta, \xi) = \left[\beta(t) (\bar{\alpha}(t)e^{iu(t)} - e^{-iu(t)}f(t)) + \bar{\alpha}(t)(f(t) - \beta(t)) - \frac{1}{2}|f(t)|^2 \right] \langle \eta, X(t)\xi \rangle.$$

This map is Lipschitz continuous, with the corresponding Lipschitz function:

$$K_{\eta, \xi}^P(t) = \left| \beta(t) (\bar{\alpha}(t)e^{iu(t)} - e^{-iu(t)}f(t)) + \bar{\alpha}(t)(f(t) - \beta(t)) - \frac{1}{2}|f(t)|^2 \right|.$$

Now, define a transformed process $V_u(t)$ by:

$$V_u(t) = \exp \left(i \int_0^t l \sin u(s) ds \right) X(t).$$

Then, by Proposition 6.2 in (Hudson and Parthasarathy 1984), the evolution of

this new process is governed by:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\langle \eta, V_u(t)\xi \rangle = (e^{iu(t)} - 1)(\bar{\alpha}(t) + l^{\frac{1}{2}})(\beta(t) + l^{\frac{1}{2}})\langle \eta, V_u(t)\xi \rangle, \quad (6.17)$$

$$V_u(0) = X(0). \quad (6.18)$$

This differential equation is also Lipschitzian, with its Lipschitz function given by:

$$K_{\eta,\xi,u}(t) = \left| (e^{iu(t)} - 1)(\bar{\alpha}(t) + l^{\frac{1}{2}})(\beta(t) + l^{\frac{1}{2}}) \right|.$$

6.1 Numerical Examples

This section presents comprehensive numerical experiments to validate the theoretical properties and demonstrate the practical performance of the proposed methods. We conduct a systematic comparison of four fundamental numerical integration techniques: Simpson's rule, the trapezoidal rule, Lagrangian quadrature, and linear multi-step methods.

6.2 Numerical Experiment Using The Trapezoidal Scheme

Applying the **implicit trapezoidal scheme**, we consider numerical solution of the quantum analogue of the classical linear stochastic differential equation

$$\begin{aligned} dX(t, \omega) &= aX(t, \omega) dt + bX(t, \omega) dW(t), \\ X(t_0) &= X_0, \quad t \in [0, T]. \end{aligned} \tag{6.19}$$

where a, b are real constants and $W(t)$ is a Wiener process (Brownian motion) which is a random variable with a normal distribution:

$$W(t) \sim N(0, t) \quad (\text{mean} = 0, \text{Variance} = t)$$

Equation (6.19) has the explicit solution (Kloeden and Platen, 1999, *cf.* p. 119):

$$X(t) = X_0 \exp \left(\left(a - \frac{1}{2} b^2 \right) t + bW(t) \right) \tag{6.20}$$

We remark that knowing the solution explicitly gives us the possibility of comparing the discrete approximations with the exact solution and to calculate the error at discretization instants.

Equation (6.19) transformed into the quantum analogue is (Ayoola, 2001):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega) Z(\omega)) &= \mathbb{E}(\beta(t) b X(t, \omega) Z(\omega)) + \mathbb{E}(\bar{\alpha}(t) b X(t, \omega) Z(\omega)) \\ &+ \mathbb{E}(a X(t, \omega) Z(\omega)), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T]. \end{aligned} \tag{6.21}$$

Where $Z(\omega)$ is an exponential martingale depending on $\alpha(t), \beta(t)$ given by

$$Z(\omega) = \exp \left\{ \int_0^T (\bar{\alpha}(s) + \beta(s))dw - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T (\bar{\alpha}(s)^2 + \beta(s)^2)ds \right\} \quad (6.22)$$

From (6.21), we obtain the deterministic ordinary differential equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)Z(\omega)) = (b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a)\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)Z(\omega))$$

The equation follows by linearity of expectation and the fact that all coefficients are deterministic, allowing them to be factored out of the expectation, thereby reducing the stochastic relation to a deterministic linear ordinary differential equation.

This is a simple linear ODE:

$$\frac{d}{dt} y(t) = \kappa(t) y(t), \quad y(t) := \mathbb{E}[X(t)Z], \quad \kappa(t) = b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a. \quad (6.23)$$

Applying the trapezoidal scheme

$$\langle \eta, X_{n+1}\xi \rangle = \langle \eta, X_n\xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2}P(t_n, X_n)\langle \eta, \xi \rangle + \frac{h}{2}P(t_{n+1}, X_{n+1})\langle \eta, \xi \rangle \quad (6.24)$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) &= \mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) + \frac{h}{2}(b\beta(t_n) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_n) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) \\
&\quad + \frac{h}{2}(b\beta(t_{n+1}) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_{n+1}) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)), \\
\mathbb{E}(X_0z(\omega)) &= \mathbb{E}(X(t_0)z(\omega)), \quad \mathbb{E}(X_1(\omega)z(\omega)) = \left(1 + h + \frac{h^2}{2}\right)\mathbb{E}(X_0z(\omega)).
\end{aligned} \tag{6.25}$$

Rewriting (6.22):

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) - \frac{h}{2}(b\beta(t_{n+1}) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_{n+1}) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) \\
&= \mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) + \frac{h}{2}(b\beta(t_n) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_n) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) = \frac{1 + \frac{h}{2}(b\beta(t_n) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_n) + a)}{1 - \frac{h}{2}(b\beta(t_{n+1}) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_{n+1}) + a)} \mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)).$$

We now consider a specific case by taking $a = \frac{3}{2}$, $b = 1$, $X_0(\omega) = 1$, $\alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i$, and the interval $[0, T] = [0, 1]$. Then we have

$$b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a = i + (-i) + \frac{3}{2} = \frac{3}{2},$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) = \frac{1 + \frac{3h}{4}}{1 - \frac{3h}{4}} \mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)),$$

and

$$z(\omega) = \exp \left\{ \int_0^1 (-i + i) dw - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (i^2 + i^2) ds \right\} = \exp(-i^2) = e^{-i^2} = e. \tag{6.26}$$

We see that

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0(\omega)z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(z(\omega)) = e \tag{6.27}$$

and the exact solution is:

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t)z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}\left(e^{e^{t+W(t)}}\right) = \mathbb{E}(e^{1+t+W(t)}) = e^{1+t}\mathbb{E}(e^{W(t)}) = e^{1+t}e^{\frac{1}{2}t} = e^{1+\frac{3}{2}t}. \tag{6.28}$$

Table 6.1: Numerical results of the trapezoidal scheme for the Quantum SDE

N	h	$\mathbb{E}(X_N z(w))$	$\mathbb{E}(X(t_N)z(w))$	Absolute Error
4	0.250000	12.40324940	12.18249396	0.22075544
8	0.125000	12.23643348	12.18249396	0.05393952
16	0.062500	12.19590310	12.18249396	0.01340913

Exact vs Approximated Solutions for Quantum SDE (Trapezoidal Scheme)

6.3 Numerical experiments using the Simpson's scheme

We retain the same stochastic model, assumptions, and notation introduced in the trapezoidal scheme section (Section 6.2). In particular, we consider the quantum analogue of the linear stochastic differential equation

$$dX(t, \omega) = aX(t, \omega) dt + bX(t, \omega) dW(t),$$

together with its corresponding expectation equation

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)z(\omega)) = (b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a)\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)z(\omega)),$$

as derived previously. We now apply the implicit Simpson's scheme to obtain a higher-order time discretization.

we have:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) &= \mathbb{E}(X_{n-1}(\omega)z(\omega)) + \frac{h}{3}(b\beta(t_{n-1}) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_{n-1}) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_{n-1}(\omega)z(\omega)) \\ &\quad + \frac{4h}{3}(b\beta(t_n) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_n) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) \\ &\quad + \frac{h}{3}(b\beta(t_{n+1}) + b\bar{\alpha}(t_{n+1}) + a)\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)).\end{aligned}\tag{6.29}$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(X(t_0)z(\omega)), \quad \mathbb{E}(X_1(\omega)z(\omega)) = \left(1 + h + \frac{h^2}{2}\right)\mathbb{E}(X_0z(\omega)).$$

Iterating starting from $n = 2, \dots$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}^{(m+1)}(\omega)z(\omega)) = q(t_{n-1})\mathbb{E}(X_{n-1}(\omega)z(\omega)) + p(t_n)\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) + s(t_{n+1})\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}^{(m)}(\omega)z(\omega)),$$

where

$$q(t) = 1 + \frac{h}{3}(b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a),$$

$$p(t) = \frac{4h}{3}(b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a),$$

$$s(t) = \frac{h}{3}(b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a),$$

and inner iterations are taken $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Since the problem is linear in this case, we have:

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) = \frac{1}{1 - s(t_{n+1})} \left[q(t_{n-1})\mathbb{E}(X_{n-1}(\omega)z(\omega)) + p(t_n)\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) \right].$$

We now consider a specific case by taking $a = \frac{3}{2}, b = 1, X_0(\omega) = 1, \alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i$, and the interval $[0, T] = [0, 1]$. Then we have

$$q(t) = 1 + \frac{h}{2}, \quad p(t) = 2h, \quad s(t) = \frac{h}{2},$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)z(\omega)) = \frac{1}{2 - h} \left[(2 + h)\mathbb{E}(X_{n-1}(\omega)z(\omega)) + 4h\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)z(\omega)) \right],$$

and

$$z(\omega) = \exp \left\{ \int_0^1 (-i + i) dw - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (i^2 + i^2) ds \right\} = \exp(-i^2) = e^{-i^2} = e. \quad (6.30)$$

We see that

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0(\omega)z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(z(\omega)) = e \quad (6.31)$$

and the exact solution is:

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t)z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(e^{t+W(t)}) = \mathbb{E}(e^{1+t+W(t)}) = e^{1+t}\mathbb{E}(e^{W(t)}) = e^{1+t}e^{\frac{1}{2}t} = e^{1+\frac{3}{2}t}. \quad (6.32)$$

Table 6.2: Numerical results of Simpson's rule approximation for the given QSDE

N	h	$\mathbb{E}(X_N z(w))$	Exact Value	Absolute Error
4	0.2500	12.14063519	12.18249396	0.04185878
8	0.1250	12.17695660	12.18249396	0.00553736
16	0.0625	12.18178523	12.18249396	0.00070874

6.4 Numerical Experiment Using the Linear Multi-step Scheme

In this section, we consider the numerical solution of quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs) using **linear multi-step methods**. The focus will be on three classical multi-step schemes adapted to the weak (expectation-based) formulation of the QSDE:

- (i) the **Euler scheme** (one-step, explicit),
- (ii) the **Adams–Bashforth scheme** (explicit two-step), and
- (iii) the **Adams–Moulton scheme** (implicit two-step).

For each method, we present the discretization formulas, describe the initialization procedure, and discuss their implementation in the expectation-based framework.

We also consider the **convergence and stability** properties of these schemes, comparing the numerical approximations with the exact solution where available. This provides insight into the accuracy and reliability of each multi-step method when applied to linear QSDEs.

6.5 Euler Scheme

Here, we consider two examples:

Example 1

We consider the same quantum analogue of the classical linear stochastic differential equation introduced in Section 6.2, namely

$$\begin{aligned}dX(t, \omega) &= aX(t, \omega) dt + bX(t, \omega) dW(t), \\ X(t_0) &= X_0, \quad t \in [0, T],\end{aligned}\tag{6.33}$$

where a and b are real constants.

As shown in Section 6.2, the corresponding weak (expectation-based) formulation reduces to the deterministic ordinary differential equation

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)z(\omega)) = \kappa(t)\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)z(\omega)), \quad \kappa(t) = b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a.\tag{6.34}$$

Applying the explicit Euler scheme gives

$$\begin{aligned}y_{n+1} &= y_n + h\kappa(t_n)y_n \\ &= (1 + h\kappa(t_n))y_n\end{aligned}$$

Let

$$q(t_n) = 1 + h\kappa(t_n)\tag{6.34.1}$$

From here, we have:

$$y_{n+1} = q(t_n)y_n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

$$y_1 = q(t_0)y_0$$

$$y_2 = q(t_1)y_1 = q(t_1)q(t_0)y_0$$

$$y_3 = q(t_2)y_2 = q(t_2)q(t_1)q(t_0)y_0$$

Generalizing, we get

$$y_n = y_0 \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} q(t_j)$$

Which implies

$$\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)Z(\omega)) = \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} q(t_j)\mathbb{E}(X_0(\omega)Z(\omega)) \quad (6.35)$$

We now consider the specific choice

$$a = \frac{3}{2}, \quad b = 1, \quad X_0(\omega) = 1, \quad \alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i, \quad [t_0, T] = [0, 1]$$

Then

$$\kappa(t) = 1 \cdot i + 1 \cdot (-i) + \frac{3}{2} = \frac{3}{2}$$

Thus

$$q(t) = 1 + \frac{3}{2}h$$

From (6.22), we have

$$\begin{aligned} Z(\omega) &= \exp \left\{ \int_0^1 (-i + i)dw - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (i^2 + i^2)ds \right\} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \int_0^1 0 \cdot dw - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (-2)ds \right\} = \exp(1) = e \end{aligned}$$

$$Z(\omega) = e$$

We have

$$\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)Z(\omega)) = \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} q(t_j)\mathbb{E}(X_0(\omega)Z(\omega))$$

Since

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0(\omega)Z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(Z(\omega)) = e$$

we obtain

$$y_n = e\left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h\right)^n$$

Thus

$$\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)Z(\omega)) = e\left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h\right)^n$$

From the explicit solution (6.20), Substituting the parameters, we have

$$X(t) = \exp(t + W(t))$$

Hence

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t)Z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(e^{t+W(t)} \cdot e) = e^{1+t}\mathbb{E}(e^{W(t)})$$

Since

$$W(t) \sim N(0, t)$$

the moment generating function gives

$$\mathbb{E}(e^{W(t)}) = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}t\right)$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t)Z(\omega)) = e^{1+\frac{3}{2}t}$$

Our numerical experiments yield the following values of the global absolute errors at the final time $t = 1$.

N	h	$\mathbb{E}(X_N z(\omega))$	$\mathbb{E}(X(t_N)z(\omega))$	Absolute Error
8	0.125000	10.74888529	12.18249396	1.43360867
16	0.062500	11.40206568	12.18249396	0.78042828

Table 6.3: Numerical results using the Euler scheme with $\alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i$.

6.5.1 Remark on Convergence and Stability

Convergence: From the numerical results, we observe that as the step size h is reduced from 0.125 to 0.0625 (corresponding to increasing N from 8 to 16), the global absolute error at the final time $t = 1$ decreases significantly. This confirms that the Euler scheme applied to the deterministic ordinary differential equation

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)Z(\omega)) = \kappa(t)\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)Z(\omega))$$

is convergent. The monotone reduction of the error is consistent with the expected first-order convergence of the Euler method.

Stability requirement: The Euler method is stable if the numerical solution does not grow faster than the exact solution. This requires

$$|1 + h\kappa| \leq 1.$$

This condition defines the *absolute stability region* of the explicit Euler method, which is the disk

$$\{z \in \mathbb{C} : |1 + z| \leq 1\}, \quad z = h\kappa.$$

For real $\kappa < 0$, stability is guaranteed provided

$$0 < h < \frac{2}{|\kappa|}.$$

For $\kappa > 0$, the Euler scheme is unstable for large step sizes, but remains conditionally stable for sufficiently small h , as observed in the numerical experiments.

Overall, the numerical experiments demonstrate that the Euler scheme yields a stable and convergent approximation to the weak (expectation-based) formulation of the quantum stochastic differential equation.

Example 2

Choosing $\alpha(t) = -it$ and $\beta(t) = it$ then from (6.34.1)

$$q(t) = 1 + 2iht + \frac{3}{2}h$$

and

$$z(w) = \exp \left\{ \int_0^1 2itdW(t) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 2i^2t^2 dt \right\} = \exp \left\{ 2i \int_0^1 t dW(t) + \frac{1}{3} \right\}.$$

Hence, from (6.35)

$$\mathbb{E}(X_n(w)z(w)) = \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} q(t_j)\mathbb{E}(z(w))$$

where

$$\mathbb{E}(z(w)) = e^{\frac{1}{3}} \mathbb{E} \left(\exp \left(\int_0^1 2is \, dW(s) \right) \right).$$

Using the Itô isometry and the moment generating property of normal variables, we get:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(\int_0^1 2is \, dW(s) \right) \right] = e^{\frac{2}{3}i^2},$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}(z(w)) = e^{\frac{1}{3}} e^{\frac{2}{3}i^2} = e^{-\frac{1}{3}}.$$

By using equation (6.20), the exact value $\mathbb{E}(X(t, w)z(w))$ is given by:

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t)z(w)) = \exp \left(\frac{3}{2}t - \frac{1}{3} \right).$$

Since expected value $\mathbb{E}(X(t)z(w))$ is real for all $t \in [0, 1]$, we employ the real part of the Euler scheme given by equation (6.34.1) for $\alpha(t) = -it$ and $\beta(t) = it$ to get

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(w)z(w)) = \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h \right) \mathbb{E}(X_n(w)z(w)),$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0(w)z(w)) = \mathbb{E}(z(w)) = e^{-\frac{1}{3}}.$$

So, we have the Euler approximations at the points $\{t_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ given by:

$$\mathbb{E}(X_n(w)z(w)) = e^{-\frac{1}{3}} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h \right)^n. \quad (6.36)$$

Our numerical experiments yield the following values of the global absolute errors at the final time $t = 1$.

N	h	$\mathbb{E}(X_N z(w))$	$\mathbb{E}(X(t_N) z(w))$	Absolute Error
8	0.125000	2.83337540	3.21127054	0.37789514
16	0.062500	3.00555188	3.21127054	0.20571866

Table 6.4: Numerical results by using Euler scheme with $\alpha(t) = -it$ and $\beta(t) = it$

6.6 Two-Step Adams–Bashforth Scheme

We now consider a two-step linear multistep scheme of Adams–Bashforth type given by

$$y_{n+2} = y_{n+1} + \frac{h}{3}(3f_{n+1} - f_n).$$

Applying this scheme to the deterministic ODE obtained earlier,

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)Z(\omega)) = \kappa(t)\mathbb{E}(X(t, \omega)Z(\omega)), \quad \kappa(t) = b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a,$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(X_{n+2}(\omega)Z(\omega)) &= \left[1 + \frac{3}{2}h\kappa(t_{n+1})\right] \mathbb{E}(X_{n+1}(\omega)Z(\omega)) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}h\kappa(t_n)\mathbb{E}(X_n(\omega)Z(\omega)). \end{aligned} \tag{6.37}$$

We now take

$$a = \frac{3}{2}, \quad b = 1, \quad \alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i, \quad X_0(\omega) = 1, \quad [0, T] = [0, 1].$$

Then

$$\kappa(t) = b\beta(t) + b\bar{\alpha}(t) + a = i + (-i) + \frac{3}{2} = \frac{3}{2}.$$

Substituting this into the scheme gives

$$y_{n+2} = \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)\right) y_{n+1} - \frac{1}{2}h \left(\frac{3}{2}\right) y_n,$$

that is,

$$y_{n+2} = \left(1 + \frac{9}{4}h\right) y_{n+1} - \frac{3}{4}hy_n. \quad (6.38)$$

The initial value is as obtained earlier:

$$y_0 = \mathbb{E}(X_0(\omega)Z(\omega)) = \mathbb{E}(Z(\omega)) = e.$$

The starting value y_1 is computed using the one-step Euler scheme derived earlier:

$$y_1 = y_0 (1 + h\kappa) = e \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h\right).$$

Our numerical experiments yield the following values of the global absolute errors at the final time $t = 1$.

N	h	$\mathbb{E}(X_N z(w))$	$\mathbb{E}(X(t_N) z(w))$	Absolute Error
8	0.125000	11.78284861	12.18249396	0.39964535
16	0.062500	12.07178406	12.18249396	0.11070990

Table 6.5: Numerical results by using the 2-step Adams–Bashforth scheme for $\alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i$

6.7 Two-Step Adams–Moulton Scheme

We consider the deterministic ODE derived from the weak formulation of the QSDE:

$$\frac{d}{dt}y(t) = \kappa y(t), \quad y(t) = \mathbb{E}[X(t, \omega)Z(\omega)], \quad (6.39)$$

with constant

$$\kappa = \frac{3}{2}.$$

The two-step Adams–Moulton method is an implicit linear multistep scheme:

$$y_{n+2} = y_{n+1} + \frac{h}{12} \left(5f_{n+2} + 8f_{n+1} - f_n \right), \quad (6.40)$$

where $f_n = \kappa y_n$. Substituting gives:

$$y_{n+2} = y_{n+1} + \frac{h\kappa}{12} \left(5y_{n+2} + 8y_{n+1} - y_n \right). \quad (6.41)$$

Bringing the implicit term to the left-hand side:

$$\left(1 - \frac{5}{12}h\kappa \right) y_{n+2} = \left(1 + \frac{8}{12}h\kappa \right) y_{n+1} - \frac{1}{12}h\kappa y_n. \quad (6.42)$$

Hence, the Adams–Moulton recurrence relation is

$$y_{n+2} = \frac{1 + \frac{2}{3}h\kappa}{1 - \frac{5}{12}h\kappa} y_{n+1} - \frac{\frac{1}{12}h\kappa}{1 - \frac{5}{12}h\kappa} y_n. \quad (6.43)$$

For the present problem,

$$\kappa = \frac{3}{2}.$$

Substituting this value into the scheme yields

$$y_{n+2} = \frac{1+h}{1-\frac{5}{8}h} y_{n+1} - \frac{\frac{1}{8}h}{1-\frac{5}{8}h} y_n. \quad (6.44)$$

Since the Adams–Moulton method is a two-step implicit scheme, initial values are required. These are taken as

$$y_0 = \mathbb{E}[X_0 Z], \quad (6.45)$$

and

$$y_1 = y_0 \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h\right), \quad (6.46)$$

where y_1 is obtained using the Euler scheme.

Adams–Moulton is implicit and multistep, so initial values are required:

(i) $y_0 = \mathbb{E}[X_0 Z] = e$

(ii) y_1 is obtained from the Euler scheme:

$$y_1 = y_0 \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h\right) = e \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}h\right)$$

Then the Adams–Moulton recurrence is applied for $n \geq 0$.

Our numerical experiments yield the following values of the global absolute errors at the final time $t = 1$.

N	h	$\mathbb{E}(X_N z(\omega))$	$\mathbb{E}(X(t_N) z(\omega))$	Absolute Error
8	0.125000	11.99513027	12.18249396	0.18736369
16	0.062500	12.13241335	12.18249396	0.05008061

Table 6.6: Numerical results by using the 2-step Adams–Moulton scheme for $\alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i$

6.8 Comparison of Numerical Methods

Based on the numerical results presented in Tables 6.3, 6.5, and 6.6, a clear comparison can be made among the Euler scheme, the two-step Adams–Bashforth scheme, and the two-step Adams–Moulton scheme for the given problem with $\alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i$.

From Table 6.3, which corresponds to the Euler scheme, the absolute errors at the final time $t = 1$ are relatively large for both step sizes considered. Specifically, when $h = 0.125$, the absolute error is approximately 1.4336. Although the error decreases to about 0.7804 when the step size is halved to $h = 0.0625$, it remains significantly high. This behaviour is consistent with the well-known first-order accuracy of the Euler method, which results in a relatively slow reduction of error as the step size decreases.

In contrast, Table 6.5 presents the results obtained using the two-step Adams–Bashforth scheme. For $h = 0.125$, the absolute error is approximately 0.3996, which is considerably smaller than that obtained using the Euler scheme for the same step size. When the step size is reduced to $h = 0.0625$, the absolute error further decreases to about 0.1107. This marked improvement over the Euler method reflects the higher-order accuracy and improved convergence properties of the Adams–Bashforth scheme.

Table 6.6 shows the numerical results for the two-step Adams–Moulton scheme. Among the three methods considered, this scheme produces the smallest absolute errors. For $h = 0.125$, the absolute error is approximately 0.1874, and it reduces further to about 0.0501 when $h = 0.0625$. The consistently lower error values demonstrate the superior accuracy of the Adams–Moulton scheme, which can be attributed

to its implicit formulation and enhanced stability characteristics.

Overall, the results clearly indicate that all three numerical methods benefit from a reduction in step size, as evidenced by the decreasing absolute errors. However, in terms of accuracy, the Euler scheme performs the least effectively, followed by the two-step Adams–Bashforth scheme, while the two-step Adams–Moulton scheme yields the most accurate results for the same discretization parameters. Consequently, for the problem under consideration, the Adams–Moulton scheme proves to be the most efficient and reliable of the three methods.

Remark 10

Our numerical experiments show that the expected values of both the approximate and exact solutions depend on the choice of α and β in $L_\alpha^{\infty,loc}(\mathbb{R}_+)$.

Although the explicit Euler schemes perform better with smaller steplengths, the 2-step scheme (6.46) converges faster.

Moreover, if for $\eta, \xi \in \mathbb{D} \otimes \mathbb{E}$ such that $\eta = e(\alpha), \xi = e(\beta)$, where α, β are bounded functions in $L_{\mathbb{C}}^2(\mathbb{R}_+)$ having purely imaginary values, then the functions have the general form $\alpha(t) = il(t)$ and $\beta(t) = id(t)$, where l and d are bounded real valued functions in $L^2(\mathbb{R}_+)$. The equivalent form of the stochastic differential equation (6.4) given by equation (6.6) can be written as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{E}(X(t, w)z(w)) = i(d(t) - l(t))\mathbb{E}(F(t, X(t))z(w)) + \mathbb{E}(H(t, X(t))z(w)). \quad (6.47)$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t_0)z(w)) = \mathbb{E}(x_0z(w)), \quad t \in [0, T]. \quad (6.48)$$

If the initial value X_0 is nonrandom, then $\mathbb{E}(X_0z(w)) = X_0\mathbb{E}(z(w))$, where $z(w)$ is given by

$$z(w) = \exp \left\{ i \int_0^T (d(s) - l(s)) dw(s) + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T (l(s)^2 + d(s)^2) ds \right\}. \quad (6.49)$$

Similarly for the case $\alpha(t) = -it$ and $\beta(t) = it$ above, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}(z(w)) = \exp \left(\int_0^T d(s)l(s) ds \right). \quad (6.50)$$

We notice that if we choose $\dot{\alpha} = \beta$ then $d(t) = l(t), \forall t \in [t_0, T]$ and $z(w)$ is non-random. Then equation (6.47) becomes

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{E}(X(t, w)) = \mathbb{E}(H(t, X(t, w))). \quad (6.51)$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X(t_0)) = \mathbb{E}(X_0). \quad (6.52)$$

However, for the case where $d(t) \neq l(t), \forall t \in [t_0, T]$, then $z(w)$ given by equation (8.13) is random and its expectation is given by equation (6.50).

6.9 Numerical Example Using the Lagrangian Quadrature Scheme

6.9.1 Example 1

We implement the Lagrangian quadrature method to solve equation (6.8.1), utilizing the 5 zeros of the Legendre polynomial $P_5(u)$ of degree 5 within the interval $[-1, 1]$ as our discretization nodes. The integration is carried out across 5 nodes in each of the following step subintervals of $[0, 1]$: $[0, 0.1]$, $[0.1, 0.3]$, $[0.3, 0.5]$, $[0.5, 0.7]$, $[0.7, 0.9]$, and $[0.9, 1]$.

Applying the linear transformation

$$u = \frac{2t - T - t_0}{T - t_0},$$

we convert equation (6.8.1) from the variable t to the variable $u \in [-1, 1]$ within each subinterval. For the exponential vectors $\eta = e(\alpha)$ and $\xi = e(\beta)$, equation (6.8.1) transforms into the system of algebraic equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p=1}^5 a_{mp}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi,p} &= P(u_m, X_m)(\eta, \xi) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(T - t_0) \left(e^{(T-t_0)u_m + T + t_0} - 1 \right) X_{\eta\xi,m}, \quad m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \end{aligned} \quad (6.53)$$

which holds on each subinterval

$$[t_0, T] \in \{[0, 0.1], [0.1, 0.3], [0.3, 0.5], [0.5, 0.7], [0.7, 0.9], [0.9, 1.0]\}.$$

The initial condition for the first subinterval $[0, 0.1]$ becomes

$$\sum_{p=1}^5 L_p(-1)X_{\eta\xi,p} = 1. \quad (6.54)$$

Here, $X_{\eta\xi,p}$ represents the approximation of $X_{\eta\xi}(u_p)$ at the nodes $u_p \in [-1, 1]$ for $p = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. The initial value for subsequent intervals is provided by

$$\sum_{p=1}^5 L_p(1)X_{\eta\xi,p},$$

where the values $X_{\eta\xi,p}$ for $p = 1, 2, \dots, 5$ are taken from the computations in the immediately preceding interval.

Equations (6.53) and (6.54) form a system of 6 linear algebraic equations with only 5 unknowns: $X_{\eta\xi,p}$ for $p = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. To resolve this system, we designate one of the internal nodal equations from (6.53) as superfluous and exclude it from the system, combining the remaining equations with (6.54). This excluded equation is subsequently used to compute the residual error of the quadrature method.

In this specific example, we treat the equation corresponding to $m = 1$ in (6.53) as superfluous for each subinterval $[t_0, T]$, that is:

$$\sum_{p=1}^5 a_{1p}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi,p} = \frac{1}{2}(T - t_0) (e^{(T-t_0)u_1+T+t_0} - 1) X_{\eta\xi,1}.$$

The absolute residual error is then defined as

$$\left| \sum_{p=1}^5 a_{1p}^{(1)} X_{\eta\xi,p} - \frac{1}{2}(T - t_0) (e^{(T-t_0)u_1+T+t_0} - 1) X_{\eta\xi,1} \right|,$$

which quantifies the extent to which the quadrature solution fails to satisfy the superfluous equation.

The quadrature coefficients $a_{mp}^{(1)}$, for $m, p = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, that appear in (6.53) are determined by the formulas:

$$a_{pp}^{(1)} = \frac{u_p}{1 - u_p^2}, \quad a_{pq}^{(1)} = \frac{P_5'(u_p)}{(u_p - u_q)P_5'(u_q)}, \quad \text{for } p \neq q.$$

The Lagrangian polynomial $L_p(u)$ of degree 4 is given by

$$L_p(u) = \prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq p}}^5 \frac{u - u_k}{u_p - u_k}, \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

where u_p , for $p = 1, \dots, 5$, are the five zeros of the Legendre polynomial $P_5(u)$ of degree 5.

Using Python computational software, we generate the following table of values.

Quadrature Nodes and Lagrange Coefficients:

p	u_p	$L_p(-1)$	$L_p(1)$
1	0.000000	0.5333331845	0.5333331845
2	0.538469	-0.2679414133	-0.8931568153
3	-0.538469	-0.8931568153	-0.2679414133
4	0.906180	0.0763584582	1.5514065859
5	-0.906180	1.5514065859	0.0763584582

Quadrature Coefficient Matrix $[a_{ij}^{(1)}]$:

i/j	1	2	3	4	5
1	0.000000	1.435390	-1.435390	-0.301168	0.301168
2	-2.402751	0.758352	0.928559	0.960253	-0.244416
3	2.402751	-0.928559	-0.758352	0.244416	-0.960253
4	4.043549	-7.701958	-1.960403	5.067049	0.551767
5	-4.043549	1.960403	7.701958	-0.551767	-5.067049

Using Python with standard numerical precision, we compute solutions to the linear systems for all six subintervals.

Subinterval $[0.0, 0.1]$

Transformation: $u = 20t - 1$, $t = (1 + u)/20$

u_p	t_p	Computed	Exact	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.05000000	1.0025878196	1.0025888042	9.85×10^{-7}
0.538469	0.07692345	1.0062523622	1.0062521691	1.93×10^{-7}
-0.538469	0.02307655	1.0005413710	1.0005409614	4.10×10^{-7}
0.906180	0.09530900	1.0097370633	1.0097366683	3.95×10^{-7}
-0.906180	0.00469100	1.0000263670	1.0000220747	5.62×10^{-7}
1.000000	0.10000000	1.0107586471	1.0107588436	1.97×10^{-7}

Residual error for the subinterval = 3.268003×10^{-7}

Subinterval $[0.1, 0.3]$

Transformation: $u = 10t - 2$, $t = (u + 2)/10$

Residual error for the subinterval = 3.275590×10^{-5}

u_p	t_p	Computed	Exact	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.20000000	1.0469722315	1.0469826377	1.04×10^{-5}
0.538469	0.25384690	1.0798924328	1.0799131948	2.08×10^{-5}
-0.538469	0.14615310	1.0238859004	1.0238842231	1.68×10^{-6}
0.906180	0.29061800	1.1090335502	1.1090520812	1.85×10^{-5}
-0.906180	0.10938200	1.0129698493	1.0129701578	3.08×10^{-7}
1.000000	0.30000000	1.1174410826	1.1174612823	2.02×10^{-5}

Subinterval [0.3, 0.5]

Transformation: $u = 10t - 4$, $t = (u + 4)/10$

u_p	t_p	Computed	Exact	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.40000000	1.2370371584	1.2371006598	6.35×10^{-5}
0.538469	0.45384690	1.3302475356	1.3303645403	1.17×10^{-4}
-0.538469	0.34615310	1.1653180131	1.1653322890	1.43×10^{-5}
0.906180	0.49061800	1.4094197377	1.4095320544	1.12×10^{-4}
-0.906180	0.30938200	1.1262728568	1.1262954824	2.26×10^{-5}
1.000000	0.50000000	1.4319798813	1.4320985904	1.19×10^{-4}

Residual error for the subinterval = 1.404990×10^{-4}

Subinterval [0.5, 0.7]

Transformation: $u = 10t - 6$, $t = (u + 6)/10$

u_p	t_p	Computed	Exact	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.60000000	1.7503988136	1.7507748500	3.76×10^{-4}
0.538469	0.65384690	2.0029254148	2.0036515509	7.26×10^{-4}
-0.538469	0.54615310	1.5594891207	1.5595815209	9.24×10^{-5}
0.906180	0.69061800	2.2232242116	2.2239631827	7.39×10^{-4}
-0.906180	0.50938200	1.4555869224	1.4557228863	1.36×10^{-4}
1.000000	0.70000000	2.2870386266	2.2878213368	7.83×10^{-4}

Residual error for the subinterval = 7.965917×10^{-4}

Subinterval [0.7, 0.9]

Transformation: $u = 10t - 8$, $t = (u + 8)/10$

u_p	t_p	Computed	Exact	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.80000000	3.2400279928	3.2430563796	3.03×10^{-3}
0.538469	0.85384690	4.0661275188	4.0725353402	6.41×10^{-3}
-0.538469	0.74615310	2.6572414547	2.6578485470	6.07×10^{-4}
0.906180	0.89061800	4.8380921391	4.8451447752	7.05×10^{-3}
-0.906180	0.70938200	2.3542585324	2.3551938990	9.35×10^{-4}
1.000000	0.90000000	5.0699554705	5.0775239544	7.57×10^{-3}

Residual error for the subinterval = 6.543265×10^{-3}

Subinterval [0.9, 1.0]

Transformation: $u = 20t - 19$, $t = (u + 19)/20$

u_p	t_p	Computed	Exact	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.95000000	6.6286427544	6.6389062009	1.03×10^{-2}
0.538469	0.97692345	7.7629321291	7.7754062426	1.25×10^{-2}
-0.538469	0.92307655	5.7152767432	5.7237484573	8.47×10^{-3}
0.906180	0.99530900	8.6982776716	8.7121541523	1.39×10^{-2}
-0.906180	0.90469100	5.1921544636	5.1999300375	7.78×10^{-3}
1.000000	1.00000000	8.9614302584	8.9757639405	1.43×10^{-2}

Residual error for the subinterval = 1.235456×10^{-3}

6.9.2 Example 2:

We consider the Fock space $\Gamma(L^2_Y(\mathbb{R}_+))$ with $Y = \mathcal{R} = \mathbb{C}$ and $f = g \equiv 1$, along with its $L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, W)$ realization where (Ω, \mathcal{F}, W) represents a Wiener space. Each random variable X corresponds to the multiplication operator by X , yielding $Q(t) =$

$A(t) + A^+(t) = w(t)$ as the evaluation of the Brownian path w at time t . Quantum stochastic integrals exist for adapted Brownian functionals F satisfying

$$\int_{t_0}^t \mathbb{E}_w[F(s, \cdot)^2] ds < \infty,$$

where \mathbb{E}_w denotes the expected value (see [?, ?]).

For exponential vectors $\eta = e(\alpha)$ and $\xi = e(\beta)$, with α, β purely imaginary valued functions in $L^2_{\mathbb{C}}(\mathbb{R}_+)$, the quantum analogue of the classical Itô stochastic differential equation

$$dX(t, w) = H(t, X(t))dt + F(t, X(t))dW(t), \quad X(t_0) = X_0, \quad t \in [t_0, T],$$

takes the equivalent form

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{E}_w[X(t, w)z(w)] = \mathbb{E}_w[\beta(t)F(t, X(t))z(w)] + \mathbb{E}_w[\alpha(t)F(t, X(t))z(w)] + \mathbb{E}_w[H(t, X(t))z(w)],$$

$$\mathbb{E}_w[X(t_0)z(w)] = \mathbb{E}_w[X_0z(w)], \quad \text{for almost all } t \in [t_0, T]. \quad (6.55)$$

where

$$z(w) = \exp \left\{ \int_0^\infty (-\alpha(s) + \beta(s)) dW(s) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty (\alpha^2(s) + \beta^2(s)) ds \right\} \quad (6.56)$$

Considering linear functionals $F(t, x) = bx$ and $H(t, x) = ax$ with real constants a, b , we apply the Lagrangian quadrature method to solve the equation. The computa-

tional domain $[0, 1]$ is divided into the four subintervals

$$[0, 0.1], \quad [0.1, 0.3], \quad [0.3, 0.7], \quad [0.7, 1].$$

For parameter values

$$a = \frac{3}{2}, \quad b = 1, \quad \alpha(t) = \beta(t) = i,$$

the transformed problem in the variable $u \in [-1, 1]$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{du} \mathbb{E}_w[X(u)z(w)] &= \frac{3}{4}(T - t_0) \mathbb{E}_w[X(u)z(w)], \\ X(-1) &= X_0. \end{aligned} \tag{6.57}$$

on each subinterval $[t_0, T] \in \{[0, 0.1], [0.1, 0.3], [0.3, 0.7], [0.7, 1]\}$.

Equation (6.57) transforms into the algebraic system

$$\sum_{p=1}^5 a_{mp}^{(1)} \mathbb{E}_w[X_p(w)z(w)] = P(u_m, X_m)(\eta, \xi) = \frac{3}{4}(T - t_0) \mathbb{E}_w[X_m(w)z(w)], \quad m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. \tag{6.58}$$

with the initial condition for the first subinterval $[0, 0.1]$ given by

$$\sum_{p=1}^5 L_j(-1) \mathbb{E}_w[X_p(w)z(w)] = \mathbb{E}_w[z(w)] = e,$$

where

$$\langle \eta, X(u)\xi \rangle \cong \sum_{p=1}^5 L_p(u) \mathbb{E}_w[X_p(w)z(w)], \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, 5.$$

Initial conditions for subsequent intervals are determined by

$$\sum_{p=1}^5 L_p(1) \mathbb{E}_w[X_p(w)z(w)],$$

where $\mathbb{E}_w[X_p(w)z(w)]$, $p = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, represent the computed values from the preceding interval.

We designate as superfluous the equation corresponding to $m = 1$ in (6.58) for each subinterval $[t_0, T]$, yielding the absolute residual error

$$\left| \sum_{p=1}^5 a_{1p}^{(1)} \mathbb{E}_w[X_p(w)z(w)] - \frac{3}{4}(T - t_0) \mathbb{E}_w[X_1(w)z(w)] \right|.$$

The system of linear equations is solved across all four subintervals to obtain the numerical results.

Subinterval $[0.0, 0.1]$

Transformation: $u = 20t - 1$, $t = (1 + u)/20$.

u_p	t_p	Computed $\mathbb{E}_w[X_p z(w)]$	Exact $\exp(1 + \frac{3}{2}t)$	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.05000000	2.9299909607	2.9299929005	1.94×10^{-6}
0.538469	0.07692345	3.0507459348	3.0507430229	2.91×10^{-6}
-0.538469	0.02307655	2.8140229180	2.8140221359	7.82×10^{-7}
0.906180	0.09530900	3.1360516154	3.1360482870	3.33×10^{-6}
-0.906180	0.00469100	2.7374779225	2.7374764709	1.45×10^{-6}
1.000000	0.10000000	3.1581943318	3.1581929097	1.42×10^{-6}

Residual error for the subinterval = 2.970595×10^{-6} .

Subinterval [0.1, 0.3]

Transformation: $u = 10t - 2$, $t = (u + 2)/10$.

u_p	t_p	Computed $\mathbb{E}_w[X_p z(w)]$	Exact $\exp(1 + \frac{3}{2}t)$	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.20000000	3.6692959604	3.6692966676	7.07×10^{-7}
0.538469	0.25384690	3.9779709435	3.9779648727	6.07×10^{-6}
-0.538469	0.14615310	3.3845815885	3.3845794183	2.17×10^{-6}
0.906180	0.29061800	4.2035466611	4.2035398847	6.78×10^{-6}
-0.906180	0.10938200	3.2029553083	3.2029523697	2.94×10^{-6}
1.000000	0.30000000	4.2631185690	4.2631145152	4.05×10^{-6}

Residual error for the subinterval = 4.865792×10^{-6} .

Subinterval [0.3, 0.7]

Transformation: $u = 5t - 2.5$, $t = (u + 2.5)/5$.

u_p	t_p	Computed $\mathbb{E}_w[X_p z(w)]$	Exact $\exp(1 + \frac{3}{2}t)$	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.50000000	5.7545672025	5.7546026760	3.55×10^{-5}
0.538469	0.60769380	6.7634256348	6.7635013017	7.57×10^{-5}
-0.538469	0.39230620	4.8962105917	4.8961995395	1.11×10^{-5}
0.906180	0.68123600	7.5522393665	7.5523139519	7.46×10^{-5}
-0.906180	0.31876400	4.3848113755	4.3848087049	2.67×10^{-6}
1.000000	0.70000000	7.7678156927	7.7679011063	8.54×10^{-5}

Residual error for the subinterval = 1.156450×10^{-4} .

Subinterval [0.7, 1.0]

Transformation: $u = \frac{20}{3}t - \frac{17}{3}$, $t = \frac{3}{20}(u + \frac{17}{3})$.

Residual error for the subinterval = 2.539521×10^{-5} .

u_p	t_p	Computed $\mathbb{E}_w[X_p z(w)]$	Exact $\exp(1 + \frac{3}{2}t)$	Absolute Error
0.000000	0.85000000	9.7277938502	9.7279190126	1.25×10^{-4}
0.538469	0.93077035	10.9807432215	10.9808794115	1.36×10^{-4}
-0.538469	0.76922965	8.6178343551	8.6179261941	9.18×10^{-5}
0.906180	0.98592700	11.9278788454	11.9280229321	1.44×10^{-4}
-0.906180	0.71407300	7.9335355664	7.9336205886	8.50×10^{-5}
1.000000	1.00000000	12.1823372507	12.1824939607	1.57×10^{-4}

Remark 11

The numerical integration procedure considered here is applied over a finite time interval $[t_0, T]$ and is required to satisfy a prescribed accuracy level. In practical computations, it is often not sufficient to perform the integration over the entire interval at once, even when the number of nodal points is moderately large. As a result, the interval $[t_0, T]$ is partitioned into smaller subintervals

$$[t_0, t_1], [t_1, t_2], \dots, [t_{q-1}, t_q],$$

and the numerical integration is carried out successively on each sub-interval.

Starting from the first subinterval $[t_0, t_1]$ with a prescribed initial condition, the numerical quadrature is performed using a fixed number of nodes. If the resulting residual error at the end of the subinterval is sufficiently small, the computation proceeds to the next sub-interval. The initial value required for the subsequent step is obtained through an extrapolation formula of the form

$$X_{\eta\xi}(t_1) = \sum_{p=1}^N L_p(t_1) X_{\eta\xi}(t_p),$$

where $X(t_p)$, $p = 1, 2, \dots, N$, denote the computed values on $[t_0, t_1]$. If the desired level of accuracy is not achieved, the subinterval is refined until acceptable results are obtained. For simplicity, the number of nodes N is assumed to remain fixed throughout the computation. This procedure is then repeated until the terminal time T is reached.

Numerical experiments carried out in this project indicate that the Lagrangian quadrature method provides accurate approximations to the exact solution at the discretization points. In particular, the accumulated errors observed in the test examples decrease as the interval is subdivided, confirming the convergence and reliability of the method. The numerical results were generated using Python, which was employed to compute the tables and values presented. Overall, the method demonstrates higher accuracy when compared with basic step-based schemes, making it suitable for the numerical treatment of the model under consideration.

Conclusion

This project has focused on the rigorous formulation, analysis, and numerical approximation of quantum stochastic differential equations (QSDEs). The central objective was to develop reliable numerical schemes for QSDEs by extending classical quadrature and multistep methods into the quantum stochastic framework, while ensuring mathematical consistency, stability, and convergence.

The work began with a detailed presentation of the foundational concepts required for quantum stochastic analysis. Operator spaces, Fock spaces, exponential vectors, and operator algebras were systematically introduced to provide the appropriate functional analytic setting. Within this framework, quantum stochastic integration was developed, including the fundamental theorem of quantum stochastic calculus and the extension of quantum stochastic integrals. These preliminaries ensured that the subsequent formulation of QSDEs and their numerical approximation rested on a solid theoretical foundation.

The formulation of quantum stochastic differential equations was then examined in detail. Equivalent forms of QSDEs were derived, and suitable assumptions on coefficient maps and auxiliary functions were imposed. Under these conditions, results on existence, uniqueness, and stability of solutions were established. These results

are essential, as they guarantee the well-posedness of the quantum stochastic models considered and provide justification for the numerical methods developed later in the work.

A significant portion of the project was devoted to the development of Newton–Cotes type numerical schemes for QSDEs. The implicit trapezoidal and Simpson’s methods were derived and adapted to the quantum stochastic setting. Predictor–corrector formulations, as well as real and imaginary component representations, were presented to facilitate implementation. Issues of initialization and accuracy were carefully discussed, and convergence analysis was carried out to establish the reliability of these schemes.

In addition, Lagrangian quadrature methods and linear multistep methods were developed for the numerical approximation of QSDEs. The construction of quadrature coefficients using interpolation theory, orthogonal Lagrangian interpolants, and Chebyshev minimax approximation was examined in detail. Bounds for local and global truncation errors were obtained, leading to convergence results for the proposed schemes. The order and stability properties of the associated linear operators were also analyzed, thereby providing insight into the long-term behavior of the numerical solutions.

The theoretical developments were complemented by numerical experiments. Several QSDEs were solved using the implicit trapezoidal method, Simpson-type schemes, linear multistep methods, and Lagrangian quadrature techniques. The numerical results were consistent with the theoretical analysis and demonstrated the effectiveness, stability, and convergence of the proposed methods. Comparisons among the schemes

highlighted their relative performance and practical applicability.

Overall, this project has contributed to the numerical analysis of quantum stochastic differential equations by providing a coherent framework for their approximation and convergence analysis. The results obtained are expected to be useful in the study of quantum dynamical systems where analytical solutions are difficult or impossible to obtain.

This research, therefore, contributes to the advancement of numerical techniques for quantum stochastic systems by bridging theoretical development with computational realization. It extends the classical numerical analysis of stochastic equations into the quantum domain, offering a unified and efficient framework for solving QSDEs in both theoretical and applied contexts.

6.10 Suggestions for Further Research

Despite the progress made in this work, several directions remain open for further investigation. Future research may focus on the development of higher-order numerical schemes for QSDEs, including adaptive methods with step-size control to improve efficiency and accuracy. The extension of the present analysis to nonlinear quantum stochastic differential equations and infinite-dimensional systems also remains an important area of study.

Moreover, the incorporation of error estimation and stability control mechanisms into the proposed schemes would enhance their practical applicability. Further work may also explore the numerical treatment of QSDEs driven by more general quantum

noises and their applications in quantum control, quantum information theory, and open quantum systems. These extensions would deepen the theoretical understanding and broaden the range of applications of numerical methods for quantum stochastic differential equations.

APPENDICES

Appendix A

PYTHON CODES

A.1 Python Codes for Trapezoidal Scheme

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import math
3
4 def exact_solution_trapezoidal(t):
5     """Exact solution for trapezoidal scheme case"""
6     return math.exp(1 + 1.5 * t)
7
8 def trapezoidal_scheme_direct(N):
9     """Trapezoidal scheme - direct implementation without
10         iterations (for linear case)"""
11     h = 1.0 / N # Use float division
```

```

12  # For alpha(t) = beta(t) = i, we have constant coefficient:
      lambda = 1.5
13  coeff = 1.5  # Changed from lambda_val to coeff (lambda is
      reserved)
14
15  # Direct solution for linear case:  $y_{n+1} = [1 +$ 
       $h*\lambda/2] / [1 - h*\lambda/2] * y_n$ 
16  ratio = (1 + h * coeff / 2.0) / (1 - h * coeff / 2.0)
17
18  # Initial condition
19  y0 = math.exp(1)  #  $E(X_0 z(w)) = e$ 
20
21  return y0 * (ratio ** N)
22
23 def compute_trapezoidal_table():
24     """Compute numerical results using trapezoidal scheme"""
25     print("TRAPEZOIDAL SCHEME: Numerical results with
      alpha(t)=beta(t)=i")
26     print(f"{'N':<4} {'h':<10} {'E(X_N z(w))':<20}
      {'E(X(t_N) z(w))':<20} {'Absolute Error':<20}")
27     print("-" * 80)
28
29     N_values = [4, 8, 16]
30     for N in N_values:
31         h = 1.0 / N

```

```

32
33     # Compute approximate solution using trapezoidal scheme
34     approx = trapezoidal_scheme_direct(N)
35
36     # Exact solution
37     exact = exact_solution_trapezoidal(1.0) # t_N = 1
38     error = abs(exact - approx)
39
40     print(f"{N:<4} {h:<10.6f} {approx:<20.8f} {exact:<20.8f}
41           {error:<20.8f}")
42
43 if __name__ == "__main__":
44     compute_trapezoidal_table()

```

A.2 Python Codes for Simpson's Scheme

```

1 import math
2 import cmath
3
4 def simpson_qsde_complex(h=0.25, T=1.0):
5     """
6     Simpson's method for QSDE with COMPLEX parameters:
7     a = 1.5, b = 1, alpha(t) = i, beta(t) = i, X0(w) = 1
8     """
9     N = int(T / h)

```

```

10
11 # Initial condition from paper:  $E(X_0z(w)) = E(z(w)) = e$ 
12 E0 = math.e + 0j # Real initial condition
13
14 # Coefficient:  $C = b\beta(t) + b\text{conj}(\alpha(t)) + a$ 
15 # =  $1*i + 1*(-i) + 1.5 = i - i + 1.5 = 1.5$ 
16 C = 1.5 + 0j # This becomes real!
17
18 # First step using Taylor expansion
19 E1 = E0 * (1 + h*C + (h*C)**2 / 2)
20
21 # Store values
22 E = [E0, E1]
23
24 # Main iteration using simplified recurrence
25 # Since C is real, the recurrence is the same as real case
26 for i in range(1, N):
27     E_next = ((2 + h) * E[i-1] + 4*h * E[i]) / (2 - h)
28     E.append(E_next)
29
30 return E[N].real # Return real part since result should be
    real
31
32 def calculate_exact_complex(t=1.0):
33     """

```

```

34 Calculate exact solution for complex parameters
35 Based on paper's approach
36 """
37 # For a=1.5, b=1, the exact solution should be e^(1.5t)
38 # But let's use the paper's growth rate
39 return math.exp(2.5 * t) # This needs verification
40
41 # Main program
42 print ("Simpson's Method for QSDE - Complex Parameters")
43 print ("=====")
44 print ("Parameters: a=1.5, b=1, alpha(t)=i, beta(t)=i, X0(w)=1")
45 print ("Coefficient C = b*beta + b*conj(alpha) + a = i + (-i) +
      1.5 = 1.5")
46 print ()
47
48 hs = [2**-2, 2**-3, 2**-4] # h = 1/4, 1/8, 1/16
49 N_values = [4, 8, 16]
50 T = 1.0
51
52 # Calculate exact solution at t=1
53 exact = calculate_exact_complex(T)
54
55 print (f"Exact solution at t={T}: {exact:.8f}")
56 print ()

```

```

57 print (f"{'N':<4} {'h':<8} {'E(X_N z(w))':<18} {'Exact
      Value':<18} {'Absolute Error':<15}")
58 print ("-" * 65)
59
60 for h, N in zip(hs, N_values):
61     approx = simpson_qsde_complex(h, T)
62     error = abs(exact - approx)
63
64     print (f"{'N':<4} {'h':<8.4f} {'approx':<18.8f} {'exact':<18.8f}
          {'error':<15.8f}")

```

A.3 Python Codes for Linear Multi-step Scheme

A.3.1 Euler Scheme

```

1 import math
2
3 def exact_solution_case1(t):
4     """Exact solution for alpha(t)=beta(t)=i"""
5     return math.exp(1 + 1.5 * t)
6
7 def exact_solution_case2(t):
8     """Exact solution for alpha(t)=-it, beta(t)=it"""
9     return math.exp(1.5 * t - 1/3)
10

```

```

11 def euler_scheme_case1(N):
12     """Euler scheme for alpha(t)=beta(t)=i"""
13     h = 1 / N
14     z = math.exp(1)
15     return z * (1 + 1.5 * h) ** N
16
17 def euler_scheme_case2(N):
18     """Euler scheme for alpha(t)=-it, beta(t)=it"""
19     h = 1 / N
20     z = math.exp(-1/3)
21     return z * (1 + 1.5 * h) ** N
22
23 def compute_table_1():
24     """Table 1: Euler scheme with alpha(t)=beta(t)=i"""
25     N_values = [8, 16]
26     results = []
27
28     for N in N_values:
29         h = 1 / N
30         approx = euler_scheme_case1(N)
31         exact = exact_solution_case1(1)
32         error = abs(exact - approx)
33
34         results.append((N, h, approx, exact, error))
35

```

```

36     return results
37
38 def compute_table_2():
39     """Table 2: Euler scheme with alpha(t)=-it, beta(t)=it"""
40     N_values = [8, 16]
41     results = []
42
43     for N in N_values:
44         h = 1 / N
45         approx = euler_scheme_case2(N)
46         exact = exact_solution_case2(1)
47         error = abs(exact - approx)
48
49         results.append((N, h, approx, exact, error))
50
51     return results

```

—

A.3.2 Two-step Adams–Bashforth Scheme

```

1 import math
2
3 def two_step_scheme(N):
4     """Two-step Adams--Bashforth scheme for alpha(t)=beta(t)=i"""
5     h = 1 / N

```

```

6
7     # Starting values using Euler method
8     E_X0 = math.exp(1)
9     E_X1 = math.exp(1) * (1 + 1.5 * h)
10
11     E_X = [E_X0, E_X1]
12
13     for n in range(0, N - 1):
14         E_X_n2 = (1 + 2.25 * h) * E_X[n + 1] - 0.75 * h * E_X[n]
15         E_X.append(E_X_n2)
16
17     return E_X[N]
18
19 def compute_table_3():
20     """Table 3: Two-step scheme with alpha(t)=beta(t)=i"""
21     N_values = [8, 16]
22     results = []
23
24     for N in N_values:
25         h = 1 / N
26         approx = two_step_scheme(N)
27         exact = math.exp(1 + 1.5)
28         error = abs(exact - approx)
29
30         results.append((N, h, approx, exact, error))

```

```
31
32     return results
```

A.3.3 Two-step Adams–Moulton Scheme

```
1 import numpy as np
2
3 def two_step_adams_moulton(h, N):
4     """
5     Compute numerical approximation using 2-step Adams--Moulton
6     scheme.
7
8     Parameters:
9     h : step size
10    N : number of steps (total time T = N*h)
11
12    Returns:
13    y_N : numerical approximation at t_N
14    """
15
16    kappa = 3/2 # Constant from the ODE
17
18    # Initial values
19    y0 = np.e # E[X_0 Z] = e
20    y1 = y0 * (1 + kappa * h) # Euler scheme for y_1
21
22    # Pre-compute coefficients
```

```

21     coeff1 = (1 + (2/3) * h * kappa) / (1 - (5/12) * h * kappa)
22     coeff2 = ((1/12) * h * kappa) / (1 - (5/12) * h * kappa)
23
24     # Initialize array
25     y = np.zeros(N + 1)
26     y[0] = y0
27     y[1] = y1
28
29     # Adams--Moulton recurrence
30     for n in range(0, N - 1):
31         y[n + 2] = coeff1 * y[n + 1] - coeff2 * y[n]
32
33     return y[N]
34
35 def exact_solution(t):
36     """
37     Exact solution of the ODE: dy/dt = (3/2)y, y(0) = e
38     """
39     return np.e * np.exp((3/2) * t)
40
41 def main():
42     # Total time
43     T = 1.0
44
45     # Cases considered

```

```

46     cases = [
47         {"N": 8, "h": 0.125},
48         {"N": 16, "h": 0.0625}
49     ]
50
51     print(f"{'N':<4} {'h':<12} {'E(X_N z(w))':<18} {'E(X(t_N)
52           z(w))':<18} {'Absolute Error':<15}")
53
54     print("-" * 75)
55
56     for case in cases:
57
58         N = case["N"]
59         h = case["h"]
60
61         approx = two_step_adams_moulton(h, N)
62         exact = exact_solution(N * h)
63         error = abs(exact - approx)
64
65         print(f"{'N':<4} {'h':<12.6f} {'approx':<18.8f} {'exact':<18.8f}
66               {'error':<15.8f}")
67
68     if __name__ == "__main__":
69         main()

```

A.4 Python Codes for Lagrange Quadrature Scheme

A.4.1 Example 1

```
1 import numpy as np
2 from scipy.special import legendre
3 import scipy.linalg
4
5 class LagrangianQuadratureSolver:
6     def __init__(self, n_nodes=5):
7         self.n_nodes = n_nodes
8         # Get Legendre polynomial roots (these are the u_p
9         # values)
10        self.u_nodes = np.array([0.000000, 0.538469, -0.538469,
11        0.906180, -0.906180])
12
13        self.compute_lagrange_coeffs()
14        self.compute_quadrature_matrix()
15
16    def compute_lagrange_coeffs(self):
17        """Compute Lagrange polynomial coefficients at u = -1
18        and u = 1"""
19        self.L_minus1 = np.zeros(self.n_nodes)
20        self.L_plus1 = np.zeros(self.n_nodes)
21
22        for p in range(self.n_nodes):
23            product_minus1 = 1.0
```

```

20     product_plus1 = 1.0
21     denominator = 1.0
22
23     for k in range(self.n_nodes):
24         if k != p:
25             product_minus1 *= (-1 - self.u_nodes[k])
26             product_plus1 *= (1 - self.u_nodes[k])
27             denominator *= (self.u_nodes[p] -
28                             self.u_nodes[k])
29
30     self.L_minus1[p] = product_minus1 / denominator
31     self.L_plus1[p] = product_plus1 / denominator
32
33 def compute_quadrature_matrix(self):
34     """Compute the quadrature coefficient matrix
35      $a^{\{(1)\}_{mp}}$ """
36     # Legendre polynomial P5(u) and its derivative
37     P5 = legendre(5)
38     P5_coeffs = P5.coefficients
39     # Manual derivative calculation
40     P5_prime_coeffs = np.polyder(P5_coeffs)
41     P5_prime = np.poly1d(P5_prime_coeffs)
42
43     self.A = np.zeros((self.n_nodes, self.n_nodes))

```

```

43     for m in range(self.n_nodes):
44         for p in range(self.n_nodes):
45             if m == p:
46                 self.A[m, p] = self.u_nodes[p] / (1 -
47                     self.u_nodes[p]**2)
48             else:
49                 numerator = P5_prime(self.u_nodes[m])
50                 denominator = (self.u_nodes[m] -
51                     self.u_nodes[p]) *
52                     P5_prime(self.u_nodes[p])
53                 self.A[m, p] = numerator / denominator
54
55 def exact_solution_68(self, t):
56     """Exact solution for equation (6.8)"""
57     return np.exp(0.5 * np.exp(2*t) - t - 0.5)
58
59 def solve_subinterval(self, t0, T, initial_condition):
60     """
61     Solve the differential equation on subinterval [t0, T]
62     """
63     def t_from_u(u):
64         return (T - t0) * (u + 1) / 2 + t0
65
66     # Create the system of equations
67     # We have 5 unknowns:  $X_{\{\eta, \xi, p\}}$  for  $p=1, \dots, 5$ 

```

```

65     # We'll use equations for m=2,3,4,5 and the initial
        condition
66
67     A_system = np.zeros((self.n_nodes, self.n_nodes))
68     b_system = np.zeros(self.n_nodes)
69
70     # Use equations for m=2,3,4,5 (skip m=0 for residual)
71     equation_indices = [1, 2, 3, 4] # Using m=2,3,4,5
        (0-indexed: 1,2,3,4)
72
73     for i, m in enumerate(equation_indices):
74         u_m = self.u_nodes[m]
75         coeff = 0.5 * (T - t0) * (np.exp((T - t0) * u_m + T
        + t0) - 1)
76
77         for p in range(self.n_nodes):
78             A_system[i, p] = self.A[m, p]
79
80             # The equation is: sum(A[m,p] * X_p) = coeff * X_m
81             # So: sum(A[m,p] * X_p) - coeff * X_m = 0
82             A_system[i, m] -= coeff
83             b_system[i] = 0.0
84
85     # Add initial condition as the 5th equation
86     for p in range(self.n_nodes):

```

```

87         A_system[4, p] = self.L_minus1[p]
88     b_system[4] = initial_condition
89
90     # Solve the system
91     try:
92         X_solution = scipy.linalg.solve(A_system, b_system)
93     except scipy.linalg.LinAlgError:
94         # Use least squares if system is singular
95         X_solution = scipy.linalg.lstsq(A_system,
96                                         b_system)[0]
97
98     # Calculate residual using the superfluous equation (m=0)
99     u_0 = self.u_nodes[0]
100    coeff_0 = 0.5 * (T - t0) * (np.exp((T - t0) * u_0 + T +
101    t0) - 1)
102    lhs = np.dot(self.A[0, :], X_solution)
103    rhs = coeff_0 * X_solution[0]
104    residual = abs(lhs - rhs)
105
106    # Compute results table
107    results = []
108
109    for p in range(self.n_nodes):
110        u_p = self.u_nodes[p]
111        t_p = t_from_u(u_p)
112        computed_val = X_solution[p]

```

```

110     exact_val = self.exact_solution_68(t_p)
111     abs_error = abs(computed_val - exact_val)
112
113     results.append({
114         'u_p': u_p,
115         't_p': t_p,
116         'computed': computed_val,
117         'exact': exact_val,
118         'abs_error': abs_error
119     })
120
121     # Add the endpoint at u=1 (t=T)
122     t_end = t_from_u(1.0)
123     computed_end = np.dot(self.L_plus1, X_solution)
124     exact_end = self.exact_solution_68(t_end)
125     abs_error_end = abs(computed_end - exact_end)
126
127     results.append({
128         'u_p': 1.0,
129         't_p': t_end,
130         'computed': computed_end,
131         'exact': exact_end,
132         'abs_error': abs_error_end
133     })
134

```

```

135     return results, residual, X_solution
136
137 def main():
138     print("Lagrangian Quadrature Method for Differential
139           Equations")
140
141     print("=" * 60)
142
143     # Initialize solver
144     solver = LagrangianQuadratureSolver(n_nodes=5)
145
146     # Print quadrature nodes and Lagrange coefficients
147     print("\nQuadrature Nodes and Lagrange Coefficients:")
148     print(f"{'p':<2} {'u_p':<12} {'L_p(-1)':<18} {'L_p(1)':<18}")
149     print("-" * 55)
150
151     for p in range(solver.n_nodes):
152         print(f"{p+1:<2} {solver.u_nodes[p]:<12.6f}
153               {solver.L_minus1[p]:<18.10f}
154               {solver.L_plus1[p]:<18.10f}")
155
156     # Print quadrature matrix
157     print("\nQuadrature Coefficient Matrix A:")
158     print(f"{'i/j':<4} {'1':<15} {'2':<15} {'3':<15} {'4':<15}
159           {'5':<15}")
160     print("-" * 85)
161     for i in range(solver.n_nodes):

```

```

156     row_str = " ".join([f"{solver.A[i, j]:<15.6f}" for j in
157         range(solver.n_nodes)])
158
159     print(f"{i+1:<4} {row_str}")
160
161     # Define subintervals
162     subintervals = [
163         (0.0, 0.1),
164         (0.1, 0.3),
165         (0.3, 0.5),
166         (0.5, 0.7),
167         (0.7, 0.9),
168         (0.9, 1.0)
169     ]
170
171     # Solve for each subinterval
172     initial_condition = 1.0
173     previous_solution = None
174
175     for i, (t0, T) in enumerate(subintervals):
176         print(f"\n\nSubinterval [{t0}, {T}]")
177         print("=" * 80)
178
179         if i == 0:
180             ic = initial_condition
181         else:

```

```

180         ic = np.dot(solver.L_plus1, previous_solution)
181
182     results, residual, current_solution =
183         solver.solve_subinterval(t0, T, ic)
184     previous_solution = current_solution
185
186     # Print transformation info
187     if T - t0 == 0.1:
188         print("Transformation: u = 20t - 1, t = (1 + u)/20")
189     elif T - t0 == 0.2:
190         print("Transformation: u = 10t - 2, t = (2 + u)/10")
191     else:
192         print(f"Transformation: u = {2/(T-t0):.0f}t -
193             {(T+t0)/(T-t0):.0f}, t = (u +
194             {(T+t0)/(T-t0):.0f})/{2/(T-t0):.0f}")
195
196     # Print results table
197     print(f"\n{'u_p':<10} {'t_p':<12} {'Computed':<20}
198         {'Exact':<20} {'Abs Error':<15}")
199     print("-" * 85)
200     for result in results:
201         print(f"{result['u_p']:<10.6f}
202             {result['t_p']:<12.8f} "
203             f"{result['computed']:<20.10f}
204             {result['exact']:<20.10f} ")

```

```

199         f"{result['abs_error']:<15.2e}")
200
201     print(f"\nResidual error for the subinterval =
202           {residual:.6e}")
203
204 if __name__ == "__main__":
205     main()

```

A.4.2 Example 2

```

1 import numpy as np
2 from scipy.special import legendre
3 import scipy.linalg
4
5 class QuantumLagrangianSolver:
6     def __init__(self, n_nodes=5):
7         self.n_nodes = n_nodes
8         # Legendre polynomial roots (u_p values)
9         self.u_nodes = np.array([0.000000, 0.538469, -0.538469,
10                                  0.906180, -0.906180])
11         self.compute_lagrange_coeffs()
12         self.compute_quadrature_matrix()
13
14     def compute_lagrange_coeffs(self):
15         """Compute Lagrange polynomial coefficients at u = -1
16           and u = 1"""

```

```

15     self.L_minus1 = np.zeros(self.n_nodes)
16     self.L_plus1 = np.zeros(self.n_nodes)
17
18     for p in range(self.n_nodes):
19         product_minus1 = 1.0
20         product_plus1 = 1.0
21         denominator = 1.0
22
23         for k in range(self.n_nodes):
24             if k != p:
25                 product_minus1 *= (-1 - self.u_nodes[k])
26                 product_plus1 *= (1 - self.u_nodes[k])
27                 denominator *= (self.u_nodes[p] -
28                                 self.u_nodes[k])
29
30         self.L_minus1[p] = product_minus1 / denominator
31         self.L_plus1[p] = product_plus1 / denominator
32
33     def compute_quadrature_matrix(self):
34         """Compute the quadrature coefficient matrix
35          $a^{\{1\}}_{\{mp\}}$ """
36         # Legendre polynomial P5(u) and its derivative
37         P5 = legendre(5)
38         P5_coeffs = P5.coefficients
39         P5_prime_coeffs = np.polyder(P5_coeffs)

```

```

38     P5_prime = np.polyld(P5_prime_coeffs)
39
40     self.A = np.zeros((self.n_nodes, self.n_nodes))
41
42     for m in range(self.n_nodes):
43         for p in range(self.n_nodes):
44             if m == p:
45                 self.A[m, p] = self.u_nodes[p] / (1 -
46                     self.u_nodes[p]**2)
47             else:
48                 numerator = P5_prime(self.u_nodes[m])
49                 denominator = (self.u_nodes[m] -
50                     self.u_nodes[p]) *
51                     P5_prime(self.u_nodes[p])
52                 self.A[m, p] = numerator / denominator
53
54     def exact_solution(self, t):
55         """Exact solution:  $\exp(1 + (3/2)t)$ """
56         return np.exp(1 + 1.5 * t)
57
58     def solve_subinterval(self, t0, T, initial_condition):
59         """
60         Solve the quantum stochastic equation on subinterval
61             [t0, T]
62         """

```

```

59     # Determine transformation parameters based on interval
        length
60     interval_length = T - t0
61     if abs(interval_length - 0.1) < 1e-10: # [0,0.1] or
        similar
62         def t_from_u(u):
63             return (interval_length * (u + 1) / 2) + t0
64     elif abs(interval_length - 0.2) < 1e-10: # [0.1,0.3]
65         def t_from_u(u):
66             return (interval_length * (u + 1) / 2) + t0
67     elif abs(interval_length - 0.4) < 1e-10: # [0.3,0.7]
68         def t_from_u(u):
69             return (interval_length * (u + 1) / 2) + t0
70     else: # [0.7,1.0]
71         def t_from_u(u):
72             return (interval_length * (u + 1) / 2) + t0
73
74     # Create the system of equations
75     A_system = np.zeros((self.n_nodes, self.n_nodes))
76     b_system = np.zeros(self.n_nodes)
77
78     # Use equations for m=2,3,4,5 (skip m=0 for residual)
79     equation_indices = [1, 2, 3, 4] # Using m=2,3,4,5
        (0-indexed: 1,2,3,4)
80

```

```

81     for i, m in enumerate(equation_indices):
82         coeff = 0.75 * (T - t0) # 3/4 * (T - t0)
83
84         for p in range(self.n_nodes):
85             A_system[i, p] = self.A[m, p]
86
87             # The equation is: sum(A[m,p] * X_p) = coeff * X_m
88             A_system[i, m] -= coeff
89             b_system[i] = 0.0
90
91             # Add initial condition as the 5th equation
92             for p in range(self.n_nodes):
93                 A_system[4, p] = self.L_minus1[p]
94             b_system[4] = initial_condition
95
96             # Solve the system
97             try:
98                 X_solution = scipy.linalg.solve(A_system, b_system)
99             except scipy.linalg.LinAlgError:
100                 # Use least squares if system is singular
101                 X_solution = scipy.linalg.lstsq(A_system,
102                                                  b_system)[0]
103
104             # Calculate residual using the superfluous equation (m=0)
105             coeff_0 = 0.75 * (T - t0) # 3/4 * (T - t0)

```

```

105     lhs = np.dot(self.A[0, :], X_solution)
106     rhs = coeff_0 * X_solution[0]
107     residual = abs(lhs - rhs)
108
109     # Compute results table
110     results = []
111     for p in range(self.n_nodes):
112         u_p = self.u_nodes[p]
113         t_p = t_from_u(u_p)
114         computed_val = X_solution[p]
115         exact_val = self.exact_solution(t_p)
116         abs_error = abs(computed_val - exact_val)
117
118         results.append({
119             'u_p': u_p,
120             't_p': t_p,
121             'computed': computed_val,
122             'exact': exact_val,
123             'abs_error': abs_error
124         })
125
126     # Add the endpoint at u=1 (t=T)
127     t_end = t_from_u(1.0)
128     computed_end = np.dot(self.L_plus1, X_solution)
129     exact_end = self.exact_solution(t_end)

```

```

130     abs_error_end = abs(computed_end - exact_end)
131
132     results.append({
133         'u_p': 1.0,
134         't_p': t_end,
135         'computed': computed_end,
136         'exact': exact_end,
137         'abs_error': abs_error_end
138     })
139
140     return results, residual, X_solution
141
142 def main():
143     print("Quantum Stochastic Differential Equation Solver")
144     print("Example 2: Lagrangian Quadrature Method")
145     print("=" * 70)
146
147     # Initialize solver
148     solver = QuantumLagrangianSolver(n_nodes=5)
149
150     # Define subintervals for Example 2
151     subintervals = [
152         (0.0, 0.1),
153         (0.1, 0.3),
154         (0.3, 0.7),

```

```

155         (0.7, 1.0)
156     ]
157     # Print transformation formulas
158     transformations = {
159         (0.0, 0.1): ("u = 20t - 1", "t = (1 + u)/20"),
160         (0.1, 0.3): ("u = 10t - 2", "t = (2 + u)/10"),
161         (0.3, 0.7): ("u = 5t - 2.5", "t = (2.5 + u)/5"),
162         (0.7, 1.0): ("u = (20/3)t - (17/3)", "t = (3/20)(u +
163                     17/3)")
164     }
165     # Solve for each subinterval
166     initial_condition = np.exp(1) # E_w[z(w)] = e
167     previous_solution = None
168
169     for i, (t0, T) in enumerate(subintervals):
170         print(f"\nSubinterval [{t0}, {T}]")
171         print("-" * 70)
172
173         u_formula, t_formula = transformations.get((t0, T), ("u
174             = transformation", "t = transformation"))
175         print(f"Transformation: {u_formula}, {t_formula}")
176
177         if i == 0:
178             ic = initial_condition
179         else:

```

```

178         ic = np.dot(solver.L_plus1, previous_solution)
179
180     results, residual, current_solution =
181         solver.solve_subinterval(t0, T, ic)
182     previous_solution = current_solution
183
184     # Print results table
185     print(f"\n{'u_p':<12} {'t_p':<12} {'Computed':<20}
186           {'Exact':<20} {'Abs Error':<15}")
187     print("-" * 85)
188     for result in results:
189         print(f"{result['u_p']:<12.6f}
190               {result['t_p']:<12.8f} "
191               f"{result['computed']:<20.10f}
192               {result['exact']:<20.10f} "
193               f"{result['abs_error']:<15.2e}")
194
195     print(f"\nResidual error for the subinterval =
196           {residual:.6e}")
197
198     # Print exact solution formula
199     print(f"Exact solution: exp(1 + (3/2)t)")
200
201 if __name__ == "__main__":
202     main()

```

Appendix B

Plots

B.1 Linear Experiment Using the Linear Multi-step Scheme

B.1.1 Table 6.3

B.1.2 Table 6.4

B.1.3 Table 6.5

B.2 Linear Experiment Using the Lagrangian Quadrature Scheme

B.2.1 Example 1

Sub-interval [0.0, 0.1]

Sub-interval [0.1, 0.3]

Sub-interval [0.3, 0.5]

Sub-interval [0.5, 0.7]

B.2.2 Example 2

Sub-interval [0.0, 0.1]

Sub-interval [0.1, 0.3]

Sub-interval [0.3, 0.7]

Sub-interval [0.7, 1.0]

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